

**MOVING AWAY FROM ZIONISM:
REFLECTIONS ON IDENTITY CHANGE AMONG ISRAELI AND
DIASPORA JEWS, AND THE ISRAELI-PALESTINIAN CONFLICT**

シオニズムからの脱却:

イスラエル在住ユダヤ人およびディアスポラ在住ユダヤ人の
アイデンティティー変容およびイスラエル-パレスチナ紛争の考察

**Division of Public Administration
International Christian University Graduate School**

国際基督教大学 大学院行政学研究科

May 16, 2011
2011年5月16日

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Introduction

This work will discuss processes of changes in identity occurring amongst Jewish Israelis and Diaspora Jews, by which they distance themselves from Zionism. It will present interviews done in Israel with actors directly involved with political and social activism, which came about as a direct result of changes they have gone through regarding their identity. Through one way or another these individuals who have been socialized in 'standard' Zionist environment, come to realize the reality they encounter first hand is different from the one they were brought up to expect. This realization often causes an identity crisis, since the gap between expectation and reality involve profound moral contradictions for these individuals. They see themselves as being part of a collective that holds a moral discourse while hiding underneath it immoral practices. Processes of identity crisis may vary in length and triggers may vary in form, but as we will see it is possible to identify similarities in patterns and results.

The relevance of this work lies in the relation between identity and conflict, in how identity might contribute to conflict and how changes in otherwise bellicose identity might contribute to conflict resolution. As I will show throughout the theoretical discussion, the way Zionist identity is built, it seem to present little possibility but to disrespect the rights of the 'other', the Palestinians, thus contributing immensely to generating and sustaining the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. The more ample question that rises when observing the identity changes mentioned above would be regarding the political implications those changes might have. This implies in drawing relations between identity, politics and foreign policy. Although I will discuss these relations as well, the questions this work attempts to focus on are more fundamental: the reasons for such changes to happen and the processes by which they occur. The changes observed, although in

small number, have turned Jewish individuals to proactively engage in political activity, pushing for social change in opposition to Zionist precepts, as well as Israeli policies towards Palestinians, which contrary to widely held perceptions that merge Jewish and Zionist identities into one, may serve as evidence of the non-essential character of Zionist identity in Jewish individuals.

A better understanding of the questions dealt with in this work, related to the larger scenario of social change, politics and the conflict, might be useful to approaches of conflict transformation. Official political approaches of leaderships on both sides for dealing with the Israeli-Palestinian conflict through negotiations and third-party brokers have proven disastrous, contributing if anything to throwbacks while raising questions regarding the real intensions behind the declared ones. These political endeavors operate superficially, ignoring that political decision-making, interests and expectation of constituents are all subjected to an identity-paradigm. The identity question is obviously left out, seemingly imperceptible, as the anecdote would suggest water is to fish. Nevertheless, Ghazi-Bouillon (2009, p. 144) concludes "Questions of history and identity lie symbolically at the heart of the peace process, inspiring political participation at both grass-roots and elite levels." However, progressive approaches to conflict transformation have suggested 'identity' to be central in processes of reconciliation and restorative justice, and it has been suggested by a few of them to employ processes of 'identity change'.

It is possible to find relevant literature regarding identity questions in this matter, but mostly remaining on a more collective 'national identity' approach and analysis, rather than looking at the phenomenon I examine in this paper. Additionally the progressive approaches I mention above also deal with the identity issue, but ignore the organic form by which it happens in Israeli society, and suggest 'identity change' in artificial settings where they are unlikely to bare results.

By no means do I intend to lay full responsibility for the misfortune of the Palestinian people on the Zionist camp, since a lot can be said for the choice of response to an aggression or oppression, and for internal organizing and leadership, and Palestinians have had insurmountable troubles regarding those

issues, and still do. However, it is unwise to not take into consideration differences in power while accessing conflict and reflecting on its core causes, and by all means I do affirm that Zionist camp has been abounding in those, and has far larger responsibility in generating and sustaining this conflict than it and its constituency would like to admit.

In the introduction I will discuss the genesis of the research, as I believe the reader will have a better perspective of my arguments by knowing how my own experience of identity change has affected my thinking. I will cover briefly a historical background, which aims to draft the sequence of main events relevant to the Israeli-Palestinians conflict. As I move to part I, in which I will cover the theoretical discussion of the thesis, I discuss in chapter 1 fundamental concepts and theory for this work. I define what I mean by 'Zionism', in order to make a clearer analysis of the interviews and be able to point out the identity changes departing from this definition. I also define concepts of victimhood and perception of threat, both out of respect to victims and their pain, past and present, and to point out that this work does not consider use of victimhood as based on ill intent, rather on a perception of threat that feels *real*, however unreal it might possibly be. I also discuss the theoretical framework in this chapter, which requires a better understanding of the perspective from which I am approaching the matter at hand, namely New Israeli History and post-Zionism.

In chapter 2 I move to an in-depth discussion of the major concept of this work, Zionist identity, and its three constituting pillars. First, *Jewishness*, the rationale that legitimized Jews having right to the land of Israel. Within that section I discuss relations of *Jewishness* to theories of nationalism and to historical narrative. Second, I discuss *security/militarism*, which is the highly militarized character of Israel due to a constant perception of threat, which is constitutive of Zionist identity. Third, I discuss *hegemonic Zionism* and its paradigmatic nature and dominance through attainment of consent from its Jewish constituency. In chapter 3 I discuss general concepts of identity and draw relations between these concepts and the identity change processes this work presents. . In chapter 4 I draw relations between the phenomenon of identity change examined in this work with the disciplines of political science and international relations, and point out

the relevance of the knowledge that emerges of this study. I also draw relations with the discipline of conflict resolution in order to point out what kind of contribution this study might offer.

In Part II of the thesis I enter the discussion of data collected through interviews in Israel in relation to the theoretical discussion of Part I. Chapter 5 presents data and discussion relating to Zionist socialization, which are the processes by which the interviewees acquired their Zionist identity. I look into aspects of narrative, education Diaspora and culture. In chapter 6 I move to the process of de-identification, where I show and discuss how the interviewees went through processes, at the end of which they did not identify themselves with Zionist identity any longer. In chapter 7 I try to assert what kind of identity the interviewees are building or moving to after their process of change, and how they identify themselves now.

Research Genesis

In order to understand the genesis of this research it is imperative to know more about the researcher *himself*, or should I say *myself*, since without such background knowledge it would be hard to grasp the insight brought about by a pragmatically observed phenomenon. Let it be said that this understanding will be valuable for a better reading of the experiences described in the interviews collected in the field, since my experiences in many ways resemble the informers'.

My Polish maternal grandparents survived the Holocaust and went to South America, while my Hungarian paternal grandparents escaped it before it happened reaching the same destination. Both my parents were born in South America, where they became very active in the Jewish community, taking part in a Zionist youth movement called *Irgun Maginei Israel* (Hebrew for Organization of the Defenders of Israel). They met in this youth movement, and in the wake of the 1967 war they immigrated to Israel. The immigration of Jews to Israel is called in Hebrew *Alyiah*, meaning "ascent" or "going up". *Alyiah* is one of the basic tenets of Zionism, which discursively creates positive value for Jews who immigrate to Israel. It works in tandem with the concept of 'negation of the exile', which had

argued there is no future for Jewish life outside Israel. The term has both a geographical and metaphysical meaning, since Jerusalem is located on higher ground, however in Hebrew '*Alyiah la regel*' means pilgrimage, and the relation becomes quite explicit. Additionally, when Jews decide to move away from Israel, the term given is the opposite, '*Yerida*', meaning descent, and has a negative value attached to it.

I was born in Haifa in 1971, and grew up in Holon, near Tel Aviv, where my sister was later born. My first childhood memory is from age 2, when I was in the anti-air-strike bunker with my parents and our building neighbors during the 1973 Yom-Kippur war. During the time I lived in Israel, Judaism was a 'given'. Everyone around me was Jewish, but for an Arab (Arab, rather than Palestinian, is to this day the way Israeli Jews commonly refer to the Palestinians) here and there, was it a worker on my uncle's farm or a Bedouin near the road on the way to the Dead Sea, the Negev Desert, or Eilat on the coast of the Red Sea. While I grew up, difference and 'otherness' I witnessed were mainly between Jewish sub-groups. There were the various religious groups, the traditional Jews, *Mizrahi*¹ Jews and so on, which were in many ways quite different from my European-descendent (now mixed with South American culture as well) secular Judaism.

I attended school until the 8th grade in Israel, and the normality included security issues on a daily basis. We were educated to never touch any garbage bags on the street, any objects were they new or old, that appeared to have been left behind by someone. If you would see a brand new *walkman* (portable cassette player), the procedure would be to call the police, and they would come with a robot that would pick up the object, and drop it into one of the thousands of 'security holes' spread around Israeli cities. There, the police would explode the *walkman*, not taking any risks of it being a bomb left by a terrorist. My father, as any of my friends' fathers, would serve the army once a year for 30 days. He would come back home and bring his weapon, wearing military uniform. My uncle is a war hero, having been wounded in the war and suffering terrible pains in his leg to this day. We all wanted to be soldiers as children, and our games were

¹ Jews are generally divided into three major categories: *Ashkenazi*, German Jews; *Sefaradi*, Jews from the Iberian Peninsula and North Africa, and *Mizrahi*, Jews from (other) Arabic and Muslim countries

often to re-enact the Entebbe operation where the IDF had rescued Israeli hostages from terrorists. I had never been religious, but I was very proud to have my *Bar-Mitzva* at the Wailing Wall in Jerusalem. At the same time I was relieved since it was much easier than doing it the more common way, in a synagogue, since I hardly had to learn any lines by heart. As much as I was a playful child, and in school not very good student, I kept the utmost reverence during ceremonies we used to have every year for the remembrance of the fallen in battle, and the ones murdered in the Holocaust. My grandparents had survived the Holocaust while all their families had been murdered. Our family was always very small because of that, and I grew with my cousins as close as brothers, partly because we were all we had. I remember hearing here and there my grandparents hinting or saying something about their memories from the Holocaust, but never fully articulated stories. It was so painful that no one wanted to bring it up. All of these elements I mention are discussed in this work as fundamental parts of Zionist identity analysis: Jewishness, security, militarism and the Holocaust.

In 1985 my family left Israel and moved back to South America, to Brazil, where the friends I made were all Jewish, since they were the offspring of my parent's previous social circle. I tried studying in a regular Brazilian school when I arrived, but adaptation was so hard that I asked to be transferred to a Jewish high school, where I immediately felt at home. I practiced sports at *Hebraica*, the Jewish sports club and socialized only with Jewish friends. I recall having some non-Jewish acquaintances, and having thoughts cross my mind such as: "*they're not Jewish, they're not Arabs... what are they? What fulfills their empty lives?*" It was such a foreign concept for me to imagine a whole universe and diversity existing outside my small world. I was fourteen at the time, and I immediately joined a Zionist youth movement called *Chazit Hanoar* (Hebrew for The Youth Front), where I spent most of the following decade, initially as a pupil, and later as an educator. The ideological platform of the movement was to educate Jewish youth to be Zionist, and possibly 'ascend' to Israel, or as it is used in common day-to-day communication, 'make *aliyah*'. Its declared goal was also to teach critical thought, which is an interesting way to notice hegemony, where all discussions, critique

and epistemological questions are subjected to limits established by hegemonic discourse, in this case Zionism.

At age 18 I went to Israel to take a year off before college. During this year I made a few good friends, and met some of my old friends who were all in military conscription age, about to enlist. I felt compelled to do the same, and started all the procedures of enlistment. I cannot recall any nationalistic sentiment that was pushing me to do it, rather it was more a will to belong, and to go through what all 'worthy' members of that group went through. In the very last moment, I felt my family ties were much stronger than my desire to remain for three years away from them in the IDF (Israel Defense Force), and I decided to go back to Brazil and start my adult life there by going to college. In Sao Paulo I went back to the Zionist Jewish youth movement for few more years and enrolled in university.

As time went by I started taking interest in other activities, which slowly took me out of the Jewish circle. I met my wife, who is not Jewish, and moved away from São Paulo to a small town on the triple border with Argentina and Paraguay, famous for its majestic Iguassu Falls. For the first time in my life I was living in a place where there was no Jewish community. I went back to university for a second time and got an undergraduate degree in *Letras* (Letters in Portuguese), which is a full teaching license and Bachelors degree in Linguistics, Languages and Literature. At the end of this course I wrote a graduation thesis on the Israeli-Palestinian Conflict, entitled "The Use of Cinematographic Language in Humanizing the Image of the Enemy: The Case of the Israeli Palestinian conflict". The research for that paper triggered the process that led up to this research you are reading now. For the first time, I had contact with literature that had never been presented to me before, and had not known to look for it. It was the writings of the New Israeli Historians and of Post Zionist scholars. I found it shocking and at the same time fascinating. The writings were shocking to me because they had shown me Israeli history was largely made of myths that served a nationalist agenda. What for me was once fact, celebrated through national commemorations, film and television, common popular understanding and taught in state schools through schoolbooks as the official knowledge, now was being shattered by scientists with the same level of authority and credibility as those who had written

the schoolbooks. In point of fact, these authors seemed to me as even more authoritative than the ones who ruled the field of 'official knowledge', since they were criticizing their own history and state, their own identity and people, using data they had collected from their own government's official records. To me, besides their sound scholarly references and work, they seemed to have a noble agenda: truth and justice before the demand for peace. The official documents these scholars used registered a radically different history from the one officially transmitted in Israel and in Jewish communities around the world. In this new version, Zionists had been the stronger party during the struggle for Statehood, and continued to be afterwards; they planned carefully and executed an ethnic cleansing of the Palestinian indigenous population; and they were not peace-seeking, but aggressive towards both the native Palestinians and other Arab neighbors, and pursued a land-grabbing, settler and expansionist agenda.

To discover these things meant the moral superiority that had played such an important role in Israeli and Jewish self-perception in regard to the process, by which Israel was founded, had never existed. I felt lost all justification, legitimacy and victimhood I had been fed all my life, and that I upheld as being part of the Israeli collective. It also meant that the anger Palestinians felt was not only understandable, but also justified. Although notions of collective social identity such as Jewish nationalism, or Zionism, were only a part of my personal identity, the feeling I had was of my whole person being completely overwhelmed, as if my only identity was Zionist, which now, given this new information I had been researching, was wrong, sinful and guilty. Having left Israel at the age of fourteen, I had never served the army, I had never killed a Palestinian, nor have I served as part of the oppressive regime in the Occupied Palestinian Territories. But the feeling of responsibility, guilt and sorrow were as if I had done all those things. To this day I find it hard to understand how must my friends and colleague, who went through this process and about whom I write in this work, felt in comparison to me. The way I used to think about the conflict was not very profound or elaborated. I had never once doubted that the problem in Israel/Palestine was complicated, and that the bottom-line was survival. It was us, or them. I was convinced they had always wanted to kill us because we are Jewish, which was

what I had always been taught through school, popular culture and official discourse.

I fell sick for six months, suffering from terrible headaches and inability to concentrate or do anything well. Going through a series of doctors and medical exams, I finally heard from the last one my problem was stress. Slowly I made the connection to my discoveries and how they impacted my health. I found ways to cope with the stress through digging deeper and finding ways to redefine who I was and trying to act accordingly. I did not agree with what had been done to the Palestinians in the name of Jews, and thus indirectly in my name. I wished to separate myself from the collective I used to be part of, which was responsible for the injustices committed and which had hidden them from the world. I wanted to be sure for my own sake I was not part of it anymore. I was taken by confusion and had no idea on how to do those things mainly because it was challenging to point out which collective it was I needed to separate myself from. I wondered whether I should relinquish my whole identity, all together, Zionist, Jewish and Israeli as they were so mixed together it was difficult to separate them. I could not decide whether I should become against those identities. It was very painful to consider those alternatives, since my family, whom I love dearly, is Israeli and I could not imagine being against them. I also thought about my grandparents who survived the Holocaust and how they would feel if I would relinquish my Jewish identity, and felt guilty again.

It took a while until I calmed down and found myself in a rather stable situation again, identity-wise. It was an identity question because I was trying to represent myself, to represent who I am, in a way I would be in accordance with my moral values, and not tied to some external label I did not relate to. I found myself being very critical of Zionist ideology, and how it co-opted Judaism as its integral component. I wanted to be an example of a Jew and an Israeli, which did not agree with the injustices Palestinians have suffered throughout the history of Zionism, and which stood for restorative justice for Palestinians and a vision of full equality and coexistence.

It was at this point that it occurred to me that something had happened, which besides unexpected, had been unimaginable until now. I had moved away

from being a component of one side of the Israel/Palestine conflict, and became something different. The way I was now did not represent any of the sides anymore. This meant to me that there was nothing essential in my self, in who I was, neither in having the origin I had, which forced me to be part of, and contribute to the conflict. I have ceased to desire the goals the conflict was being fought over. Only at this moment I noticed how politically distant I was from my starting point. Before this process, I had always considered I had gone as far as it was possible to go in terms of reaching out towards peace with Palestinians. I had identified with the Zionist Peace Camp and the Zionist Left. I felt I represented the forefront of peace-seeking Jews, and yet, I had still fallen so much shorter than where I had arrived after this process of change I am bringing here to discuss. The distance was enormous. I could look back and see that it is possible to believe wholeheartedly that one is completely committed to the goal of peace, that one is progressive and open, and yet still be ignorantly upholding the most aggressive beliefs or ideologies.

The thought that occurred to me was that the identity change I had gone through had disintegrated the Israel/Palestine conflict in me. I still was the same person, who came from the same background, but I was no longer party to any injustice. I now had a comprehension that allowed me to fully defend the needs Palestinians have for a dignified existence. The following thought was: if it happened to me, does it happen to other people? And if it does, *how* does it happen? Is it a similar process? Do we go through the same difficulties and suffer similar pain? And what is the end result? Do we agree on how this new way of looking at the conflict should be translated into action?

Historical Background

In this section I cover historical events relating the Zionist enterprise and the Palestinian question, in order to place the discussion over the identity changes analyzed in this work in relation to the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. I chose to place this section within the introduction since this work will not focus on history proper. This historical background is quite brief and is meant to make reference to

the main milestones in the history of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict, within which context this research will look at identity changes.

The State of Israel is the realization of Zionism, the Jewish nationalist movement that appeared in Europe at the end of the nineteenth century. Initially Zionism motivated some immigration to Palestine, starting in 1883, and over time the volume of immigration grew larger. After the First World War and the fall of the Ottoman Empire, in accordance with the Sykes-Picot agreement between Britain and France in 1916, British Mandate took control of Palestine. Zionist nationalist discourse and growing number of Jewish immigrants started creating tensions with the local Palestinian Arab population. Between 1883 and 1947, Palestinians have watched Jewish population grow from about 2% to 33% in Palestine, and according to Benny Morris (2001, p. 37) “the fear of territorial displacement and dispossession was to be the chief motor of Arab antagonism to Zionism,” much to the contrary of Ben-Gurion’s explanation, saying Jewish settlers were “being murdered [...] simply because they were Jews” (Finkelstein, 2003, p. xiii). The two main examples of that time were the Palestinian riots of 1929 and the Palestinian Revolt from 1936 to 1939, however, Morris maintains the reason for Palestinian antagonism to Zionism remained the same onwards.

Zionists continuously refer to two important historical cornerstones, which gave international approval and legitimacy to the Zionist goal of founding a Jewish State. These were the 1917 Balfour declaration in which the British promised they would support a Jewish state in Palestine, and another was the 1947 UN partition plan, which divided Palestine into two territories, one Jewish and one Arab: The United Nations General Assembly, counting with various countries that many analysts say had a feeling of debt towards the Jews in the aftermath of the Nazi Holocaust, voted on the Partition Resolution for Palestine (Laqueur & Rubin, 2008, p.69), which determined that the Palestinians, who were the majority of the population and owned most of the land, would get less than half of Palestine, and the Jewish population who were the minority and owned under six percent of the land, would get more than half of Palestine. This also determined that about half a million Palestinians would remain within the borders of the new Jewish State. Arguably, any people offered this plan would have

rejected it, simply due to its lack of balance in considering the needs on both sides, and sure enough, it was received as a blatant injustice on the Palestinian side. But at the time, decolonization had not been completed, and the ruling mentality was still insensitive to non-Western cultures, which allowed for such injustices to go unnoticed, more so due to the fact that as mentioned before, Zionist leadership was mostly European Jews, with whom the leading powers identified more.

Ilan Pappé (2006) describes how Zionist leadership had started to execute aggressive military operations against Arab villages around 1947, which reached its peak with the expulsion of over 750,000 Palestinians from their land in 1948 during what Israelis call the independence war, and Palestinians call the 'Nakba', Arabic for 'catastrophe'. Rashid Khalidi (2006, p.XXXIII) says that out of the Arab armies that had supposedly warred against Israel, the only serious military incursion into the territory of the Jewish State was the Egyptian one. In Israeli history, as well as most of the Western world that in large part has identified with Israel in its struggle for statehood, this war is remembered as the heroic war of independence, one of the founding myths of the State of Israel, This was the origin of the Palestinian refugee problem. As a result of the war, Zionists conquered another twenty two percent of the land, having the Jewish state founded on 77% of Palestine. As we will see in the section dealing with New Israeli Historiography, this version of history is contesting the Israeli official version, which has reigned unchallenged until the late 80's, and presented a narrative exempting Israel of any responsibility of the expulsion of the Palestinians. Although the new version explains Israel had military superiority throughout the war and a rather aggressive role in initiating it, traditional claims sustain Israel was the weak party, and was forced to defend itself.

The existence of Israel has been marked by intermittent wars and military operations, out of which the majority has been related with the Palestinian question. In 1967, Israel conquered from Jordan and Egypt the remaining 22% of Palestine, giving origin to the longest ongoing military occupation of our time, and turning another 250,000 Palestinians into refugees. In 1982 Israel started the Lebanon war, in the attempt to expel the Palestinian Liberation Organization's (PLO) leaders that were exiled there, who ended up escaping to Tripoli. In 1987

the Intifada (Palestinian revolt) broke out, which suffered terrible repression from Israel. Lybarger (2007) describes how in 1993 the Oslo process started to advance, and the PLO was allowed to return to the Palestinian territories to form an autonomous government, which was one of the goals of the Oslo process. Finkelstein² (2003) explains how during this process, Israel had doubled the illegal settlements in the occupied territories from 200,000 to 400,000 Jewish settlers, in clear violation of international law, and complete opposition to the Oslo peace initiative. Other attitudes such as that made the Oslo process decline and generate frustration among Palestinians who had lowered their guard hoping to finally have their state. This intensified internal conflicts among Palestinians and the wedge between the PLO and Hamas started to widen considerably.

In 2000, PLO leader Yasser Arafat rejected a peace deal offered by Israeli Prime Minister Ehud Barak at Camp David. To the Israeli public this was presented as a rejection by the Palestinian leader of the most generous offer ever made to Palestinians, seeming that nor he or his people had any interest in making peace with Israel, and which meant a violent blow to the political left and the peace camp in Israel. Shlomo Ben-Ami³, Foreign Relations Minister in Barak's government and key participant in the Camp David negotiations said "Camp David was not the missed opportunity for the Palestinians, and if I were a Palestinian I would have rejected Camp David, as well." With the right wing hard-line political leadership strengthened, tensions raised once again. Still In 2000, the Al Aqsa Intifada (second Palestinian revolt) broke out. These events radicalized the Israeli electorate and caused right wing leader Ariel Sharon to rise to power. This period was marked by the highest violence since the 1967 war, involving many Israeli military operations and various suicide bombings. In 2002, Israel invaded Jenin refugee camp in the West Bank, in what was defined by various human rights organizations as a massacre. In the same year it held the PLO headquarters under military siege with the Palestinian leader inside, which lasted

² Lecture: *An Issue Of Justice: Origins Of The Israel/Palestine Conflict*. University of California, Berkley.

³ Interview: *Democracy Now!* (April 17, 2006, www.democracynow.org)

for two years. As a result, Yasser Arafat's health was weakened, which led to his death. In 2005 Israel withdrew unilaterally from Gaza, but maintained control over its borders, aerial space and coastal line. In 2006 Israel fought Lebanon again, this time against Hezbollah, who were trying to get Israel to leave an occupied Lebanese territory next to the border called the Shebaa Farms.

In 2006 Hamas was elected to government by a landslide, in the first transparent and internationally supervised elections in the region. Fatah, late Arafat's faction that was leading the Palestinian National Authority up until the lost elections, backed by US government (Rose, 2008) entered in violent confrontation with Hamas, which resulted in a split in power where Hamas remained in control of Gaza and the Palestinian Authority in control of the West Bank. Israel put a military siege on Gaza, which escalated and resulted in the Gaza War in December of 2008 and January 2009. The war has been investigated by the UN Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR), which commissioned an inquiry mission led by Judge Goldstone has found that Israel has committed war crimes during the Gaza war, in which 1,400 Palestinians and 13 Israelis were killed⁴. Although Judge Goldstone has retracted the accusation the Israel has targeted civilians deliberately as a policy, various human rights organizations maintain that this question remains open, among which are B'Tzelem, the Israeli center for human rights in the OPT and, *Braking the Silence*, which has collected testimonials from IDF soldiers who took part in the Gaza war where they relate the orders were to shoot at everything that moved (BBC, 2009). Israel had been found guilty for committing war crimes in the 2006 Lebanon war as well, and has been found guilty for violating international law and human rights on many accounts. It has been ordered to dismantle the West Bank separation wall by the International Court of Justice, which has ruled it illegal by a vote of 14 to 1. This wall has been annexing West Bank land to Israel illegally,

⁴ Judge Goldstone has recently acknowledged that the report was flawed and Israel did not target civilians as a policy. This caused a media storm where Israel and its supporters spun this news as a full-retraction, which of course, it was not, and did not clear Israel from the charge on which Goldstone has backed on, since Israel has still not investigated malpractice on its policy level, only on individual level, and there are still many organizations such as B'Tzelem, the Israeli center for human rights in the OPT, that did not acquit Israel of the charges of war crimes and crimes against humanity in the Gaza war (Montell, 2011).

separating farmers from their land, students from their schools, families and villages. The most recent clash that drew international attention was the Gaza Freedom Flotilla. Six ships loaded with Humanitarian aid and construction materials were headed to Gaza, organized by the Free Gaza Movement and the Turkish Foundation for Human Rights and Freedoms and Humanitarian Relief, when they were raided by the IDF in international waters. The clash was violent and there are still no conclusive results of any probe since Israel will not cooperate with international efforts to look into the matter. IDF soldiers killed eight activists on board of one ship, the *Mavi Marmara*. Israeli soldiers were seriously wounded in the clash, and Israel alleges there was weaponry amidst the humanitarian aid materials, however no convincing evidence was presented.

PART I - THEORY

1. Concepts and Theory

In the last section I described briefly the historical background of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. In this section I will look into Zionism, its structure and history, discussing aspects that will relate to the identity change processes I discuss in this work. In the following section I will discuss identity in relation to Zionism, nationalism and politics.

1.1 Zionism, victimhood and perception of threat.

Before looking into the beginning of Zionism, I will take the reader on a non-linear timeline journey: we begin from the end. Looking back, we see Zionism as quite an ample concept, and we notice the question 'what is Zionism?' would not at all be easy to answer. We could say Zionism was a nationalist movement that resulted in the creation of Israel. It was also an ideological platform that not only served as rationale for justifying the creation of Israel, but also later for its development and existence, as it still does. It became a national identity, which on the individual level generated its aspect of individual Zionist identity. Around the practices involved in Zionism, a Zionist historical narrative and a Zionist culture emerged. Throughout this process, as expected, different understandings within the Jewish constituency of what Zionism was became different currents of Zionism, among which the main ones were: Labor Zionism, based on socialist principles and agrarian settlement; Revisionist Zionism, based on conservative values and hard-line politics; Religious Zionism, mixing nationalism and religion.

For the purpose of this work, we will reduce the scope of the term Zionism to a more manageable one, and adopt three core aspects to define Zionism:

Jewishness, security/militarism and hegemonic Zionist conception of the Jewish State, which appears in this work interchangeably as *hegemonic Zionism, Zionist hegemony* or *hegemonic Zionist discourse*. The first one, *Jewishness*, refers to the premise that Judaism is central to Zionist identity, and Israel should be a Jewish State. The second one, *security/militarism*, refers to the belief Israel is under constant threat from Palestinians and other regional enemies requiring a severe security apparatus and requiring a highly militarized society in order to survive. The third one, *hegemonic Zionism*, refers to an ideological paradigm set by the founding fathers of Zionism, which defines the limits within which meaningful reasoning and debate on Zionism can take place, as well as what can be thought, imagined or said about it. Social dominance of European cultural elements inherited from that leadership result from its ascendancy over other Jewish groups, which were integrated to, or under, its hegemonic structure. In order to establish these three aspects, I draw on the work of the late Baruch Kimmerling, Hebrew University Professor of Sociology (2005, 1) who stresses Israel is “based on two deep cultural codes, common at least to its Jewish citizens-militarism and ‘Jewishness’.” I also draw on the conclusion Asima Ghazi-Bouillon reaches in her recent book (2009, p.158), where she affirms the pillars of Israeli identity “remain – ahead of other considerations – Jewishness (the boundaries of which remain undefined), security, and the hegemonic ‘Labor’ Zionist conception of Jewish State.” She recognizes that “Today, it is problematic to talk of only one form of Zionism, although [...] it is possible to identify a hegemonic form of Zionism.” Ghazi-Bouillon explains this does not mean there were no other forms of Zionism, just that they were marginal, and even opposition kept within the parameters of the hegemonic discourse. Later on, I discuss the ‘Labor’ aspect of her definition. I consider all other aspects of Zionism to be secondary to these three major pillars, in the sense they depend on these pillars or derive from them, as well as that these three pillars are transversal to all forms of Zionism today. Although the reference of both authors I cite above is to Israeli identity or culture, Israel constitutes an interesting case of being a state of all Jews, not of all its citizens, and in this sense its national identity extends over its physical borders in the form of Zionism to the Diaspora, where Zionist education and socialization is similar to that in Israel and the values instilled in its

Jewish constituents are as well. Another way of looking at this is that Zionism as a national identity intersects the notion of national identity as referring to the sense of belonging to a country or State, and the one of belonging to a 'nation' or 'people', which in this sense will include again the Jewish Diaspora. In either case, deriving from the context in which both authors have used this definition, I can affirm that both were using 'Israeli national identity' as interchangeable with 'Zionism'. Additionally, these three pillars are by no means independent; rather, they form a crystallized set, being sometimes difficult to point out the exact fault lines between them.

Another concept that may require clarification for this work is *victimhood*. By victimhood, as it is presented in this work, in my own thought and that of various authors on whose work I draw, what is meant is the political manipulation in which the *victim status* is used in order to get the upper hand or justify an attitude, relying on real past victimization situations, or on conjectures or vague possibilities of risk of future victimization, which do not concretely apply to, or justify, the situation at hand. For instance, although the Holocaust was a real event where immeasurable losses happened to Jewish people as a result of radically degrading and inhumane ideas, policies, procedures and attitudes, it does not justify giving legitimacy to Israel having aggressive policies towards Palestinians based on a perception of threat that has no correspondence in measurable facts in the present. While the perception of threat is real, the threat itself does not seem to be there. The threat that I refer to here relates to Sonnenschein, Bekerman, and Horenczyk's (2010) discussion of an ethnographic study that analyzed data gathered in a dialogue course conducted at an Israeli university among Jewish and Palestinian students, all citizens of the State of Israel:

As the process progressed, all the Jewish participants developed greater awareness of the central place that the threat holds in their national identity and the uses to which it is put. The Jewish participants developed an awareness of the circular dynamic, a trap with no way out, inherent in their need for an existential threat and victimhood as part of their national identity. The circularity is embodied in the fact that the threatened identity is where they tended to close ranks during a crisis, and where they felt safer. Closing ranks led to aggression toward the Palestinians. When the Palestinians did not cave in but instead responded to the aggression directed toward them, the Jews felt threatened and organized in turn to respond aggressively once more toward the Palestinians, thereby strengthening

their own (Jewish) national identity. The struggle with the sense of threat uses the threat as a resource. (Sonnenschein, Bekerman, and Horenczyk, 2010, pp. 62, 63)

I should mention that this concept of perception of threat has been enhanced over time by observable events such as rocket attacks from over the borders with Gaza or Lebanon, by suicide bombings, and by hate speech which sometimes is captured and vehicled by mass media and internet, occasionally from a head of State such as Mahmoud Ahmadinejad, president of Iran, and others by imams or other spiritual leaders. These attacks are associated with anti-Semitism and the Holocaust in various ways, not the least of which are speeches by Israeli political leaders. Israeli Prime Minister Netanyahu said

We will not allow the Holocaust deniers [referring to Ahmadinejad, who questions aspects of the Holocaust such as the number of victims] to carry out another Holocaust against the Jewish people. This is the supreme duty of the state of Israel. This is my supreme duty as prime minister of Israel. (Haaretz, 2009)

Additionally, Israeli President Shimon Peres said in a speech commemorating Holocaust Remembrance Day:

It is hard to fathom why despots such as Hitler the Nazi, Stalin the Bolshevik and Ahmadinejad the Persian chose the Jews as the main target for their hatred, their madness and their violence," Peres said in a speech commemorating Holocaust Remembrance Day. (Haaretz, 2009)

These images often play in Jews' minds as a prelude for the next Holocaust, which only the State of Israel can prevent. The lacking information which seems would be able to change this perception, is that Israel indeed is the strong party in these dualities, and holds wide responsibility for injustice committed against Palestinians, to which all those aggressions are in fact responses, when not plain resistance. Therefore, when use of the victim position is made based on this perception of threat, then it is to that use this work refers to as *victimhood*. It is with the utmost respect to real victimization situations in the Jewish past, such as the Nazi Holocaust, *pogroms* in Eastern Europe, and other forms of persecution and discrimination, to which any kind of victimization and discrimination must be added without any exclusiveness to Jews, that this use of the term *victimhood* is

made. It should be seen as a distinction between warranted victim status and an unwarranted one. This work acknowledges that while the use of unwarranted victim status in the present, based on past suffering such as the Holocaust as its rationale, seems to be disrespectful of those past events' victims, the perception of threat appears of becoming victims again appears to be genuine, however misguided. While the fear is real, it seems to be a result of *Zionist hegemonic discourse*, which establishes a connection in people's minds of present-day animosities towards the State of Israel and its policies to those terrible past persecutions based on discrimination. It does not allow for an understanding that those animosities are a result of Israeli aggressive actions, and as such, in this work it is deemed a misplaced sentiment.

1.2 New Israeli history and post-Zionism.

This work is written based on a theoretical framework sympathetic to New Israeli History and post-Zionism. New History emerged in the 80's and consisted of a series of publications, which contested traditional Israeli historiography. The most relevant aspect of that work to this discussion on identity is it established new parameters by which to measure responsibility in the Israeli-Palestinian conflict, challenging the Jewish place of 'victim' (Bar-On, 2004). It brings to life a debate on collective memory and identity.

Edward Said (2001, p.1) points out how, aside from land acquisition, it was the battle over the narrative of the land that was won by Zionists which was the main contributor to the success of creation of the Jewish State in 1948. Ghazi-Bouillon (2009, p.57) asserts, "Narrative is not merely a cultural tool, but one of undeniable political significance in a world of nation states. Victory is inevitably accompanied by the subjugation of competing narratives." Said points out:

Almost from the moment that the state of Israel came into being in 1948 - and although the preparations were made well before that time - the West was deluged with a whole series of narratives and images that acquired the solidarity and the legitimacy of 'truth'. In spite of the presence of a comfortable 67 per cent majority of Palestinian Arabs who owned over 90 percent of the land in 1948 (this was after decades of Jewish immigration and settlement) the world heard of an 'empty' territory whose inhabitants brutishly opposed Jewish settlement in Zion even after the Holocaust had occurred. Thereafter the myths proliferated and

formed a system which, in the West at least, it became inordinately difficult to deny. (Said, 2001, pp. 3, 4)

“Israeli historians were firmly embedded in this process”, which created a narrative that connected the Jewish people to their land (Gahzi-Bouillon, 2009, p.57). Until the emergence of the New Israeli Historians, there was no powerful enough counter-narrative that could challenge the Zionist hegemonic discourse, an important part of which was Zionist historical narrative, or the ‘official Zionist history’, as New Historians called it. Many of the facts revealed by New Israeli Historiography were not actually new discoveries. They had been published before but ignored, as was the case of the founders of the Israeli Socialist Organization known as *Matzpen* (compass) Akiva Orr and Moshe Machover, whose book *Shalom, Shalom Ve'ei Shalom* was published in 1961 (Gahzi-Bouillon, 2009, p.69). What made the New Historians’ case different was their findings were based on governmental documents declassified in 1978, according to the 30-year rule, which describes events since the period around 1948 and the war of independence. Initially these historians set out to write interesting and somewhat controversial historiography, not really grasping the extent of the impact their work would have.

New Israeli Historiography and post-Zionist scholarship are at times confused and put together in the same category. This is not the case. New historians have published on new findings, but the way they developed the newfound facts as time went by was not uniform. Ilan Pappé talks about his position and that of Benny Morris:

It took time for me to be able to translate my work that it would be a fundamental criticism of Zionism not just of Israel’s behavior in 1948, and it took time for Benny Morris to realize that all that he was doing was criticizing a certain aspect whilst he was perfectly happy with the ideology behind it. (Ghazi-Bouillon, 2009, p.64)

Both are New Historians, and both stand in opposition in their opinions of Zionism. Another position, that of New Historian Avi Shlaim, as he is quoted in a debate “I have never questioned the legitimacy of the Zionist movement or of the state of Israel within its pre-1967 borders. What I reject, and reject totally, is the

Zionist colonial project beyond the 1967 border” (Ghazi-Bouillon, 2009, p.95). Shlaim’s criticism falls only on the occupation of the West Bank and Gaza (currently not occupied but under military siege), and sees no problem in pre-1967 Israel, ignoring the 1948 independence war and expulsion of Palestinians, which is a typical position of the Zionist left. According to Ghazi-Bouillon (2009, p.95), “New History did not in itself, either by intention or consequence, undermine Israeli identity by questioning the historical foundations of Israeli society.” New Historian Benny Morris believes “new historians broadened the field – they opened the field, liberalized the field” (Ghazi-Bouillon, 2009, p.71). Daniel Bar-Tal believes that until the 70’s Israeli society and scientists shared the same belief system, and the fragmentation that occurred in the 80’s as part of its social development had set the conditions for the questions of New Historians to be heard (Ghazi-Bouillon, 2009, p.70).

These arguments point to a confluence of elements that allowed for New Historiography to emerge, and that while by itself it might have established a challenge to Zionist official historiography, it might not have established a challenge for the *Zionist hegemonic discourse* as a whole. However, it did open a window of opportunity for post-Zionist thought to establish itself and grow on a solid New Historiography base. As to the relevance of New History to the identity issue at hand, Bar-On (2004, p.2) points out that “In fact, the ongoing heated debate is not just an academic controversy; rather it seems to be a cultural struggle over identities and self-perceptions with heavy political overtones.” As we will examine further on, historical narrative and identity are connected in more than one way, and New Israeli History is fundamentally connected to the identity changes this work is looking into.

Post-Zionism is a debated framework, which merits further definition. An important distinction should be made from anti-Zionists, who according to Ophir (2008, p. 89) present a longing for a pre-Zionist age, when the world was devoid from its nationalist ideas. He says not all post-Zionists necessarily agree with anti-Zionist positions, but deem Zionism unviable. Ghazi-Bouillon (2009, p. 94) points out a definition rooted in the media, which influenced public perception in Israel of what post-Zionism is. This definition by journalist Neri Livneh, published in

Ha'aretz newspaper, considers Zionism as a legitimate Jewish national movement that has concluded its role or lost its legitimacy at a certain point in history for doing injustices to others. I reject this definition in my views and in this work, since it reflects a certain acceptance not only of the past, which is pointless, but also of the moral implications of Zionism as a theoretical concept, lacking then in a critical approach to the ideas behind it. I tend to agree with definitions of post-Zionism that go beyond the mere chronological admittance that the Zionist era is over, and that do not settle for *realpolitik* rationalizations such as that there is a *pattern* through which states are born, and *because* it is a pattern it should be accepted as 'natural' and not be subjected to critique, which to me seems an attempt to avoid the implications such critique might bring to the fore in terms of legitimacy claims. The Jewish State goes to great lengths to ensure its legitimacy in the eyes of its Jewish constituents, both in Israel and in the Diaspora, as well as the international community, which dismisses the *realpolitik* argument.

For instance, Ophir (2008, p. 94) argues that post-Zionism would be any approach that challenges the discourses of victimhood and security, saying "a critic of Zionist ideology challenges the dominant image of the Israeli Jew as someone who always already occupies the victim position." In my understanding Ophir's affirmation seem to apply to a large portion of Diaspora Jews as well, where Zionist education and socialization reproduces this self-perception. In regard to the definition of Zionism I am adopting in this work, I consider victimhood to be at the root of the second characteristic of our definition, security/militarism, which I will discuss further later on. Uri Ram (Ghazi-Bouillon, 2009, p. 7) defends "post-Zionism is a discursive strategy that attempts to strengthen Israel's civil society in opposition to growing trends of nationalism and chauvinism." Ram's understanding seems to point to a critique of the *hegemonic discourse of Zionism*, the third characteristic of Zionism in this work, which he considers to weaken Israeli society. In this definition, post-Zionism would be then a way to overcome the destructive nationalist and chauvinist Zionism, to the benefit of Israeli society. Additionally, Uri Ram (2003, p. 36) considers post-Zionism to have globalist, liberal ethos, which he sees as opposed to neo-Zionism, a counter-current that emerged as a response to post-Zionism,

which Ram characterizes as having localist, ethno-religious ethos, reinforcing Zionist foundations and trying to address the new claims presented by post-Zionists and New Historians. Information uncovered by New History pushes Zionist constituency who analyzes it, either Israeli or Diasporic, to reconsider their self-definition. Some become critically aware of the extreme nationalist paradigm they were sequestered by, which corrodes the values they believed their Zionist discourse supposedly upheld. As with New Historians, reactions to the new data vary and while some feel compelled to become critical, others, still the majority, seem to feel threatened and to become defensive. Those are the ones who according to Ram (2003, p.36) integrate these new data into a more extreme nationalist identity.

Ghazi-Bouillon's definition of post-Zionism is broader. She argues that post-Zionism is defined by its critical theoretical approach

Post-Zionism does not need to be unified by anything other than a post-positivist approach to social, cultural, political, and economic structures of power. [Post-Zionist work is] based on critical theoretical approaches [...] i.e. it questions existing structures and paradigms of knowledge within Israeli academia in regards to Israeli society. (Ghazi-Bouillon, 2009, p. 94)

In this work, I see post-Zionism as challenges to the *hegemonic Zionist discourse*, combining Ophir's challenge to the Jewish permanent victim's position, Ram's challenge maintaining that it should contribute constructively to Israeli society in whichever direction it should take it (which might be a radical change in national configuration), and Ghazi-Bouillon's less Zionist-specific definition, which allows for a dialectic between local and universal critique.

In chapter 3, I present a discussion on relations of identity to political science, international relations and conflict resolution. Since the last one provides an important part of the contextualization I intend to provide for the interviews and identity change processes analyzed, in order to establishing the relevance of this study, it is important to point out that I will approach theory of conflict resolution from a post-Zionist critical perspective as well. Approaches of conflict resolution still accepting the Zionist paradigm, at least to a certain extent, tend to perceive the conflict as two-sided where Zionist identity is a given that has to be

accepted. A critical approach would suggest that it is not a given, and should be challenged.

2 Tripartite Critique of Zionist Identity

In order to understand the processes of moving away from Zionism we should look into and understand better Zionism itself, and the academic critique of it through New History and post-Zionism. The definition for Zionism I am adopting in this work helps define more clearly what is the process of moving away from it. It also allows us to understand how these three characteristics that according to Gahzi-bouillon and Kimmerling compose an all-encompassing Zionist identity today, relate to the development of Zionism. Each of these aspects that make up the core of Zionist identity are the 'tip' of much larger 'icebergs'. The three pillars of Zionism, *Jewishness*, *security/militarism* and *hegemonic Zionism*, are also interconnected and form a cohesive internal logic amongst themselves.

2.1 Jewishness.

The notion of *Jewishness* is centered in Judaism being in some way central to Zionist identity, without having any connection to religion other than the use of similar symbolism. It is constructed around the notion that modern Jews form a continuum with the ancient Israelites. As a result emerges a connection of today's Jews to the biblical land of Israel. This perception is central to modern Jewry and is a common notion outside Jewish circles as well. Yiftachel (2008, p. 130) says "The perception of the land as only Jewish was premised on a distorted national discourse of a 'forced exile' and subsequent 'return'." Hence, after two millennia in exile, the influx of Jews first into Palestine and later the State of Israel, since the beginning of Zionism to this day. Israeli law allows any Jew to automatically become a citizen of Israel, making the Jewish State a state of all the Jews, wherever they are, instead of all its citizens – an odd formulation of a modern democratic state. A Jewish individual from any part of the world who has never been to Israel,

nor his parents or grandparents, has more right to the land than a Palestinian who has been living on that land all his/her life, as has his ancestry for generations. It is a simple way to notice in concrete present-day facts the Zionist principle of *Jewishness* in Israel. The construction we are about to discuss of the notion of *Jewishness* into Zionist identity has long been forgotten, and the common perception is of an eternal characteristic that has always been there. It is only through critical approach such as post-Zionism that a foundational aspect such as this can be challenged.

Discussing the difference between *Jewishness* and Judaism, Professor Yaakov Rabkin has written about the opposition of Judaism to Zionism. He quotes writings of Hebrew University Professor Yeshayahu Leibowitz, a prominent Orthodox Israeli philosopher and critic of Zionism and Israel

Leibowitz said it is particularly difficult to define the Jewish people, for, since the nineteenth century, the majority had lost most of the common traits that had once made up its primary identity (Leibowitz, 26). He is referring, of course, to the practice of the Torah commandments, which, unlike faith, can be observed in the daily life of the pious Jew. (Rabkin, 2006, p.34)

Rabkin says following the commandments of the Torah constitute the traditional framework of Jewish identity. When this practice stopped among large numbers of Jews, it put in question their belonging to the Jewish collective. According to Leibowitz,

It was then that the fracture, which has not ceased to widen with time, first occurred: the break between Jewishness and Judaism. The human group recognized today as the Jewish people is no longer defined, from the factual viewpoint, as the people of historical Judaism, whether in the consciousness of the majority of its members, or in that of the non-Jews. There indeed exist within this people a substantial number of persons who strive, individually or collectively, to live the Judaic way of life. But the majority of Jews – while sincerely conscious of their Jewishness – not only does not accept Judaism, but abhors it.” (Leibowitz, in Rabkin, 2006, p.35)

The decline in Jewish religious practice Leibowitz refers to in 19th century, most likely was the result of emancipation of Western European Jewry, in the wake of European Enlightenment. Waxman (2006, p. 17) explains emancipation of Jews started in France, first with Clermont Tonerre’s call for equal rights for Jews

in the National Assembly in 1789 and later when Napoleon gathered a rabbi and Jewish notables assembly in 1807. Jews were invited to express their loyalty to their host states in exchange for full citizenship, and they responded declaring they were not separate from the French nation. The same followed in other Western European states, and once external pressure was lifted, European Jewry found itself in a profound identity crisis, being able to assimilate into their host societies they had not been able to before. This was the origin of what became known as the 'Jewish question' in Europe, which was the fear of disappearance of the Jewish people through assimilation, and to which later on was added the fear of modern anti-Semitism. Responses to this identity crisis, says Waxman, counted with the emergence of the modern Orthodox, the Conservative and the Reform Jewish movements, which in one way or another conserved Jewish religion. "Others attempted to develop a secular Jewish identity based upon common ethnicity rather than religious belief. This attempt, labeled by Gideon Shimoni (1995, p.47) as 'ethnicism,' was particularly associated with Jewish intelligentsia in Eastern Europe." Again, we see here the emergence of *Jewishness*, which is the secular Jewish identity.

While Eastern Europe Jewish intelligentsia defended the 'ethnicist' approach, seeking to counter the Jewish question by creating a secular Jewish identity, Western Europe Jewish intelligentsia defended the 'integrationist' approach, seeking to normalize the Jewish people through assimilation (Waxman, 2006, p. 18). The latter was championed by Theodor Herzl, considered the father of Zionism and the visionary of the Jewish State. Initially, Herzl believed Jews should assimilate into European Christian society as a solution for modern anti-Semitism, suggesting a mass baptism (Waxman, 2006, p. 19). He later changed his mind due to the Dreyfus affair⁵, reaching a conclusion that even converted Jews would never be fully accepted into European Christian society. He then turned to the idea of creating a Jewish State, and founded the Zionist Organization in the first Zionist congress in Basel in 1897. His vision of political Zionism, sought a territory in which to create a Jewish nation with European culture. He had no interest in

⁵ Dreyfus affair - Alfred Dreyfus was a French officer of Jewish origin, who was accused in 1894 of treason, an unsubstantiated allegation motivated by anti-semitism. (Pappe, 2006, p.36)

Judaism, and in order to mobilize Jewish constituency to adhere to Zionism he would rally “around common features that distinguished Jews from their surrounding European populations. Strangely, they were often the same negative features that anti-Semitic rhetoric ascribed to the Jews” (Ghazi-Bouillon, 2009, p. 35). Herzl’s posture denotes clearly a rejection of the image of the traditional Jew, in favor of the image of the new, assimilated Jew, which carried no Jewish vestige whatsoever. In the Zionist congress of 1903 Herzl strongly promoted the British offer of creating a Jewish State in Uganda. Chaim Weizmann, leader of the Russian Jewish delegation, fought back insisting only Palestine would be acceptable (Waxman, 2006, p. 19). Weizmann as most Eastern European ‘ethnicist’ Jews, was motivated by the writings of Asher Ginsberg, also known as Ahad Ha’am, who was an ardent promoter of a secular Jewish culture, which although secular, believed Jewish culture should be rooted in what he called the ‘Jewish spirit.’

Although Herzl had become the father of ‘political’ Zionism, and had stepped away from his original ‘integrationist’ ideas, it was not he who established the *Zionist hegemonic discourse*. Ghazi-Bouillon (2009, p. 36) points out his promotion of a collective identity around Jewish ethnicity gave birth to a new political religion – Zionism. But it was not only Jewish ethnicity that established the sense of *Jewishness* at the core of Zionism. There had to be some level of use of Judaic symbolism that Herzl was willing to completely dispense with. “Judaism was almost entirely absent from Herzl’s thinking [...] In his utopian novel *Altneuland* (Old New Land) he portrayed a society that was secular, progressive, cosmopolitan, and pluralist, guaranteeing full equality for both the Jews and non-Jews, who were partners in a cooperative venture” (Waxman, 2006, p. 19). Ahad Ha’am, who became the father of ‘cultural’ or ‘spiritual’ Zionism, “vehemently criticized Hertzl’s vision in *Altneuland* for ignoring the distinct character of the Jewish national spirit, and simply wishing to copy western culture” (Waxman, 2006, p. 19). It was Ahad Ha’am’s vision of the foundation of a Jewish nation based on secular culture and Hebrew language revival, while turning away from religion that became the basis of Zionist discourse. Ahad Ha’am

prescribed the boundaries of Zionist discourse that remain largely intact today. [...] By severing the links between ‘Jewishness’ and faith, Ahad Ha’am’s critique

was to have far-reaching implications. [...] A Jew was no longer to be defined by his religion, nor by his state, but by his immutable secular 'Jewish' identity and shared culture [where 'culture' was a broad and flexible concept] (Ghazi-Bouillon, 2009, p. 37)

Zionist leadership strived in transforming this Zionist secular Jewish culture into the force that transformed the consciousness of the Jewish constituencies into believing they are part of one 'nation'. Since Jews were spread in numerous locations, spoke different languages and practiced religion with cultural differences, Zionist political elites understood the need for a common culture, the "production and control of common myths, symbols, national heroes and, above all, national territory" (Ghazi-Bouillon, 2009, p. 38). *Jewishness* was at the core of Zionism.

Jewishness and historical narrative.

Jewishness plays a fundamental role in defining Zionist identity due to its value of continuity. A definition of identity given by one of the fathers of Identity studies, Erik Erikson (1994, p.19) stresses this very notion: "a *subjective sense* of an *invigorating sameness and continuity*" (I discuss Erikson more extensively later). 'Continuity' evokes a sense of relation of identity and historical narrative, which Stuart Hall also seem to make:

Far from being grounded in a mere 'recovery' of the past, which is waiting to be found, and which, when found, will secure our sense of ourselves into eternity, identities are the names we give to the different ways we are positioned by, and position ourselves within, the narratives of the past. (Hall, 1990)

Hall suggests identity is not 'produced' by the past, but it is us that choose how to use the past in shaping our identity, and how to insert ourselves in that narrative. As vital element in Zionist identity, *Jewishness* reinforces it, gives it meaning and a sense of direction and destiny, a sense of continuity, eternity or ancientness, as it connects present-day Jews with an ancient people, history and territory.

The notion of an eternal Jewish 'nation' or 'people' has been propagated in Israeli and Diaspora Jewish education, symbolism, official discourse and public

commemorations to a point where common knowledge among Jewish constituency everywhere does not seem to even consider questioning the idea that modern Jews form a *continuum* with ancient Israelites, and have maintained the structure of a 'people' throughout history, until their return to the land of Israel through the Zionist enterprise. In his controversial critique of the notion of an eternal Jewish people, "*The Invention of the Jewish People*", Tel Aviv University Professor Shlomo Sand discusses the moment such perception of Jews as an eternal people first appeared, substituting older understandings that saw Judaism solely as a religion. Sand points out that under the influence of growing nationalist thought in nineteenth century Europe, changes occurred in academic writings of Jewish history scholars. Sand (2009, p. 77) observes, "The hardening of German nationalist definitions based on origin and race, [...] stirred new sensitivities among a small group of intellectuals of Jewish descent." It appears Jewish scholars felt compelled, in face of new nationalist tendencies and national identity formation, to counter-form their own identity according to the same standards, as if one had no identity unless one belonged to an ethnically defined group with a common origin. Sand (2009, pp. 73-81) points out Heinrich Graetz's retold Jewish history in *History of the Jews* in 1853 transforming its image from the one described by his predecessors, namely Isaak Marcus Jost. Rather than being a religious civilization, with rich diversity and cultural influences from being scattered around the world, Graetz portrayed the Jewish people as an eternal people or tribe. This portrayal was radicalized by Hess's racial "materialism", shifting it to a still harder essentialist and nationalist position. Sand describes Hess's main argument for the Jewish people's unifying identity as being rooted in ancient times on one hand, and inexplicably resilient to history, probably by divine justification, on the other. This combination of nationalist argument of *ancientness* and religious argument of divine justification is a tendency Sand points out, relating nationalist tendencies in early nineteenth century Jewish history scholars to the recourse to Biblical texts as historical sources:

Right from the start there was a close connection between the perception of the Old Testament as a reliable historical source and the attempt to define modern Jewish identity in prenationalist or nationalist terms. The more nationalistic the

author, the more he treats the Bible as history - as the birth certificate attesting to the common origin of the 'people'. [...] From Isaak Jost, through some of the intellectuals who joined the second stage of the science of Judaism, to the appearance of the great innovator Heinrich Graetz, the Old Testament came to serve as the point of departure for the first historiographical exploration into the invention of the 'Jewish nation', an invention that would become increasingly important in the second half of the nineteenth century. (Sand, 2009, p. 71)

Moses Hess is considered to be one of the fathers of Jewish history, as well as one of the fathers of Zionism, and his ideas still resonate strongly regarding the reasons for the Jews to have survived as a 'people' for so long. This special quality the Jewish 'people' or 'nation' has, is an important facet of *Jewishness* in Zionist rationale, and may arguably be related to the election myth, which as Anthony D. Smith points out

Was the ideal of a covenant between the deity and the *ethnie* [ethnic community] In the Israelite prototype recorded in the Pentateuch, the people are chosen by God and undertake to follow His commandments, moral and ritual, and, to this end, they must become entirely separate from the profane world, a world of idolatry. (Smith, 2009, p.93)

Since the pact was made with the whole *ethnie*, which defines here the Jewish people not on its practice of religion or the commandments of the Torah, but on a common ethnic origin, this 'pact' included and protected whoever ethnically belonged to it and their descendents throughout history, transporting this group identity through time.

Of course other explanations for Jewish permanence through history exist, such as the materialist approach to history, which appears practically nowhere in Jewish history field. Leon's (1981) approach structure an argument for the survival of the Jewish people totally based on their means of production, that is, their economic activities. For instance, the situation of Jews in "Eastern Europe, where they had been allowed to have a limited number of occupations such as brokers, agents, bankers, money lenders and so on" (Pappe, 2006, p.54), which alongside Christian religion and xenophobia contributed to the anti-Semitism prevalent in Europe at that time, and also accounted for maintaining unity, both against persecution and favoring stronger market competitiveness, but mostly, because in

Leon's view they constituted a separate class. Leon argues that the opposite situation attests to this fact:

In reality, while Jewish history is the history of the preservation of Judaism, it is at the same time the history of the assimilation of large sections of Judaism. 'In Northern Africa, in pre-Islamic times, great numbers of Jews were engaged in agriculture, but of these, too, the vast majority have been absorbed by the local population.' This assimilation is explained by the fact that the Jews by turning agriculturists ceased to constitute a separate class. Could they at all have taken to agriculture, they could hardly have done so without scattering through the country and its numerous villages, which, in spite of the difference in religion, would probably in a few generations have resulted in complete assimilation. Engaged in commerce and concentrated in towns, they formed agglomerations and developed a social life of their own, moving and marrying within their own community.

Let us also recall the numerous conversions of Jewish landed proprietors in Germany in the fourth century; the complete disappearance of the Jewish warrior tribes of Arabia; the assimilation of the Jews in South America, in Surinam, etc.

The law of assimilation might be formulated as follows: Wherever the Jews cease to constitute a class, they lose, more or less rapidly, their ethnical, religious, and linguistic characteristics; they become assimilated. (Ruppin, 1934, in Leon, 1981, p.26)

Sand structures the argument of his book, *The Invention of the Jewish People* around three main points, questioning this notion of *Jewishness* produced by the Zionist enterprise: 1) Israelites were never expelled from ancient Israel except for minor numbers among the elites, but rather left of their own will and settled elsewhere out of economic interests. Jews have not been longing or even trying to return for two millennia; 2) Large numbers of Ashkenazi⁶ Jews are descendents of converted peoples from the Caucasus (such as the Kazars, among others), never having had any connection to the ancient Israelites, nor having ever had any connection to the land of Israel; 3) Jewish communities around the world constituted religious groups, never having shared a secular cultural connection or a common language and thus, never having constituted a 'people', but many Jewish 'peoples'. Sand's definition of a 'people' is a group of people who share a common language and a secular culture. Sand's work brings to the forefront the questioning of the element of *Jewishness*, which in *Zionist hegemonic discourse* has been quite untouchable. Sand, amongst others who have been challenging

⁶ Term referring to German Jews, more broadly used to refer to European Jews, with exception for the Iberian Peninsula, where Jews are referred to as *Sefaradi*

Zionism's foundations has suffered his portion of backlashes due to his initiative, and has received death threats for expressing his ideas in his book, as I heard from him first hand. The fact of the matter is, if Jews were never expelled from their ancient land but chose to leave, if a large portion of those who immigrated and live in Israel have no ancestry which ever lived there, and if Jews have constitute for two millennia a religion, in the same fashion Christians and Muslims have, the argument left to be made for the need for a Zionist-concept of a Jewish State becomes feeble.

Zionist leadership brought *Jewishness* to the fore by making Palestinian/Israeli landscape seem to have been eternally Jewish. Although there is no refute of the ancient presence of 'a' Jewish people in ancient Palestine, there had been an effort directed at erasing any memory of Palestinians having ever existed on the land, and the centuries of Arabization and Islamization it had undergone under Ottoman rule. Benvenisti (2000, p.18) writes about the erasure of Arabized characteristics of the land through language. He describes how his father took part in a government commissioned team of linguists, who carried out a project of substituting all Arabic names of places throughout Israel for Hebrew ones, and "wiping out an entire cultural heritage that must certainly conceal within it elements of the Israeli-Jewish heritage as well." This Jewish heritage was the legacy left by small numbers of Jews that had remained in Palestine throughout the centuries, and had no connection to European culture.

Jewishness and theories of nationalism.

As pointed out before through Erikson and Hall's writings, historical narrative and continuity are important elements of identity. Nationalism theorist Anthony D. Smith has also made reference to connections to an ancient past when he defined ethnic communities, or *ethnie*: "named units of population with common ancestry myths and historical memories, elements of shared culture, some link with a historic territory and some measure of solidarity, at least among their elites" (Smith, 1995, p.57). He suggests there is a "need for a type of analysis" based on a rejection of modernist standpoint that "There is a radical break

between pre-modern units and sentiments and modern nations and nationalism” (Smith, 1991, p. 14). This new analysis would allow a better understanding of *continuity* between “modern national units and sentiments and the collective cultural units and sentiments of previous eras,” which Smith terms *ethnie*. He points out that a crucially important concept for this analysis is ‘identity’, which he defines as follows:

The notion of ‘identity’ has received considerable attention, not least in political science and international relations literature. Here, however, it relates mainly to a sense of community based on history and culture, rather than to any collectivity or to the concept of ideology. [...] the growth of a sense of the collective self is treated as an important part of group (especially ethnic) identity and solidarity. Only here the sense of self is viewed through the prism of symbols and mythologies of the community’s heritage. The need of identification with a community in order to achieve individual identity and self-respect is in part a function of socialization experiences in the historic culture-community; and the modes and goals of identification are given by the group and its past experiences as they coalesce into a collective ‘tradition’. (Smith, 1991, p. 14)

However, Smith’s theory seems to explain what Zionists *believed* they were doing, or at least what they wanted others to believe they were doing. The recovery of connections of their ancient past with their modern collective identity, and formation of their own nation, in response to a new age where all around them identities were being structured into nations, and nations into nationalist projects in the form of modern states. But if we look at the basic premise Smith presents, the *ethnie*, and apply it to the Jewish case, we encounter a series of problems. Indeed, Jews have common ancestry myths dating to Biblical times, which also relate the Jewish group to a historic territory. However, Pre-Zionist Jewish communities in the Diaspora did not share culture, while only sharing some religious characteristics and even there many differences can be found. As Sand (2009) pointed out, each community had evolved for centuries in their host societies through interaction and exchange, developing unique and rich cultures, while they grew different from each other.

Ghazi-Bouillon points out that Smith’s theory pertains to a ‘primordialist’ approach of explaining the phenomenon of nations and nationalism. The ‘primordialist’ school relies on concepts of maintenance of the essence of the

nation, the antiquity of the nation, and bases nationalism on culture. This approach explains the *features* that constitute a nation, but it fails to explain *why* it does so, and also fails to acknowledge the role of *human agency* in the process of creating a nation. “This perspective privileges the Zionist historical narrative and, until recently, has dominated the understanding of Jewish life in Europe,” says Ghazi-Bouillon, and was the base on which intellectuals influenced the development of the Zionist movement. However, there was a contradiction in describing the Jews as an *ethnie*, since “implicit or explicit recognition of early Zionist leaders and nationalist thinkers that the Jews had to be ‘re-bound’ together implies that even they sensed that a national identity needed to be constructed,” (2009, p. 15) which confirms Sand’s assertion.

Central to this approach is the idea that national identity is a constructed, rather than inherited, entity, and, more importantly, that because of this it is fluid and subject to change. Nations, then, are indeed a ‘product’ of human agency. They are modern, constructed and in essence ‘imagined’ as Benedict Anderson has argued. (Ghazi-Bouillon, 2009, p. 15)

Ghazi-Bouillon affirms Benedict Anderson’s theory pertains to a different approach to explaining nationalism which is broadly defined as ‘constructivist’, and relies on concepts of the constructed quality of nations, their emergence in relation to modernity, and on nationalism as being fuelled by political aspirations. Looking at the differences between definitions pertaining to ‘premordialist’ and ‘constructivist’ approaches, Guibernau compares definitions of pre-modern ‘nation’ or ‘people’ and modern nation:

Pre-modern ‘nation’ in the neo-perennialist perspective is defined, predominantly, in cultural terms, as a ‘people’, a community of historical culture linked to a particular ancestral territory or ‘homeland’. [... a modern nation is] a named human population sharing a historic territory, common myths and historical memories, a mass, public culture, a common economy and common legal rights and duties for all members. (2001, p. 19)

What Guibernau calls ‘mass, public culture’ might only be achieved through instruments of mass communication, possibly what Anderson referred to by print capitalism. Anderson (2006, p. 153) points out “The significance of the emergence

of Zionism and the birth of Israel is that the former marks the reimagining of an ancient religious community as a nation” Anderson (2006, p. 212) has made central to his theory the emergence of ‘print capitalism’, the combination of new printing technology and capitalist system, and the use of popular language which made it possible to reach large masses with the same message or hegemonic (I discuss Gramsci’s hegemony in the next section), or counter-hegemonic discourse. It provides a solid explanation for the proliferation of *Zionist hegemonic discourse*, which we examine in the next section.

Thus, the *Jewishness* core aspect of Zionist identity has been constructed politically, historically and culturally in order to connect present day Zionist identities through time and history to ancient Israelites and their territory. It has been used to form a perception of unity around an ethnic characteristic, which is secular in its base, but makes use of religious symbols, which seems to be the little it has in common with Judaism. It is only through a critical approach such as post-Zionism that it is possible to discuss this element of Zionist identity, *Jewishness*, or the Jewish character of the State of Israel, which previously to post-Zionist approach was largely deemed unquestionable.

2.2 Security/militarism.

Security/militarism aspect of Zionist identity is rooted in, and at the same time justified by *victimhood*, through which it gains legitimacy. The main argument is that *security/militarism* is a *necessity for survival*. It is through this assumption that victimhood shows its importance, since it is not mere survival that is presented as an argument but the survival against unjustified aggressions. It is believed that there is nothing Israel has done to deserve such aggressions and it merely needs to defend itself from it. In this situation, the Zionist entity is the victim of aggression from which it constantly has needed to defend itself, ever since the foundation of the state. On one hand if one is a victim, one must be prepared for any attack, and if needed defend oneself being completely justified in doing so. On the other hand, if one perennially occupies the place of the victim, one can never be an oppressor, thus any otherwise ‘aggressive’ act cannot be

called that, rather, it can only be defensive, having entitlement to legitimacy. While in traditional Zionist history Israel is represented as the weaker party, which always sought peace with its neighbors and was forced into defending itself in battle in order to survive, New Israeli History shows the opposite image, challenging its status of victimhood and its claim to legitimacy.

Israel's huge military apparatus surpasses most military forces on the planet, be that Israel is the sixth largest nuclear power (unconfirmed due to Israel's policy of ambiguity), and has an air force said to be only second to the USA. Its rationale for military operations is usually based on 'security' or 'defense' concepts, where the agenda it promotes is most of the time aggressive. However aggressive the action might be, it is not seen as such by Zionists, leaders or civil society for the most part, who interpret the actions taken as necessary security defensive measures. Interpretation of events depends heavily on the belief system put in place by the Zionist ideological discourse and culture, which reproduces the victim identity that in turn perpetuates discourse and culture in a cycle. Israel seemingly uses the place of the victim strategically, as Adi Ophir terms how the State apparatuses use victimhood as "aggressive victimhood" (Ghazi-bouillon, 2009, p. 7).

To external observers some cases may seem exaggerated, possibly cynical, when Israel pleads self-defense. For instance, in the case of operation Cast Lead, also known as the Gaza War of 2008/2009, where 1400 Palestinians and 13 Israelis were killed, out of which at least half the Palestinians were non-combatants, and a third were minors, while Israelis were all military. Another case could be the day-to-day occupation in the West Bank, where Palestinians live under heavy constrictions on freedom of movement and ultimately completely subjected to Israeli military law; or the case of an eight-meter tall wall being built supposedly along the internationally recognized border, but actually annexing Jewish settlements that are built on Palestinian land to Israel, annexing natural resources such as water and separating Palestinian farmers from their lands, splitting families and villages - all of which are justified with not much effort but for a mention that it is necessary for 'security' reasons. Yiftachel (2008, p. 130) points out a "discourse developed in reaction to the Arab-Jewish conflict, [...] elevating

exigencies of national security onto a level of unquestioned gospel.” In a criticism of Levinas’s claims that persecution is one of the defining aspects of the Jewish People, Judith Butler draws relevant relations to this discussion:

... to argue that any historically constituted group of people are, by definition, always persecuted and never persecutory seems not only to confound the ontological and preontological levels but to license an unacceptable irresponsibility and a limitless recourse to aggression in the name of 'self-defense.' (Butler, 2005, p. 96)

Adi Ophir (2008, p. 87) writes about the difference between becoming a victim and ‘being’ a victim: “Unlike *becoming* a victim, which may be a result of contingent, ephemeral forces, *being* a victim means taking, holding to, or being stuck in a victim’s position.” Ophir suggests victimhood is culturally constructed and the emergence of New Israeli History takes it away. He says it is no wonder New Historians are met with so much anger, condemnation and contempt, since they take away victimhood that is felt to be entitled by name, right or inheritance, since in

Basic Zionist narrative, Israeli Jews are presented as victims and heirs to victims (European Jews), who sought refuge and homeland in their fatherland, where they became victims of Arab violence. Their ongoing struggle against the various forms of violence that permeate very sphere of social life has been carried out in justice with great courage and talent. (Ophir, 2008, p.88)

Ophir mentions European Jews, referring to the inheritance of the eternal status of victims of the Holocaust. As we shall see, the Holocaust is a recurring theme in the interviews, and justifiably so. Israel promotes the Holocaust as a symbol of eternal victimhood quite aggressively. Sonnenschein, Bekerman, and Horenczyk (2010) observed the Holocaust theme was central to affirmation of Zionist identity in their study with Jewish and Palestinian Israeli university students:

The Holocaust and persecution made up a central and significant component in the national identity of the Jewish participants and were mentioned repeatedly in the pre-course interviews. In fact, the persistent appearance of the existential threat during the dialogue and the apprehension that new options for defining the state would amount to a new holocaust point to the success of a broad existing

process of education and indoctrination, a process that has constructed the Holocaust and the existential threat as key components of the identity of Jewish Israelis, and has transferred all that to the conflict with the Arabs in general and the Palestinians in particular. (Sonnenschein, Bekerman, and Horenczyk, 2010, p.60)

The indoctrination Sonnenschein, Bekerman, and Horenczyk talk about is not propagated only through school system official education, but public commemoration and a huge cultural production around it. The state promotes organized visits of soldiers to the Holocaust museum in Jerusalem; organized trips to Poland for high school students to visit concentration and extermination camps; and organized trips for soldiers of the same sort. In the Diaspora there are several programs that offer the same kind of educational trips. Through the Holocaust Jews become the owners of the top suffering to have ever existed, the ultimate victims who can never be challenged on their victimhood. "The Holocaust is conceived of, thought, learned, and taught through the prism of the question of Jewish identity. The Holocaust is used and abused as a means in the construction of Jewish identity, and identity questions frame and shape the domain of Holocaust discourse" (Ophir, 2008, pp. 84, 85).

It was only possible to gain critical perspective on the problems extant in Israel's justification for its military actions throughout its history, when the position of victimhood finally suffered a blow. It might not have been a blow that revolutionized the political status quo, but it certainly has integrated new historical 'truths' into the scene, which became a solid counter-reference to the Zionist narrative. As Ghazi-Bouillon puts it,

What is interesting, however, is that this often vehemently acrimonious debate has ensued over a topic as innocuous as a historical narrative. It is a vital part of the hegemonic discourse that holds a deep-rooted significance for the evolution of national identity and reflects contemporary political developments as well as shifts in national culture." (2009, p. 68)

New Israeli History has become central to identity crisis and discussion around identity issues in Jewish academia, and rose media attention and public debate. By revising the facts they opened a window for deeper critique that post-Zionist scholarship developed further. The original myth of independence is

essential for the purpose of this research, since we can note a few aspects that underscore the claims for identity constructions I am trying to argue. The representation of Israel as small and weak against the giant Arab armies reminisces of the myth of David and Goliath, as Bar-On describes it (2004, p.5). New Israeli History was based on evidence found in declassified Israeli government documents, which under the 30-year rule became public in the late 70's. According to New Israeli Historian Avi Shlaim, the documents described in a surprising level of detail (Ghazi-Bouillon, 2009, p. 61), all events concerning Israel's independence up until 1951. In interviews conceded to Asima Ghazi-Bouillon New Israeli Historians express how they felt surprised when they found the evidence they used to formulate New Israeli History. They used to define themselves as Zionists at the time, albeit left wing, but as New Israeli Historian Ilan Pappé puts it "...my whole activity was within the Zionist frame of mind: namely that it's great that we are willing to talk to the Arabs after all they have done to us." The shock was inevitable since the process was also affecting their identity as well. Pappé was also surprised at how "his interpretation of the material he found rendered the imagery of David and Goliath a little more than fable", apparently a recurring theme amongst New Historians and post-Zionist scholars, but what Pappé (2009, pp. 61, 62) says shook him the most was not the story itself, "but the fact that he was unaware of it, despite being more interested in history than the average young Israeli." Hegemonic Zionist narrative appears to have a reach that includes academic circles, and as by Gramsci's definition of hegemony where dominance is achieved by consent (which I will go back to in the next section on *hegemonic Zionist discourse*), it makes it difficult to critique one's own paradigm.

New Israeli History consisted in presenting a few central differences from traditional Zionist narrative around the war of independence. Zionist narrative says Jewish leaderships had to overcome difficulties imposed by the British. Zionists declared Israel's independence after the 1947 UN Partition Plan had been voted, and was attacked by a league of five Arab armies. Although Israel was the weaker party, it won. Local Palestinian population fled with incentive of local Arab leaders and abandoned their homes and lands. New history tells an opposite

story, where besides support from the British, the Zionists had military superiority throughout the fighting that was mainly against Egypt, the only country who engaged Israel more seriously. The Palestinian problem was born out of an intentional violent expulsion carefully planned, named Plan Dalet (plan D). Violent expulsions involving many documented massacres of civilian Palestinian population began before the 1948 war, and during the war it intensified greatly in order to reach the goals of the plan. The result was over seven hundred thousand Palestinians became refugees.

Under the critical academic approach that had been started regarding the 1948 independence war, narrative of the 1967 war also came under scrutiny. While Zionist narrative used to claim preemptive attack due to intelligence on an Arab plan of attack by Egypt and Jordan, it became clear that although there might have been such intention from Egypt, there was no need for an attack on Jordan, much less a conquest of territories. This war resulted in the occupation of the West Bank and Gaza, whereas the occupation of the first is ongoing and the latter has been terminated in 2005, only to remain under Israeli military external control to this day. This war generated over two hundred and fifty thousand Palestinian refugees. At the date of this work, 2011, according to official numbers from UNRWA (United Nations Relief and Work Agency for Palestinian Refugees in the Near East), there are 4.7 million registered Palestinian refugees.

Coming back to the identity question, and the relation of victimhood and legitimacy to *security/militarism* aspect of Zionist identity, when New History undermined the victimhood root rationale, the legitimacy of the Zionist enterprise suffered the consequences. It is not only through the State's apparatuses that the traditional version of history was propagated in order to protect the legitimacy of the 'nation'. On personal level, the participants were part of the fabrication of a historical narrative that meant to exclude any damning episodes from the legitimate Zionist record. New Historian Benny Morris, the one who coined the term itself, 'New Israeli History', has made claims that the 'old' historians had taken part in the fighting in 1948 and thus their account was not objective. Adi Ophir (2008, p. 93) recounts how he found out about the atrocities committed during 1948 when his father, who was part of the *Irgun*, organization, which

executed the *Deir-Yassin* massacre, confessed their occurrence to him in 1982. His father had denied them up until then, and only spoke because the massacres of *Sabra* and *Shatila* in Lebanon had just occurred under the auspices of the Israeli Defense Forces (IDF), and he seemed to want to relieve his conscience. Ophir had believed his father and in debates over the issue had denied the occurrence of massacres committed by Jewish organizations until then. His father had also told him he had adulterated data in a book he helped publish on the issue. Ophir describes his deep disillusionment with his father's lies. Possibly because it was his father who had been his source for the Zionist narrative as a first hand participant, that Ophir had believed so blindly in him, and that he had ceased to believe in him as well.

Another important point in the discussion on *security/militarism* and its relation to victimhood is the question of suicide bombings. The way these occurrences are portrayed, they contribute to the image of victimhood of Jewish Israelis in the hands of 'religious fanatics', which can only be dealt with by force. As Eidelson (2003) points out, groups will develop collective templates of interpretation of their lived experiences. Such has been the case of Israelis and Jews in Diaspora interpreting Palestinian violent resistance over the years. Victimhood has been a prevalent template through which experiences are interpreted in the Jewish/Israeli collectives. Although since the beginning of the history of this conflict there have been "repetitive violent attempts of the Palestinians to disrupt the Zionist project" (Bar-On, 2004, p.14), which contributed to this rationale of victimhood on the Jewish side, they were always attempts at resisting dispossession. As mentioned earlier in this work, even New Historian Benny Morris (2001, p. 37), who declares himself a Zionist, affirms Palestinian resistance to Zionism was and still is motivated out of fear of displacement. Bar-On also stresses that

The self-positioning as victims also feeds on the traditional Jewish ethos that perceives the Gentiles as perennial enemies who are always set on harassing the Jews and, if possible, on exterminating them. The experience of the Holocaust only five years earlier [before the foundation of Israel], fortifies this self-righteous ethos of the Israelis. (Bar-On, 2004, p.14)

According to Erikson (1979, p.102, 103) there will always be defensive reactions “against insights which seem to rob us from our self-made certainty”, thus any attempt at challenging the status of victimhood is usually met by Jews with a strong defensive reaction, as well as offense, and shock at the lack of understanding of the reality Israeli Jews live under, and the necessity of Israeli policies to prevent another Holocaust from happening. As Eidelson (2003) warns, data discrepant with the belief of victimhood will go unnoticed, or will suffer reframing to be consistent with Zionist worldview, unless of course, dramatically challenged. It is not clear to me what Eidelson means by ‘dramatically challenged’. In my experience one of the most alienating attitudes taken by so-called ‘promoters of peace’ has been to challenge Zionists dramatically, including myself in early stages of my political activism. If by ‘dramatic’ Eidelson meant ‘effective’, meaning that positive results can be measured, I would agree.

Palestinian suicide bombings, along with any violent Palestinian resistance, have contributed to this sense of Jewish/Israeli victimhood, and strengthened Zionist identity. Within Zionist circles, or those who accept Zionist claim as legitimate, the only discussion regarding possible reasons for such violence, mainly in relation to suicide bombings, points to religious extremism on the Palestinian side. Since there is no part in the collective memory-based narrative that points to injustices committed against Palestinians during the creation of the state in 1948; in occupying the OPT in 1967; in imposing a regime that deprived Palestinians of political, civil and human rights for decades, there is no reasonable grievance that can be understood as universal. There is a perception of the existence of hatred from Palestinians, but when it comes to questioning the reasons for this hatred, the prevailing rationale is of anti-Semitism and persecution, the wish to exterminate Israel and the Jewish people. This template of interpretation contributes to further blurring separation between *Jewishness* and Zionism, and to dehumanization of the image held by Israelis and Jews of Palestinians. Amira Hass (Omeish, 2007), Israeli award-winning journalist and author, contends, "Any violence by a large population is not because this people is more violent than any other. It's an alarm, it's a sign, it's a signal that something is wrong in the treatment of this population." She stresses that the first suicide

bombings were inside the OPT, against military targets and settler targets (viewed as military by Palestinians). These bombings were motivated by deep helplessness of individuals living under military occupation, their total loss of hope and feeling of impotence derived from the pass system and closure policy imposed by Israeli government in 1991. In 1994 the first suicide bombings inside Israel happened as a revenge following the massacre performed by an American Jewish settler in Hebron's Mosque against unarmed local worshippers, where 29 Palestinians were murdered. Suicide bombings became instrumentalized by Hamas and politically motivated to undermine the Oslo peace process with which they disagreed. More recent use of suicide bombing, says Hass⁷ (2003), during the second Intifada, were tools in a competition between factions for popular support among Palestinian constituencies. Hass (2003) argues that individuals who suffered horrible losses would often offer themselves to organizations looking to recruit people to carry out suicide bombings. As to the suspected religious extremist motivation of suicide bombers, Hass (2003) attests out of her personal experience as a journalist living in the OPT and interviewing Palestinians first hand, that religious motivations come last, and are not the core motivations for such acts. Many of the ones who carried out these bombings had careers, were not coming from the poorest families, or were enrolled in universities, in other words, not people whose lives were a total loss in Western or Palestinian norms. "They felt they represented society in its despair and wanted to make some use of this despair: revenge" (Hass, 2003). Many got more strength by becoming more observant as a preparation for the act itself, after their decision had been taken.

While Israeli oppressive policies in the OPT generate hatred and fear of further displacement that would drive individuals to commit suicide bombings, it does not make it an attack based on anti-Semitic rationale, rather an anti-Israeli rationale. Collective Jewish/Israeli template of interpretation is that those are attempts to eliminate the Jewish people, motivated by anti-Semitism, and they should be stopped at all costs, with any violent measure, regardless of concern towards civilian population, since their religious extremism pus them beyond any

⁷ Interview, 2003, October 24: Occupation and Terrorism. *Conversations With History*. University of California at Berkeley.

comprehension in rational or even human sense. *Security/militarism* as part of Zionist identity can only hold as long as it is backed by legitimacy, which in turn relies on status of victimhood. Once that is removed, this trait appears to be a simple instrument of aggression, and the identity's legitimacy is lost. Many of the New Historians, critical sociologists and post-Zionist scholars and thinkers have gone through their personal process of coming to terms with the new (to them) discoveries regarding Zionism as well. Some have become extremely critical of Zionist enterprise, and others try to negotiate with themselves and with others, ways to frame the new data and critical thinking within Zionist thought. The same occurs to non-scholars who are exposed to this debate, in one way or another, as we will see in the interviews I will present in this work.

2.3 Zionist hegemonic conception of the Jewish state.

Ghazi-Bouillon (2009) uses a series of theories to structure an argument describing how Zionism has become the dominant, all-defining reference for Jews, one that historically has been difficult to critique, and which still stands today, albeit not intact. I will outline her proposition and point out a couple of challenges to it, but in general terms I regard it as a good model for explaining Zionism as a constructed paradigm. She refers Antonio Gramsci's (Ghazi-Bouillon, 2009, pp. 16, 17) cultural hegemony theory to describe the process by which the ideology generated by the founders of Zionism, European secular Jews, became the 'cement' that brought together the different currents of Zionism under it in the process of 'nation-building' as a necessary pre-condition for 'state-building'. What Gramsci terms the 'hegemonic class', in this case the Zionist leadership, gained ascendancy over other Jewish groups by getting their consent, without the use of force, and combining the interests of all into their own project of creating a 'national identity'.

Making mention of Foucaultian theory Ghazi-Bouillon (2009, p. 22) describes how this hegemonic movement established its power through 'regimes of truth', which she terms the 'hegemonic Labor Zionist discourse'. As a form of political power, discourse is one of the resources that allow one group to gain ascendancy over other competing groups, which were other visions for Jewish

identity. It is a structure of thought that includes historical narrative, ideology and practice of state, and while embedded deep in state structure, it influences production of self-knowledge. Ghazi-Bouillon affirms

The nationalist project is an intellectual as well as political project, and it relies on collective memory to reinforce its claims of a shared past and a common destiny. Clearly then, intellectuals stand at the heart of the nationalist enterprise because they assist in shaping the collective self-imagination of the nation – not merely in the emergence and the initial stages of the formation of national identity, but throughout the continuous struggle for its redefinition. (2009, pp. 22, 23)

This discourse has been propagated by ‘state apparatuses’, which established the parameters by which Zionism, *Jewishness* and the right to territory would be discussed from then onwards. As part of hegemony theory, Ghazi-Bouillon argues that an existing hegemony contains within it the seed of its destruction, due to its inclusion of the largest number of members under its leadership, weakening its base. In the case of Israel, the Zionist elite ruling group, *Ashkenazi* Jews, had their base weakened by their aggressive nation building policies, which called for the inclusion of all Jewish groups.

In discussing the relation between knowledge and power, Ghazi-Bouillon points out the importance of Edward Said’s distinction between pure knowledge and political knowledge. The latter is close to political power and has political implications. History then, becomes such a political knowledge, as Ghazi-Bouillon points out

History is a source of political power (though not the only one, and certainly not the most important one) because in the case of Israel it provides the bridge between a ‘nation’ and the justification of its right to a particular land. In doing so, it lays the foundation for economic and political control. Without land the ‘nation’, it is argued, cannot survive – not merely historically, but also in a practical sense. It is the basis for strategic military interests, access to and control over water resources, agricultural land, and land needed for development and housing. (2009, p. 32)

As political knowledge, history expands the *hegemonic Zionist discourse*, and becomes a tool for acquiring land and control over it as sources of power.

According to Ghazi-Bouillon (2009, p. 39), Labor-Zionism hegemony was established by the ‘founding fathers’ of Israel, the leadership of moderate socialist

Mapai party, headed by David Ben-Gurion, which remained intact for its first 50 years, roughly from 1930 to 1980. Ghazi-Bouillon argues that while Labor Zionism favored a diplomatic solution for the establishment of the state, and its main challenger, revisionist Zionism, favored militant political action, both of them were expressions of Labor Zionism. Comparing with the present-day political heirs of both currents, labor party and *Likud* party, differ even less than they did back when the question was how to *establish* a Jewish state, while nowadays it is how to *secure* a Jewish state, both questions referring to cultural, military, economy and diplomatic aspects. Labor-Zionism hegemony, according to Ghazi-Bouillon, is the discourse established as a 'regime of truth', producing and defining the object of knowledge by which the new national identity revolves around the link between the Jews and the land in Palestine. This discourse governs the way this topic can be meaningfully discussed (2009, pp. 39, 40).

Although Ghazi-Bouillon defend Labor Zionism is differed from its challenger current of Zionism, Revisionist Zionism, in that the first favored a diplomatic approach to state building, as opposed to more aggressive stances of the latter, which favored militant political action, New History has shown such differences did not really exist. Zionist narrative has suggested Revisionists composed more radical and aggressive armed forces groups during the early phases of fighting for the establishment of the Jewish State. Armed organizations such as the Revisionist Zionist *Etsel*, which gave birth to *Herut* political party and later became the right-wing *Likud*, and the nationalist extremist *Lechi*, which was declared a terrorist group but later conceded amnesty by the new-born Israeli government, remained registered in history as responsible for the Dir-Yassin massacre, which enabled the main armed forces group, Labor Zionist *Hagana* to not be associated with such atrocities. New Israeli Historian Ilan Pappé has claimed differently, in his book *The Ethnic Cleansing of Palestine*, where he speaks of the violent expulsion of over seven hundred thousand Palestinians, mainly by the forces of the *Hagana*, as evidenced in the Israeli government declassified documents, which served as a base for New Israeli History:

The perpetrators here are not obscure - they are a very specific group of people: the heroes of the Jewish war of independence, whose names will be quite familiar

to most readers. This list begins with the indisputable leader of the Zionist movement, David Ben-Gurion, in whose private home all early and later chapters in the ethnic cleansing story were discussed and finalized. (Pappe, 2007, p. 5)

Thus Labor Zionism seemed to have the same aggressive impetus that Revisionist Zionism had. Additionally, during the 70's a political shift happened. Diminished confidence in Labor Zionist leadership and their military elite due to the wars of attrition in the late 60's and the Yom-Kippur war in 1973, added to increased political awareness amongst marginalized Jewish groups in society, heirs of Revisionist Zionism took over, and for the majority of the next 30 years have governed Israel, up until now. If anything, polarization towards the political right has increased considerably. The emergence of *Israel Beiteinu* political party, led by Lieberman and its rapid growth to significant influence in the coalition government formed by Netanyahu in the 2009 elections, has shown this clear tendency.

I tend to agree with Ghazi-Bouillon that there is a Zionist hegemony based on a discourse that links the constructed notion of Jews as a 'nation' to the land in Palestine, relying on a narrative that endorses that notion. The use of the designation 'Labor' in her definition of Labor-Zionist hegemony does not seem to serve any purpose other than pointing who it was that led the Zionist enterprise first. It also confuses the reader as to what Labor characteristics are embedded in her concept of hegemony, in the sense of left wing politics. Additionally, in the last three decades Israel has moved away from its socialist welfare-state structure that characterized it in its first three decades of existence, into a privatized conservative small-government structure, and has become more radicalized in its nationalist ideologies, also point to changes that would, if anything, not contribute to the maintenance of 'Labor' as the designation of the ruling Zionist ideology. The emergence of neo-Zionism, which incorporates the post-Zionist critique into a discourse of realpolitik 'necessary' for survival, and that there was no other way to found the Jewish State. Evil done to Palestinians in this conception is not different from the way all nations were born harming other victims in one way or another, thus dismissing the moral consequences of New History and post-Zionist thought. This kind of approach is based on what can be understood as double standards,

where the relativization of victimhood in blatantly bolstering the suffering of the Jewish people and ignoring that of the Palestinians, makes an ethno-centric, prejudiced world view evident. In regard to the change in leadership, although there might have been a change from Labor-Zionism originated left wing government to Revisionist-Zionism originated right wing government, there was no change in the ruling political elites, since to this day there has never been a prime-minister in Israel that was not *Ashkenazi*.

The Zionist hegemonic conception of the Jewish state, as mentioned before, defines the limits within which debate is 'acceptable' or 'meaningful' on the subject of Zionism. New Israeli History and post-Zionist scholarship has challenged this hegemonic discourse. The loss of the historic argument has been a serious blow to this hegemony, since it lost its tool, traditional Zionist historical narrative, which maintained its 'regimes of truth' intact. It has been a personal struggle for academics involved in this debate, emotionally as I have pointed out, and materially as well. Since Zionist hegemony is still in place, discourse and regimes of truth are still deeply embedded in institutions. Academicians, as well as academic institutions have been struggling between keeping academic freedom and fear of challenging hegemony, since the latter has developed powerful weapons to respond to challengers. The most common one is to make use of the Zionist hegemonic conception of Jewish and Zionist identities as being merged into one, by which an attack against Zionism can be easily characterized as an attack against Judaism and Jews in general. Jewish academicians, who have been outspoken against Israeli policies, have been often called 'self-hating Jew', which has become an automated response to any criticism, which enables to not look into the content, by de-legitimizing the messenger.

It has become quite risky to express critique of Israel and its Zionist policies, or of Zionism as a nationalist identity, ideology or discourse, since often it has been met with an 'automated' defensive reaction accusing of anti-Semitism. Judith Butler (2004) has written a 20-page article analyzing a two-sentence excerpt of a speech given by then Harvard President, Laurence Summers, where he suggests criticism of Israel end up being anti-Semitic if not by intent, then by effect. She deconstructs the thinking behind his words, which intent is to stifle any

criticism of Israel. As Butler points out, no academic wants to have his/her name associated with a stigma of anti-Semitism. Post-Zionism is a critique of Zionism, and the use of anti-Semitism as a threat against it supposes Zionism is connected to Judaism in its essence, and any criticism or antagonism towards one automatically is towards the other as well. Harvard University President Laurence Summers's words represent to me the embodiment of a perception of Judaism and Zionism as 'merged' concepts, and it is central to the discussion in this work.

In the academic field the fusion of Judaism and Zionism was, and still is only possible through the separation of the subject of Jewish History, with its mythical dimension, from field of General History, with the influences it suffered from, and was forever changed by Marx's Historical Materialism. Professor Zeev Sternhell (1998, p.X) warns about the implications of maintaining separation in universities of Jewish History from General History, generating an impediment for critical thinking in the field, as I discuss further down in the education section of the chapter on Zionist socialization.

The interviewees in this work are not academics, but they are subject to these same aspects in their Zionist identity: *Jewishness, security/militarism, and a hegemonic Zionist conception of the state.*

3. Reflecting on Identity, Identity-Change and Zionist Identity

This work discusses cases of people that have gone through a process by which they come face to face with a gap between what their Zionist identity upholds and what they encounter through direct experience. These discrepancies cause them to question Zionism, its morality and legitimacy. Since Zionism is a hegemonic discourse, which relies on having achieved dominance through consent, its historical narrative elements and the identity it has structured for Jews becomes challenging to question, especially so since the construction process is not part of the collective memory. Recapitulating Foucaultian and subsequent Saidian theories discussed in previous sections of this work, as a hegemonic discourse, Zionism presents discursively 'regimes of truth', which derive their credibility from 'establishment academics' basing their findings on science. This structure then defines not only what is 'truth' but also what and how one 'knows', since the 'apparatuses' that support this truth and knowledge, either by promotion or acceptance, have high credibility among their target public, such as schools, state structure and collective culture. This 'political knowledge' drives its unsuspecting mass-consumers in a direction defined according to the hegemonic class. It is such an all-encompassing domain that an individual seems to be powerless against it. However, once some element of it does not withstand scrutiny, or collapses before events where direct experience does not confirm that element of hegemonic discourse, it seems to generate a ripple effect where doubts regarding the rest of its structure multiply. To question Zionism seems to represent a high risk of losing trust in everything around, one's own identity, family and friends, and the larger collective of Jewish community, Israeli society or Jewry worldwide. Reactions vary, from denial to proactive political engagement for change. Many go through a long process of slow and difficult transformation, achieving stages they can characterize their identity differently from 'Zionist'; some remain along the

way in a 'negotiated' intermediate identity, and others resist any kind of questioning, or co-opt the criticism into formulation of a new, extreme nationalist identity.

The notion of identity derives mainly from the work of developmental Psychologist Erik Erikson, famous for his theory on social development and for coining the term *identity crisis*. He has associated the notions of individual and collective identity, pointing out how they form a unit which is separable but interdependent: "We deal with a process 'located' in the core of the individual, and yet also in the core of his *communal culture*, a process which establishes, in fact, the identity of those two identities" (Erikson, 1994 p.22). It seems to me that this description might account for Zionism as a collective and individual identity. Hegemonic Zionist culture has continuously perpetuated historical narrative and components of Zionist identity over all diversities that exist within the Jewish collective. Erikson points out that in the process of identity formation

the individual judges himself in the light of what he perceives to be the way in which others judge him in comparison to themselves and to a typology significant to them; while he judges their way of judging him in the light of how he perceives himself in comparison to them and to types that have become relevant to him. This process is, luckily, and necessarily, for the most part unconscious except when inner conditions and outer circumstances combine to aggravate a painful, or elated, 'identity-consciousness.' (Erikson, 1994 pp. 22-23)

Within the collectivity, identities seem to bounce off each other as mirrors that give meaning to one another, while upholding certain expectations of each other. As Erikson points out, this co-production and co-maintenance of identities in a group become more salient when identity is challenged, breaking the cycle of intra-group confirmation of this personal/group identity. Many of the interviewees in my research have expressed in various ways changes in interactions with previously close group members, and a surprise at how concrete this co-production and co-maintenance of identity used to be, albeit only perceived by them when they broke away from it.

Erikson uses concepts of both William James and Sigmund Freud, "founding fathers of the psychologies on which our thinking on identity is based," to describe a sense of identity as being "a *subjective sense of an invigorating sameness*

and *continuity*,” as I have previously mentioned. He seems to draw on William James’s notion of a deep connection between one’s identity and one’s own morality, where only through being faithful in action to one’s morality, the individual is overcome by the strongest feeling of being active and alive, at which point an internal voice says to him “this is the real me!” (Erikson, 1994, p.19) Erikson interprets Freud’s personal assertion of Identity as “A deep communality known only to those who shared in it, and only expressible in words more mythical than conceptual” (Erikson, 1994, p.21).

Fearon (1999) discusses a definition for the way the word ‘identity’ is understood in common use. He describes it as

(a) a social category, defined by membership rules and (alleged) characteristic attributes or expected behaviors, or (b) socially distinguishing features that a person takes a special pride in or views as unchangeable but socially consequential (or (a) and (b) at once). In the latter sense, “identity” is modern formulation of dignity, pride, or honor that implicitly links these to social categories. (Fearon, 1999)

He defends that this definition is more concrete than the standard definitions offered by political scientists, and that it gives answers usually sought for in social science, and not explained by theories such as rational choice, namely regarding explanation for action. Fearon argues that based on the explanation of identity as a social category or as the base for dignity or self respect on the personal level, “‘identity’ can explain actions either in the sense that membership in a social category can explain actions, or in the sense that the desire to gain or defend one’s dignity or self-respect can explain actions” (Fearon, 1999, p.26). The relevance of this definition for this work, relates to the motivations individuals presented in the interviews for changing, or at least reflecting on the way they define their identity, which as we will see are closely related to the pursuit of dignity and self-respect. This understanding seems to relate to William James’ connection of identity and morality.

Philosopher Charles Taylor (1992) defines identity as the spontaneous answer to the question “who am I?” where the sought answer

...is an understanding of what is of crucial importance to us. To know who I am is a species of knowing where I stand. My identity is defined by the commitments and identifications which provide the frame or horizon within which I can try to determine from case to case what is good, or valuable, or what ought to be done, or what I endorse or oppose. In other words, it is the horizon within which I am capable of taking a stand. (Taylor, 1992, p.27)

Taylor (1992, pp. 27, 28) also discusses the notion of 'identity crisis' as the emergence of situations where people need to re-orient themselves in moral space, as they lose a clear notion of who they are or where they stand, and "they lack a frame or horizon within which things can take a stable significance, within which some life possibilities can be seen as good or meaningful, others as bad or trivial. The meaning of all these possibilities is unfixed, labile, or undetermined." Once more, we have the moral imperative influencing identity, as well as identity change, preceded by an identity crisis. I understand these definitions that point to a relation between morality and identity not necessarily need to be taken as a fixed, crystallized or solid in structure, but may be fluid and change according to changing circumstances that redefine moral references.

Laitin and Chandra (2002) published a paper called *A Framework for Thinking About Identity Change*, which might serve as a basis for a theory on identity change. They understand 'identity' as "the category that an individual uses to describe herself. By 'identity change,' [they] mean a change in the category of self-description" (Laitin & Chandra, 2002, p.2). This simple approach can contribute to the clarity of the discussion in this work, by determining for the section on de-identification that change in identity has occurred when an interviewee chose a different category to identify him/herself by. Laitin and Chandra's classification of identity is structured according to three main components: *categories*, *attributes*, and *dimensions*. Individuals use *categories* to describe their identity, for instance 'student', 'grandmother', 'Jewish' or 'Zionist'. In order to be eligible to be part of a category, one must possess certain qualities called *attributes*, which for the category 'student', could mean 'to be enrolled in an educational institution'; for 'grandmother' it could mean 'be female' and 'have a grandchild'; for 'Jewish', it could mean 'to be born from Jewish parents', or 'to have converted to Judaism'; and lastly, for 'Zionism', it could mean to subscribe to

the three pillars suggested in this work, *Jewishness, security/militarism and hegemonic Zionist discourse*. Identity categories of the same kind compose a *dimension*, for instance the dimension of 'student' could be 'occupation'; that of 'grandmother' could be 'kinship'; for 'Jewish' it could be 'religion', and for Zionism, it could be 'national identity'. Again, referring to a possible change under this structure could be simply a change or withdrawal from one of the *attributes* needed to qualify for a *category*, that is, if one does not subscribe anymore to the concept of *Jewishness*, one does not qualify for 'Zionist'. In a further section on de-identification we will come back to these theories and see how they can help us discuss the phenomena analyzed in this work.

The notion of identity was central to the perception of my own process, which led to this study. In my personal perspective, it related to how I perceived who I was, and how that had changed. But as I thought about it further, I found that *identity* was not an isolated concept, nor was it easy to define. There was no 'one identity' that I used to have, and that ceased to exist, which now I had substituted with a new one, different from the previous. Evidently, an identity of an individual is more complex than that. It is multi-faceted and combined of elements of various ranges. Some aspects are closer to the individual, and others are social categories one belongs to. In terms of this work, Zionist identity can be described as an affiliation to Zionist ideology or hegemonic discourse, which in this work translates into identification with, acceptance and defense of the principles of Zionism: *Jewishness, security/militarism* and 'unconscious' subjection to the *hegemonic Zionist discourse*. To "'unconsciously subject' to the past cultural choices of [the] forefathers [...] who helped define the 'tradition' which they [in this case, Zionist Jews] are now endeavoring to defend," according to Shani (2007, p. 13), is "nothing other than the forgetting of history." Shani explains this using Pierre Bourdieu's notion of *habitus*: "embodied history, internalized as a second nature and so forgotten as history – is the active presence of the whole past of which it is a product" (Bourdieu 1990: 56, in Shani, 2007, p. 14).

In this sense, I noticed that Zionist identity as a national identity was discursively constructed in a manner where realms of identity that are closer to the individual and those which are farther and more collective, are both woven

together tightly. I was able to contrast that to my other nationality, Brazilian, where none of those feelings existed towards the state, nor have I ever perceived them in any Brazilian I had ever encountered. As a historical process, discursive construction that had woven together the personal and national identity into one has become forgotten. The notion of Jewish identity, its history and heritage, prior to advent of Zionism, has been forgotten. The construction process has also been forgotten. Now, the *habitus*, is the identity that already exists in a certain form, relying (unknowingly) on discursively constructed connections to ancient Jewish history and territory, where identity, narrative and territory form a unified and crystallized structure, which presents no possibility of separation or questioning to the bearer of that identity. Hence, the challenge for Jews is not whether to question this hegemonic conception or not, rather, it is to overcome an apparent impossibility of questioning it. In this conception, Israel can only exist under a Jewish character, and Jews can only survive if there is a Jewish Israel. When a challenge to the national political configuration of Israel emerges, suggesting a 'real democracy' where Israel becomes State of all its citizens, and no longer the Jewish State, where Jews, Palestinians and any other integrants of the population will enjoy equal rights, it is perceived as a threat. This perception derives from the superposition of identities mentioned before, where the state's *Jewishness* is woven to the people's *Jewishness*. Sonnenschein, Bekerman, And Horenczyk (2010) point this perceived fusion of national identity and personal identities in their study of Jewish and Palestinian university students in Israel:

Among the various threats, the Jewish group evidently had the most difficulty in liberating itself from the threat to Jewish hegemony in the state. When the Jewish group's national identity and the identity of the state itself were perceived as identical, the Jewish participants felt that if they lose Jewish hegemony in the state, they lose their own identity and their national existence, to the point where losing Jewish identity of the state is perceived as another Holocaust. The difficulty in relinquishing Jewish hegemony in the country was expressed mainly in the conception that there is a complete overlap between national (Jewish-Israeli) identity and the identity of the state itself. The problem with this perfect overlap is that it excludes Palestinian citizens of the country from any partnership in it, and gives the Jewish participants the feeling of being the privileged group, the masters of the country. (Sonnenschein, Bekerman, And Horenczyk, 2010, p.61)

Searching for literature published on the subject of individualized processes of identity change amongst Israeli and Diaspora Jews in the context of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict, there was little clear scholarly discussion that would encompass the various aspects of the experience I had undergone. I found side-comments on personal accounts of academics that described part of their personal experience of living through surprising changes regarding their identity, resulting from their own investigations. During my field research, I noticed in the interviews that my understanding of identity had to be better explained for the sake of clarity of this work. The insight I had in my own experience was that I had changed somehow, while recognizing a lot of me had not.

When Kelman (2004, p.120) defends identity change as an approach to conflict transformation and resolution, he affirms that change in identity will imply a strengthening of one's core identity rather than weakening it. Not only I could relate to that on a personal level, but I also noticed it in this research's interviewees as well. They have gone into processes of identity crisis, and 'internal conversation' regarding the relation that existed between how they defined themselves and what they stood for. As they did that, they internalized a new way of looking at the Palestinian 'other', and reached a place where changes in the way they identified themselves were necessary in order to express this new internalized way of relating to the other. While this meant a rupture with Zionist precepts, they felt they were stepping closer to their own true moral values, as Kelman (2004, p.120) points out "Internalization represents a readiness to change an attitude because the new attitude [...] is more consistent with the person's own, preexisting value system." This observation agrees with Erikson's (1994) understanding of William James's assertion regarding the relation between identity and morality. It also relates to Fearon's (1999) assertions on relation of identity and dignity or self-respect, and to Taylor's (1992) notion of identity and moral orientation.

Identity in the Israeli-Palestinian conflict is defined heavily in relation to a hostile 'other'. When a process of humanization of the image of the Palestinian 'other' occurred to the interviewees in this work, it usually occurred by means of a couple of realizations: that Israel has always been in fact the stronger party in the

conflict; that there have been committed grave injustices towards the Palestinians; that Israel is responsible for those injustices; and the discovery that the violence that comes from Palestinians is defensive or of protest. Sonnenschein, Bekerman, And Horenczyk (2010) found similar results in their ethnographic study on a dialogue course conducted at an Israeli university among Jewish and Palestinian students, all citizens of the State of Israel:

Later in the process, the entire Jewish group, and not just individuals within it, abandoned the patterns of behavior designed for collective moral face-saving and began to accept responsibility for being the stronger group in the conflict. When the Jewish participants acknowledged their power and felt less threatened, they were able to see the vulnerability of the other. It is worth reiterating here that the acknowledgment of injustice, acceptance of responsibility for the injustice, and attribution of illegitimacy to the injustice make up perhaps the most significant turning point for all the Jewish participants. This is a process that constitutes identity in the workshop: It was able to liberate the Jews from the role of victim and partially restore their humanity. (Sonnenschein, Bekerman, And Horenczyk, 2010, p.63)

For the interviewees, this newly discovered common humanity seems to account for a logic that was missing in the previously demonized image of Palestinians. The process of becoming able to see the *other* as a human being, different in so much, but similar in so much more, seemed to have brought a release, a deeper understanding, and to many, shame, for not having had such a natural understanding, that they felt should have been obvious to them from the beginning. Many expressed their surprise at how much they were subjected to a socialization process that resulted in an anti-natural divisive identity, and were powerless against it. Recurrence of feelings of taking offense in being lied to by their previously most trusted people, institutions and symbols. This was the case mentioned in previous sections of a few academics, such as Ilan Pappé and Adi Ophir.

As Stuart Hall argues, identities are fluid and constantly being constructed:

Identity is not as transparent or unproblematic as we think. Perhaps instead of thinking of identity as an already accomplished fact, which the new cultural practices then represent, we should think, instead, of identity as a 'production', which is never complete, always in process, and always constituted within, not outside, representation. (Hall, 2003, p.222)

Ghazi Bouillon (2009, p.20) points out “Identity in Israel, though not subject to radical overhaul, is constantly being redefined over time in line with social and political change in the country”. The challenge to *hegemonic Zionist discourse* and consequent struggle over identity that this work discusses happens on at least two fronts. One, which I have discussed in previous sections, is the academic front. Ghazi-Bouillon (2009, p.33) affirms those scholars who defend or challenge the political status quo are no longer ‘objective’ observers, and “contribute to the paradigm of knowledge that is governed by the hegemonic discourse of the state.” She defends that the hegemonic identity and narrative of the Jewish state will only change if there is significant structural change to the *habitus* – to the discourse, and the political realm that constitutes it. Possibly it is a matter of time, considering the production of knowledge and self-knowledge has been at the core of generating the *hegemonic Zionist discourse*, which vis-à-vis increasing challenges might not be able to continue to rely on its self-produced ‘regimes of truth.’

The other front, on which the challenge to *hegemonic Zionist discourse* and consequent struggle over identity happens, is the non-academic one. Those who do not research the matter thus are less involved with its theoretical discussion. However, those are ‘recipients’ of *hegemonic Zionist discourse*, as are academics of course, but their sources for challenging the discourse do not come from academic research. It is quite safe to assume that the people who populate this group are largely unsuspecting Jews, who tend to mass-consume whichever discourse will come their way under the right hegemonic structure. Incidentally, hegemonic power lies in acquiescence from this larger group, since it is them who will choose their political representation according to their identity, culture and political aspirations. Simultaneously, as I discussed before, hegemonic class will rely on intellectuals to generate the knowledge and ‘regimes of truth’, the basis for discourse, historical narrative and identity. However, within this group, to which a large part of the interviewees in this work belong, challenges to hegemonic discourse and identity will be sparked otherwise. These interviewees have experienced a situation where their *habitus* shocked with reality in a manner that it became clear there is a disconnection. To an extent, it becomes an epistemological

question, since what they 'knew' through their submission to the hegemonic discourse, could not uphold against their practical experience, that became their new way of 'knowing'.

"Identity plays against difference", says Ghazi-Bouillon (2009, p.20). In other words, it is against an 'otherness' that a specific identity has its boundaries delimited. Stuart Hall points out Identity "entails discursive work, the binding and marking of symbolic boundaries, the production of 'frontier-effects'. It requires what is left outside, its constitutive outside, to consolidate the process" (Hall, 1996, p.3). These boundaries delimiting identity, who belongs to it and who doesn't, in this work will be represented, as mentioned in this work before, by the three elements defining Zionist identity, *Jewishness, security/militarism and Zionist hegemony*. In the process of changes or shifts in identity, these boundaries may serve as indicators as to whether an individual is on this or that side of them. However, these 'frontiers' can also be used strategically as tools in the hands of those who see a need to make a change in identity, by choosing specifically certain frontiers to cross and other to not cross. In the cases we will see, most of the interviewees are careful to cross the frontier that defines Zionist identity, but to not cross the one defining Jewish identity. These choices that an individual starts to make seem to come about as result of an 'internal conversation', a reflexive process, which is sparked by some experience the individual has lived. This is an entirely different state of awareness from the one described by Shani (2007, p.13) of 'unconsciously subjecting' to a hegemonic discourse. The latter seem to have a passive quality to it, and the former a proactive one of agency.

This work does not attempt to describe the psychological step-by-step process of changes in identity, but to point out the *factors* that have influenced individuals to reconsider their definition of their own identity and their affiliation and loyalties. It tries to bring out to the clear the reasons for these individuals to have been able to challenge the hegemonic discourse and their identity as its product, by pointing out the 'moments' where hegemony did not hold up against reality. The relation this work draws between identity changes of this sort, and politics and foreign policy, is the state can only maintain its cohesion through a hegemonic discourse and a national identity that legitimizes it. Once the state

looses this apparatus, it looses its ascendancy over its constituency. It then becomes vulnerable to (new) competing discourses that may achieve hegemony if they gain access to tools of mass media, control over state apparatuses and a new discursively built narrative, which places identity differently in the national and international context.

4. Identity, Foreign Policy And Conflict Resolution

In producing this Master of Arts thesis some concerns have occupied my mind regarding the contribution I wish this work to produce. In a way, I wish to establish that a deeper understanding of the individualized processes of changes in identity presented in this work can be meaningful to a more complete understanding of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. Yet, the question that rises is 'meaningful to whom?' Evidently, as any work in social science this one is written under the bias of its author, which defines this work's agenda. My personal experience drove me to write this work, out of a curiosity regarding this phenomenon of change in identity, which seems to me, removes from the individuals that undergo such process the most central motors to this conflict on its most powerful side, Israel, and its large supportive constituency, Israeli and Diaspora Jewry. Therefore, the answer to the question I posed 'meaningful to whom?' in my view, would be to any person or group of people, institution, organization or government who sincerely wish to influence this conflict towards a resolution, reconciliation and ultimately transcendence. Returning to my concern as to establishing the relevance of this study in a realm that might be able to, on its far end, influence decision making and policy, I believe this discussion cannot remain within an anthropologic or sociologic circle of knowledge alone, but must be discussed within the political science and international relations realms as well. My concern is intensified since the academic major within which this Master of Arts thesis is being written is international relations, and issues regarding identity are not the easiest to argue in this field. Therefore, I would like to draw some relations between international relations, political science and ultimately, as part of my declared bias in this work, conflict resolution, and the data presented and analyzed in this work regarding changes in identity.

As I mentioned earlier in this work I have encountered literature by Israeli and Diaspora Jewish, as well as non-Jewish scholars, which address the identity question in relation to the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. However, as usually found within political science and international relations literature, their approach is focused on identity as social and collective categories rather than paying any attention to the individual realm and its connections to a larger picture. What I attempt to do is to structure an argument thinking from an international relations perspective, where I can link and point out the relevance of the changes in identity examined to the international scenario and the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. In this sense, within an international relations approach, Israel was born into the setting of the modern international system of states, where identity is based on territory, and where if a group of people does not have a state, they do not exist internationally, since international recognition is given to states alone. This work discusses phenomena where individuals from the Zionist national group escape the hegemonic discourse that structures that group's identity, and become politically active in demanding a change in the configuration of the concept of what or who constitutes the 'nation'. Dov Waxman (2006) writes from the international relations perspective and talks about the crisis in Israeli national identity, and its relation to the Oslo Peace process, and how according to him,

...the domestic debate in Israel over the Oslo peace process was not about Israeli-Palestinian relations at all. It was about Israeli-Israeli relations. It was an intra-Jewish debate [...] in which one's attitude to the occupied territories was served to demarcate on which side of a broader cultural divide one was on. (Waxman, 2006, p.viii)

Ghazi-Bouillon (2009, p.6) disagrees with Waxman in the sense that "the debate over Israeli identity, as reflected through Israeli academia, was far more complex than a conflict between those who favored an 'Israeli' Identity and those who favored a 'Jewish' identity." However in Ghazi-Bouillon's work as in Waxman's, the individual process of identity change is not addressed. Ghazi-Bouillon's criticism of Waxman possibly derives from his understanding that among the plurality that exists in Israeli national identity, there is a polarization around the issue of de-occupying or not the OPT, and what it means in terms of

having a national identity that is more centered in 'Jewish' identity, more ethno-religious, or 'Israeli' identity, a civic conception of the secular-Jewish section of the population. Waxman's analysis appears to be aligned with the section of Israeli and Diaspora Jews whose self-perception is of progressive Zionists, at times pacifists, mostly composed of the *hiloni* (secular) majority, the secularist culture of Ben-Gurion's civic-religious society. Although Waxman considers the debate over the occupation of the OPT to represent "profound differences over the definition of Israeli national identity," he remains within *hegemonic Zionist discourse*, does not question the Jewish nature of the State of Israel, nor the questions, of security/militarism, victimhood and responsibility. It might prove difficult for his analysis to account for Israel's foreign policy's general direction staying the same, despite internal disagreements, since it does not consider the foundations of Zionist identity critically.

Nevertheless, I do agree with Waxman's take on the role that identity plays in international relations and foreign policy. He defends that identity, through identity politics, has an impact on foreign policies of states,

...which all-too-often are believed to be dictated by *Realpolitik* considerations of security and power. According to the widely held "realist" view of International Relations, states are solely motivated by their need for power and security in order to survive in the anarchic conditions of the international system. For realists, security concerns underlie both the foreign policies of states and the violent conflicts between them. While this exclusive focus on security and conflict has often been criticized for slighting other important aspects of international politics (such as international cooperation and international trade, to name just two), it also fails to take into account the role that identity politics can play in shaping states' foreign policies and in fueling conflicts, both within and between states - a serious omission for a perspective that is principally concerned with issues of national security. (Waxman, 2006, p.5)

Waxman's assertion assists me in making the point I am aiming for, which is to underpin my understanding that focus must be made on identity in order to make better sense of a situation such as the Israeli-Palestinian conflict, and in order to approach it more constructively. I have pointed out previously in this work that official political attempts of resolution for this conflict have so far worsen the situation, thus traditional approaches will not suffice, as Waxman (2006, p.6) points out, it will require Israelis "not only to make territorial

concessions (according to the formula of 'land for peace'), but also identity concessions. They [have] to revise their own national narrative and self-image." At the same time Waxman attempts to contribute in his book to an understanding of how "collective identities are resistant to change and the ways in which they can complicate peacemaking efforts". Once more, this stresses the need that I point out in this work for a better understanding of the inner workings of processes of change in identity. It appears that such knowledge might prove useful for initiatives of interventions that seek to deal with the problems Waxman pointed out. Waxman also points to the importance of international relations taking into account identity politics, as its main concern as a field of knowledge is national security, to which issues of identity have been proving to be capable of being a serious threat.

Fearon (1999) points out the resistance within political science in regard to discussion focused on identity:

With some important exceptions, political scientists have generally held back from this most recent round of inquiry concerning identities, often treating both the concept and humanities research using it with skepticism. This is partly skepticism by association. A rough correlation obtained between recent work focused on 'identity' and postmodernism, which often seems to reject social science as an empirical enterprise of any value.

But political scientists' skepticism about 'identity' stems also from the vagueness and implicit complexity of the term itself. (Fearon, 1999, p.36)

The 'vagueness' and 'implicit complexity' Fearon refers to, which were discussed previously in this work, most likely include the existence of multiple dimensions to identity, as well as multiple categories. Waxman (2006, p.8) observes, "Of all contemporary categories of collective identity, national identity is often the most powerful." He explains:

Most scholars agree that a major reason for the strength of national identities is the role that states play in sustaining them (through public ceremonies and festivals, for instance, and in its memorabilia, symbols, and monuments). States deliberately foster and promote national identities out of a need to ensure their popular legitimacy and the loyalty of their citizens. [...] Even in so-called postmodern Western societies, where the process of globalization is most advanced, people are continually reminded of their national identity in political discourses, cultural products, the media, and a host of other ways. (Waxman, 2006, p.8)

Assuring national identity is dominant in people's minds, in the way they see the collective, themselves, and how they identify and integrate with that collective, which in the case of this work is Zionist identity, guarantees that certain policies will be supported. As to the influence national identity has over foreign policy, Bloom (1993) writes:

The mass national public will is thus shown to be a discrete actor in the foreign policy decision-making process: The mass national public will always react against policies that can be perceived to be a threat to national identity. The mass national public will always react favorably to policies which protect or enhance national identity. (Bloom, 1993, p.80)

Waxman (2006) refers to constructivist theory of international relations to argue that it is by first knowing who one is, that one's interests can be known, thus, interests presuppose identity. He argues that

An identity in influences an actor's preferences by shaping what s/he regards as appropriate, intelligible, and/or desirable. In line with this argument, a national identity can shape the definition of national interests that, in turn, determine a state's foreign policy and, by extension, behavior. Thus, it is by means of shaping national interests that a national identity influences foreign policy. (Waxman, 2006, p.11)

Action or behavior seems to reinforce identity, which seems to constitute a cycle - State control over national identity production/maintenance - which manufactures the consent needed for foreign policy aligned with that national identity - which in turn reinforces that same national identity. Thus, The processes that are discussed in this work, can possibly shed light on how this cycle is broken, by the interruption of State control over production of national identity sparked by, in the case of the interviewees, direct experience which is incongruent with the national identity and its constitutive discourses, or in the case of scholars, information and knowledge discrepant with that identity.

Returning to the political science discussion, it seems to accept better and discuss more assertively the 'social category' or 'collective' aspect of identity since it is less 'vague' and 'complex'. But here we find reason to argue for the importance of political science to consider the 'personal' dimension of identity as

well, since, as we Recall Fearon's discussion on identity in section 1.5, in which he defines identity apart from membership in a social category as a modern formulation of dignity, pride, or honor, in which sense he defends 'identity' can explain actions, both as membership in a social category can, or resulting from a wish to attain or defend values such as dignity, pride, honor and self-respect. (Fearon, 1999, p.26).

The cases analyzed in this work show processes by which individuals have been resisting the dominant identity inscribed by the state. It also shows how motivated by a desire to regain or defend their dignity, self-respect, honor and pride, they engage in political action. Defending the idea of identity being the representation of the values above mentioned, Fearon argues 'identity' can help explain political actions, a long time challenge in political science:

If this is a reasonable statement of the meaning of 'identity' as now used, then political scientists have no good reason to avoid the concept. Quite the contrary, both social categories and the sources of individuals' sense of self-respect or dignity are *obviously* relevant to understanding politics in many of its aspects. It may be that in specific cases it is better to dispense with 'identity' and analyze instead the politics of social categories and the political implications of desires for dignity, honor, and self-respect. These are more concrete objects of analysis than 'identity,' which links together social categories and the sources of self-respect in a somewhat murky (unarticulated) way. Even so, there is no good reason to try to banish 'identity' in favor of these more specific component ideas. By putting together social categories and the bases of our self-respect, 'identity' makes a suggestive connection between two important aspects of social and psychological reality. (Fearon, 1999, p.37).

This connection between social and psychological reality that Fearon points out, I understand as the connection between the changes in identity described in this work to possibilities of change in the political reality of the State. Post-Zionism may become a critical approach to Zionism that will force the character of the State of Israel to change over time. As I have previously discussed, there have been several conditions that allowed post-Zionism to emerge: the social evolution of Israeli society from a forcibly homogenized society under Labor Zionism, into a fragmented pluralistic society under the heirs of Revisionist Zionism. This more controversial social context allowed for a more critical generation of historians to create a New Historiography, which happened to rely on solid evidence. Having

no way to maneuver out of this situation since the evidence were governmental official documents, this new knowledge found its way into the heart of academic debate. It was out of that debate that the critical scholarship of post-Zionism emerged. For the first time, experiences that have been lived by people similar to the interviewees in this work since the inception of the Jewish State could be articulated not only by academics, but by non-academics as well. Now, there was a new knowledge in place that warranted those experiences as real. Now they could be spoken of, thought of, and rejected, since *Zionist hegemony*, which kept that from happening, had been broken. Understanding this personal experience allows seeing it as a possible building block for larger significance. However non-measurable it is right now in the Israeli national context, the reactions of the Israeli government have been of perception of serious threat coming from post-Zionist thought.

The possibility of shift from Zionism to post-Zionism, or some other framework of critical approach to Zionism may represent a change in national identity that will extensively affect the situation of conflict. Waxman (2006) discusses the relation between identity and conflict resolution:

The politics of collective identities (national, ethnic, religious, etc.) drive many violent conflicts around the world. These "identity-based conflicts" tend to be especially protracted and hard to resolve. Increasingly scholars and practitioners in the field of conflict resolution now emphasize the necessity of addressing and reconciling the identify needs of both sides in a conflict. Failure to take into account the importance of collective identities, according to this line of thinking, will doom peace negotiations and the settlement of intractable conflicts. It has even been argued that changes in collective identities are necessary in order for a protracted conflict to be fitly transformed into a peaceful relationship, and that true reconciliation between enemies requires the development of new collective identities. (Waxman, 2006, p.5)

Waxman proposal of 'development of new collective identities' as 'reconciliation between enemies' has been featured in progressive conflict resolution approaches, such as one I have mentioned in the discussion over identity, proposed by Herbert C. Kelman, professor emeritus at Harvard University. Kelman had an active role in the track II meetings that led up to the Oslo agreements in the 90's, and his proposal of reconciliation as identity change

(Kelman, 2004) reflects some of the points covered in this work, such as revision of narrative and others. However, I am skeptical in regard to such approaches because they have been designed always in a bi-national dialogic structure. This kind of approach seems to leave out an internal dynamic of debate over identity, which appears to be its natural *locus*, e.g. Waxman's (2006) assertion on the discussion over the Oslo peace process in Israel: It was not regarding Israeli-Palestinian relation, but rather Israeli-Israeli relations, where national identity was being debated and defined according to political positions on the occupation of the OPT. It is my understanding that in a bi-national interaction which would include both Jews and Palestinians, the tendency would be to polarize and defend each one's identity, rather than go through a difficult process of self-criticism and identity change, where vulnerabilities are exposed. Sonnenschein, Bekerman, And Horenczyk's (2010) pose an example for the differences between bi-national and uni-national settings of discussion over Zionist identity, leading to a possible assertion of a critical perspective:

When the Palestinians were present, the Jews—to preserve their power—talked about their strong attachment to their national identity. But outside the binational group, when they met alone in the uninational forum, or together with their friends or their family, the Jewish participants felt and expressed guilt and anger about the injustices perpetrated. Their strong attachment to their national identity did not prevent them from also feeling, at the same time, collective guilt. On the contrary; perhaps it was actually because they felt such an attachment and obligation to their national identity that they could feel guilty about the injustices done to the Palestinians. It is possible that this attachment magnified the pain and shock of their discovery of the injustices their group perpetrated against the Palestinians. In structured encounters between Jews and Palestinians, many of the Jewish participants undergo such a process. (Sonnenschein, Bekerman, And Horenczyk, 2010, p.63)

Therefore, I argue that the approaches to conflict resolution, which are structured on identity change processes as their base, have better chance of success if developed in uni-national settings, stimulating internal conversation within the Jewish group. Structurally, I see works such as Sonnenschein, Bekerman, And Horenczyk's (2010), *Threat and the Majority Identity*, which investigated the threat perception in Israeli Jews in interaction with Israeli Palestinians, as being too quick to interact bi-nationally. I believe the same model should be used but in a uni-

national setting, where a Jewish Zionist majority and a Jewish post-Zionist minority can interact with the goal of looking at the problems of Zionist identity, without the deterring presence of foreigners to those identities. I also believe attempts such as the official negotiations during the Oslo process may seem to the international community as a peace process, being that they are called as such, have an official structure as such, and participating political leaderships may present declared intentions of seeking peace. But the identities of the leaders involved, and of the constituencies they represent, as well as the identity of the state they represent, all come into the negotiating room, which paradoxically, it is those same identities that by their own nature make conflict the only possible interaction. Thus if the stage of high-level political negotiations ever occurs again, I consider the chances of success depend on reduction of presence of bellicose identities on that level, and in the case of this work, that means a reduction of presence of Zionist identity, or its dissolution.

Approaches that call for change in Zionist stances towards the Palestinians have attempted to make use of supposed universally accepted international values, such as international law and human rights. Calls from governments, the UN and international NGOs have all revolved around such notions, and if I honestly ask myself the question of how could they do it otherwise, I am not sure whether the possibility even exists, since these moral references stem from the structure itself, the international system, the same one that does not recognize the existence of identities with no territory. However, mechanisms by which these international moral references are alienated from of Israeli society, and by extension from Zionist Jews in the Diaspora, has been observed by Sonnenschein, Bekerman, And Horenczyk (2010)

Societies whose internal minorities do not enjoy full human rights develop varied and elaborate mechanisms of cultural denial (Cohen, 1995). Cultural denial refers to situations in which an entire society exists in collective denial but is not subject to a totalitarian regime. Without anyone telling them what to think or what not to think, and without punishing those who know what it is forbidden to know, societies come to an unwritten consensus about what can be acknowledged publicly. People learn to behave as if they actually believe the information that they inwardly know to be untrue, but they will never admit this. This may well be the same process we have witnessed in the group process in this study. (Sonnenschein, Bekerman, And Horenczyk, 2010, p.62)

According to Lilly Weissbrod (1997, p.62), who in my understanding rights from the Zionist perspective, Israel has developed a 'society-specific' identity, where a unique collective identity is highly valued, and made impossible to be based on universal values. Weissbrod (2002, p.222) argues that Israel's democracy, which is conceptualized as Jewish-ethnic, is merely the Israeli interpretation of the concept of democracy, just as any other Western society interprets its own. She believes the Israeli secular camp's attempt to shake Judaism from its political system means to "lose its identity and its right to its patrimony" (Weissbrod, 2002, p.209).

I would like to finalize the argument for the relevance of this research. I believe there is sufficient support to be found in the disciplines of International relations and political science to warrant a productive discussion on the relation of identity to conflict. This relation should underline the need for strategic thinking involving identity in approaching conflict, whether aiming for resolution, transformation or reconciliation. Universal values such as human rights, international law or democracy do not mean the same in Israeli society as they do to the states or organizations that believe they are universal. This dissonance between systems of moral reference is one of the products of Zionist identity, founded on, at least, the pillars of *hegemonic Zionist discourse, Jewishness and security/militarism*. However, in the cases examined in this work, it seems that Zionist moral references, which ultimately are the ones that collide with international modernist universal values, ceases to represent the interviewees the moment they find out how those Zionist values translate into social and political reality. Incoherencies and double moral standards appear to corrode the structure of Zionist moral discourse, when the 'other' is perceived as a fellow human being rather than essentially a mortal enemy. Zionism, rather than a unique moral system in the minds of these individuals, epitomizes violence, and violence has been central to Zionist discourse when describing its victimizers. The victim thus becomes as bad as the victimizer.

If the use of universal value language cannot serve as common ground for communication, there is a need for something else in order to meaningfully

discuss this identity problem. This basis in my view needs to be group membership. Jews will listen to Jews, but not unconditionally, as we see in the fierce internal debates around this matter. If the conversation is perceived as a threat, which requires close to nothing to be evoked in Zionists as Sonnenschein, Bekerman, And Horenczyk's (2010) have pointed out "the central role of a sense of threat in the construction of the national identity of the majority Jewish-Israeli group. Feelings of being threatened fill the Jewish-Israeli identity and provide a feeling of unity vis-à-vis the common enemy." If we can learn anything from the interviews it is that this kind of change happens. It does not matter how much it happens at this point, rather just the fact that it is possible, that it can be found, and that it can be articulated in a way that makes sense is enough. The challenge of not sparking the all-pervasive threat perception in Zionists when attempting to challenge their identity, with the aim of discussing dialogically the problematic of Zionism/post-Zionism in an effort to make headway in social justice in the Israel/Palestine conflict, has possibly a few different answers. However, none of them have been traditional approaches of political elites to conflict resolution or peace negotiations so far.

Looking from a standpoint of peace studies, Johan Galtung (2000), which points to the notions of *deep culture* and *structural violence*. Galtung's approach aims to transform, rather than resolve conflicts, by addressing their root causes. In the language of peace studies, this is a similar line of thought to the one presented in this work, which addresses discourse, narrative and identity issues, which underlie the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. Galtung, confirming my criticism of 'official peace negotiations', points to the weakness of negotiating deals such as the mid-90s Oslo peace accords. That agreement led to a temporary cessation of direct violence without addressing social injustices generated by a structural asymmetry in power, what Galtung calls *structural violence*. The latter is underpinned by *deep culture*, which Galtung (2000, p.33) defines as "a web of notions about what is true, good, right, beautiful, sacred," which in this work is referred to as *Zionist hegemony*. Without addressing root causes of violence, direct violence was bound to return, as it did in the year 2000 Intifada.

PART II - INTERVIEWS AND DISCUSSION

Research Methodology

The field research, which results I am discussing in this work, was conducted by me in Israel from July to November 2010. The research was done with Jewish Israelis and Jews from the Diaspora, living in Israel at the time of the interview or who have lived there in the past, and who were brought up in a standard Zionist environment, and have in some way or another stepped away from that identity. The research tried to assert within a larger context and discussion, why did this change in identity happen, and why these changes can be relevant to the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. Standard Zionist environment is defined in this work based on Gahzi-Buillon (2009, p.158) and Kimmerling (2005, I), consisting of three fundamental aspects: *Jewishness, security/militarism and hegemonic Zionist discourse*, that I have discussed in previous sections of this work, and any change observed in the interviewees' identities will be considered in reference to these aspects.

In order to collect the data I had first inserted myself within grass-roots environment, working for organizations that promote social justice and human rights in Israel/Palestine. I searched for the ideal interviewees with what might seem a broad requirement for people unacquainted with the political situation and the power of the *hegemonic Zionist discourse*. The requirement I put forth was I was looking for people who were brought up in standard Zionist environment, and now find themselves removed, distant, withdrawn from their Zionist identity. I received referrals from people I have interacted in work environment in order to reach my interviewees, since within that environment I had the best chance to have access to people with such characteristics, give that Zionist identity is quite dominant in Israel as Ghazi-Bouillon (2009, p.158) affirms. The description of desired characteristics I was looking for in a good candidate for the research did

not include political activism. However, all interviewees happened to be political activists, some of which were on a hiatus at the time of the research. They were all part of organizations that approach the Israeli-Palestinian conflict advocating for social justice in various ways. The methodology applied was of qualitative social research, which was conducted by face-to-face, semi-structured interviews, out of which two were done by videoconference. The approach I used was based loosely on Goal-Free Evaluation (GFE), based on Michael Scriven's work, where the questions are open-ended leaving space for whichever outcomes that might occur, "Since one has not been told what the intended effects--goals--are, one works very hard to discover any effects, without the tunnel vision induced by a briefing about goals" (Scriven, 1975). My concern was to avoid any influence or direction I might have on the interviews due to my own experience. Interviews were recorded, and based on the transcripts I present the contents using excerpts and my own paraphrasing and descriptions, for purposes of keeping this work to a reasonable length.

While selecting interviewees, I attempted to include a wide range of backgrounds, considering the debated tendency for socialization process to influence worldviews. Some interviewees came from leftist progressive families; others came from right wing conservative families; some from nationalist religious families, and others from ultra-orthodox families. Some are Israeli and others Diaspora Jews, some were born in Israel and others emigrated, some are *Ashkenazi*, others *Mizrahi*, and others *Sefaradi* Jews. In this work, I will not be able to present all the data collected, since this is a work in progress and at this stage to use all the data would require do overstep the limits established for this Master of Arts thesis. However, I reserve this data to continue this research in a PhD program, expanding on the political implications influences exerted by approaches based on knowledge of this kind of processes. All names of interviewees used in this work are fictitious, in the interest of protecting their identities.

5. Zionist Socialization

In order to understand the perception interviewees have of how they acquired their Zionist identity, we will look into their own articulation of what were the Zionist values instilled in them during their upbringing. In this section I will explain what I mean by *Zionist socialization*, and I will draw connections between identity, narrative, culture, and belief system. Let us first look into the relation between narrative and identity.

Narrative

As I have mentioned in the introduction of this work, Stuart Hall (1990, p.225) draws a connection between narrative and identity, pointing out how identity gains both positional and strategic value in its placement in historical narrative. The emergence of Israeli New Historiography during the 80's, and its gradual growth in the following decades has caused a stir amidst Israeli academia. A central aspect of Israeli revisionist historiography is confrontation of collective memory and its resulting Zionist identity, against scholarly historiography and its impact on that identity. Bar-On (2004, p.4) describes the Israeli revisionist school as "an attempt to pit historical research against false popular or misconceived 'collective memory.'" Throughout Israel's history, the place of collective memory has been well established, protected and perpetuated. Jewish academia ensured the legitimacy both within and out of Jewish circles. Collective memory or traditional Israeli historiography has been ruled by the field of Jewish History, which occupied and settled the place of the *academic* field of History, being awarded value of fact and scientific truth, unchallenged up until the emergence of

scholarly work by the Israeli New Historians. I mentioned Professor Zeev Sternhell earlier in the section on hegemony, citing his concern regarding separation of Jewish history from general history:

An unfortunate aspect of traditional Israeli historiography is the prevailing separation in universities of Jewish history from general history. The view that Jewish history is a separate area of study has already had many negative results, but in twentieth-century history and especially the history of Zionism, its consequences have been truly appalling. Very often this approach has paralyzed any real critical sense and any effort at comparative analysis, has perpetuated myths flattering to Israel's collective identity and has led many historians of Zionism to lock themselves up in an intellectual ghetto where there are no means of comparison or criteria of universal validity. Such exclusiveness can lead to ignorance. (Sternhell, 1998, p.X)

Sternhell's concern refers mostly to the continuing dominance of Jewish collective memory over time and its, in his words 'appalling' more recent results, obviously referring to the way in which it provided the justifying rationale for the Zionist enterprise since its inception, for which Palestinians have paid a dear price.

Zionist socialization has relied heavily on collective memory perpetuation through its institutions of reproduction of knowledge and culture. "The narratives and images against which the New Historians direct their crusade are to be found in school textbooks, commemorative ceremonies, popular journalism, popular songs, and the speeches of politicians rather than in serious historical research," sais Bar-On (2004, p.4).

Education

As Bar-On (2004) mentions, Zionist education in schools is one of those means of reproduction of Zionist narrative, both within Israel and abroad. Israeli state school system accounts for over 80% (Israeli Ministry of Education, 2011) of Israeli students and is backed by sectors of Israeli/Jewish academia, which provide academic legitimacy to Zionist narrative. Any attempt to break with the *collective memory* version of history is met with strong resistance. To illustrate let us look into a recent occurrence in 2009: The book *Nationalism: Building a State in the Middle East* was included into 11th and 12th grade curriculum. A chapter in the book "for the first time presented the Palestinian claim that there had been ethnic

cleansing in 1948" (Kashti, 2009). The book had been approved because the ministry of education had overseen this content. When it found out about its existence, two months after the book's countrywide distribution to schools, the ministry of education collected back all the copies of the textbook. The text presented a mild departure from Zionist narrative:

The Palestinians and the Arab countries contended that most of the refugees were civilians who were attacked and expelled from their homes by armed Jewish forces, which instituted a policy of ethnic cleansing, contrary to the proclamations of peace in the Declaration of Independence," states the text, which presented the Palestinian and the Israeli-Jewish versions side by side. (Kashti, 2009)

Its character was merely 'mild' because the version was presented as 'claims of Palestinian and Arab countries', and presented side by side along with Zionist narrative giving both the same weight of 'sides' of history. It completely omitted the vast Israeli New Historiography, which affirms the same only in more substantiated and scholarly structure, since its sources are Israeli government official documents declassified in the 80's. These documents describe how well planned and forcible was the expulsion of Palestinians in 1948. The book was published by the *Zalman Shazar Center*, which was created by The Israeli Historical Society and the Israeli government. Its mandate is to "Intermediate between those who work in the History field and the wide public"⁸. Zvi Yekutieli, executive director of the Shazar Center said, "the book has to be aimed at the widest possible consensus and not at the fringes on the left or the right" (Kashti, 2009). Yekutieli's remark epitomizes the calculated preference in Israeli government policy of promoting and sustaining collective memory over historiography when it comes to shaping Jewish perception of history, where guidelines for history teaching in Israel are the 'wide consensus' and not historical fact. Furthermore, Yekutieli ignores the fact that despite political differences among some of the Israeli New Historians, such as Ilan Pappé being strongly left wing post-Zionist, and Benny Morris being mildly right wing conservative and a declared Zionist, there are few differences in their findings, which states the obvious that dispute over the historical facts at hand does not hinge on political affiliation.

⁸ Zalman Shazar Center official website in Hebrew

The struggle between collective memory and New Historiography might seem at times ubiquitous, but

...Despite the observable intensity and conspicuousness of this debate in the Israeli press and media, the entire discourse is actually rather limited to narrow segments of the public. It is a controversy that touches primarily on more educated sections of society, while important sectors of the population are mostly left out of it. (Bar-On, 2004, p.12)

When looking for the prevalent understanding Israelis and Jews in the Diaspora have of Israeli history and how it was founded, Bar-On (2004, p.5) considers it is safe to assume most of the Israeli public still believes in the myths taught in school, regarding what happened in 1948. Notions of Israel being “Little David” and the Arabs being “Giant Goliath”, and of the British not wanting to leave Palestine and undermining efforts to create a Jewish state. Regarding this same myth, as I mentioned earlier, even New Historian Ilan Pappé and post-Zionist philosopher Adi Ophir have manifested how surprised they were to learn the inverse reality in their academic investigations.

Diaspora

Both in and outside Israel it should be noted that on several occasions there has been suggestion of forces that aim to stifle the debate regarding the clash of collective memory and New Historiography, and its relation to the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. Thus whatever little chance there is of including a larger section of the Jewish population in the debate is weakened even further. Such seemed to be the case of Professor Norman Finkelstein’s denial of tenure by DePaul University, Chicago, where he used to teach. The university dean argued the refusal of tenure based on Finkelstein’s aggressive writing style, despite high approval of the department where Finkelstein taught and other committees in charge of recommending tenure (Cohen, 2007). Such was also the case of the call for resignation of Haifa University Professor, Ilan Pappé by the president of the university (Traubman, 2005), as well as calls for resignation of Professor Neve Gordon from the Negev University, also in Israel (Curiel, 2009), who in both cases called for international academic boycott of Israeli academic institutions. Israeli

government's reaction to such scholars has also seemed to reinforce these claims, such was the case of deportation and ten-year-ban of Jewish American scholar Norman G. Finkelstein, explained by authorities as being due to "security concerns" (Senyor, 2008), and the denial of entry to Professor Noam Chomsky in 2010 (Hass, 2010). To this long list we can add Judith Butler's (2004) article mentioned here earlier, regarding Harvard University President's public address, where he associates any criticism of Israel to anti-Semitism, except he does so in an entrapping manner where he affirms that even if anti-Semitism is not intended, the results of such criticisms might contribute to it.

If we look outside Israel, at Jewish communities around the world, there are various institutions through which Zionist education is carried out. Besides Jewish schools that teach Zionist curricula mixed with its Jewish education, there are congregations and youth movements that offer a wide variety of activities many of which, involve Zionist education. When it comes to identity, in most Jewish circles distinction between Judaism and Zionism is unclear, and Zionist education is continuously and actively shaping identities in such manner. Gidi Mark, CEO of *Taglit-Birthright* Israel, the "leading Zionist youth project in the world" (Ynetnews, 2010) said, "I don't think it's political for Jews to support Israel. It should be an integral part of every Jew's identity" (Shabi, 2006). Mark's statement reflects the prevalent perspective of amalgamation of the two identities, Jewish and Zionist, where Zionism is Jewish nationalism that created the state of Israel. *Taglit-Birthright* Israel, a program funded by Israeli taxpayers, Jewish philanthropists and Jewish communities around the world, was initiated in 2000. It originated from a project presented by MK (Member of Knesset, the Israeli parliament) Yossi Beilin, to the Israeli government in the 90's. Beilin, a Zionist left-wing politician known for initiating the secret peace talks, which led to the Oslo Peace Process, is a good example of softer peace groups in Israel, who do not share the same views of the *peace camp/radical left*⁹. The project's stated goal is "to diminish the growing division between Israel and Jewish communities around the world; to strengthen the sense of solidarity among world Jewry; and to strengthen

⁹ In this work, peace camp refers to groups that challenge Zionist core aspects, such as Jewishness, security/militarism and the hegemonic Zionist discourse.

participants' personal Jewish identity and connection to the Jewish people."¹⁰ It awards thousands of young Jewish adults aged 18 to 26 a ten-day program in Israel, free of charge. The participants

Spend 10 days on a jam-packed itinerary - including a mud-rub at the Dead Sea, a camel ride and dinner in a Bedouin tent, clubbing at Tel Aviv port, day trips to the holy sites in Jerusalem and the Holocaust Museum - as trip organizers work tirelessly to market a problem-free Middle East with Israel as a Jewish utopia in its midst. (Molayem, 2010)

The scope of the program's impact lies in the large numbers it has the opportunity to influence. "In the 10 years since its creation, Birthright has brought some 265,000 Diaspora youths to Israel to strengthen their connection with the state and their Jewish identities" (Ahren, 2010).

Culture

Besides educational means of reproduction of collective memory, there are cultural channels contributing to the same end. Erik Erikson, who as mentioned in the section on identity in this work, has brought up the necessary relation between individual identity and group identity "views the entire process of identity clarification as "cultural consolidation"" (Bar-On, 2004, p.5) Thus, Zionist culture has been reproduced through institutionalized

... rituals, festivals, ceremonies and myths. To forge itself into a single firm entity, it had to engage in continual public cultural activities and to invent a unifying collective memory. Such a novel system of accessible norms and practices was also needed for the overarching consciousness, an amalgamating ideological consciousness: namely, nationalism. (Sand, 2009, p.39)

To speak of culture, is to speak of collective identity, and collectively held beliefs. Ideology is also connected to the same notion, since it is defined as a system of social beliefs. If we revisit the Bourdieu's notion of *habitus*, it is based on a *belief* history developed in a certain fashion. In Eidelson's (2003, p.183) discussion of belief systems that propel groups to conflict, and how these beliefs parallel on the individual and group levels, he says that "in contrast to core beliefs an

¹⁰ *Taglit* Birthright Israel official website - www.birthrightisrael.com

individual holds about his or her personal world, collective core beliefs or group worldviews are the template through which group and group members interpret their shared experience. Such beliefs are an essential component of group culture.” Bar-Tal affirms, “A group’s essence can be defined by shared beliefs among group members. These beliefs stem from similar experiences and elaborate socialization processes, and they are viewed as basic truths and held with great conviction” (Bar-Tal, 1990, 2000 in Eidelson, 2003, p.183). Eidelson points out Psycho-cultural and psychoanalytical perspectives as well, which emphasize “collective templates for understanding the world emerge from culturally determined common experience and shared frame of reference, with dynamics often operating at levels beneath full consciousness.” In making his argument, Eidelson refers to other definitions of culture by Triandis and Lustick: Triandis (1996 p.407) says, “an examination of a range of definitions of culture indicates that almost all researchers agree that culture is reflected in shared cognitions, standard operating procedures, and unexamined assumptions.” The analysis of beliefs that have gained hegemonic status in a group in Lustick’s (1993) work, indicate they stop being evaluated since they are inferred as truth. According to Eidelson (2003), “unless dramatically challenged, data and feedback discrepant with a core belief typically either escape notice all together or undergo reframing to be consistent with preconceptions.”

Production of Zionist culture has also reproduced such collective memory in more fluid and pervasive forms. Stuart Hall (1997) explains, “Culture is about shared meaning”, and “language is the privileged medium in which we ‘make sense’ of things, where meaning is produced and exchanged”. He says that language is able to do this due to its inherent property of representation, where symbols used in language stand for things in the realm of reality. Zionist ideology has produced a homogenous system of shared meanings among Jews in Israel and elsewhere, which is structured around strong connections between linguistic representation and shared experiences and/or *supposed* experiences, which give structure and life to the foundational concepts of adopted in this work, *Jewishness*, and *security/militarism*, and *hegemonic Zionist discourse*. Culture’s presence in society is all encompassing and permeates all circles of society from the family

nucleus to the community, and to larger abstract groupings such as the city, the 'people' and the 'nation'.

Summarizing, Zionist socialization is founded upon collective memory narrative reproduced by education and culture, as well as state institutions and state-supported or state-related institutions, and mass media; encompassing all social circles an individual takes part in throughout his/her upbringing and adulthood.

5.1 Interviews

Yosef

Born in Jerusalem in 1981, Yosef was raised in a family who used to vote for progressive left-wing parties such as *Meretz* and. These political parties were considered to be located to the left of the Labor Party in the political scene, and had promotion of peace as a large part of their agenda. Nevertheless, they were and are still under the banner of Labor Zionism, which meant any conception of peace they sustained did not account for social justice based on Israeli New Historiography and post-Zionist thought. Constituencies of these parties historically have viewed themselves as 'peace supporters' or even 'peace activists', and still do. What differs in the rationale of this section of the Jewish Israeli and Diasporic constituency, considered a 'softer' and mostly Zionist peace groups, from the *peace camp* or *radical left*, relates to a divide that intensified with the New Israeli Historiography. The softer section believes the problem lies only with the occupation and its origin in 1967. There is a belief that ending the occupation will solve all problems. While it is true that ending the occupation might represent serious headway for peaceful coexistence, this solution does not account for the 1948 Palestinian Nakba (Arabic for *catastrophe*). New Israeli History showed there had been an ethnic cleansing, which occurred around and during the 1948 Israeli war of independence. Accounting for this part of local history would mean basically two things: Admitting Zionism has had questionable morals since its inception, and pursuing restorative justice and reparations for the Palestinian people. Thus, the Zionist leftist peace groups stand far apart from the knowledge

that forms the *peace camp* or *radical left*. Yosef's parents also supported the pro-peace movement *Peace Now*.

...we would never drive through the territories, so I actually never knew what was going on... or understood the context. I could relate to things that *Peace Now* (one of the most important peace movements) were saying [...] but I never actually understood the context. [...]Cause my family would stay away, they would say 'that's not for us, it's not ours, we don't even drive through, let alone find a cheap place to live somewhere else...'

Yosef was quite active in the Jewish scouts youth movement, *Hatzofim*, which is one of many movements that are not only active in Israel, but also anywhere there is a Jewish community around the world.

Youth movements educate young Jewish children throughout their adolescence and onto adulthood in Zionist ideology, each one according to its political inclination. Some movements have socialist principles as part of their foundation and are rooted in Labor Zionism; others are rooted in revisionist Zionism; Religious movements vary in degree of observance, and are rooted in religious Zionism or the National Religious Party. These movements compose an important ideological pillar that has always sustained the Zionist enterprise and continuously provided it with new supporters. It is not uncommon for many of these youth movements to think of themselves as apolitical, which means they do not affiliate themselves with any political party. However, this *apolitical* self-perception of some movements, or the political affiliation of others, does not include Zionism in their political considerations, at least not the two pillars of Zionist identity pointed out by Kimmerling (2005) and Ghazi-Buillon (2009), Jewish character of the state and its military/security imperative. This extricates the understanding of Zionism from the political sphere, and places it within the identity sphere: if one is in a youth movement, one is Jewish, and thus one must be Zionist. After Israel's foundation, youth movements in Diaspora communities focused on educating youth up until they would reach an age where they would be encouraged to move to Israel, in Hebrew to do 'Aliyah', Hebrew for 'ascension', where the youth would 'ascend' to Israel. Movements in Israel used to focus on settling the land and on developing new settlements.

Yosef was a central leader and took part in opening new chapters of his youth movement in Occupied East Jerusalem; in the Israeli town of *Afula* for young new immigrants from Ethiopia; in *Acco*, for young new immigrants from the Caucasus. He was so involved with this endeavor that he delayed his army service in two years to pursue these goals. In Israel, military service is compulsory for men from age 18 to 21, and for women from age 18 to 20. Yosef was head of his *Gar'in* (Hebrew for 'nucleus'), which was the youth movement group in which he was acting. This same term, *Gar'in*, has been used since early 20th century Ottoman rule over Palestine, designating groups of Jews that would move together to Palestine and form communities, many of which later became *Kibbutzim* (Hebrew plural for *Kibbutz*, agrarian community based on socialist model).

I was religiously in the youth movement, and it was one of the most empowering experiences... I think any... I think something very special about Israel... that's rooted in Israel's kind of foundation in it's past is the youth movement, and I still think it's something very very special about Israeli society... and it's definitely built who I am... I mean, the tools that I received growing up in the youth movement is definitely something that's part of me today, it built me to do what I do and who I am today. So I grew up in the youth movement, I was actually a very poor student in high school because I was in the youth movement active all that time...

After a postponement of the service in order to continue his work with the youth movement, known in Israel as 'Service Year', Yosef joined the army. His transition into the military phase of his life was through a program that allowed him to do so with his friends from the youth movement's *Gar'in*. This way, his social group could maintain its structure and nomenclature, only now adding to it the name of the infantry brigade: *Gar'in Nachal* (*Nachal* in Hebrew is an acronym for *Noar Halutzi Lohem*, in English 'Fighting Pioneer Youth'). Historically, this particular brigade combines military service and establishment of new agricultural settlements, and more recently it included welfare and social projects. Keeping the friendship circle provided a smooth transition from one phase of his Zionist education to the next. In reality, large part of the education in the youth movement

provides a preparation to face what is about to happen in the next phase, the army.

When you grow up in the scouts youth movement, which is already in uniform, we already like... we start training for the army since the fourth grade... like, you are eleven years old, and you are already training for the army... you know how to jump into bushes, you know what a commander is... as you get closer and closer, and older and older, you know, 15, 16, 17... that's what it's all about. Whether you notice it or not, aware of it or not, as you are being empowered in the youth movement, and you get to run these wonderful project with your group, and you are empowered to do whatever, it is always in the context of - this is preparation for your army service, for your leadership, for your ultimate role as an Israeli, to be part of the...

Q: Did the service then seemed like a natural continuation of that?

Absolutely, absolutely... it was... in the army it very much is... I mean it is run by kids... the fact that my commander... the person who runs Hebron today, is 22, 23 year old kid?! He runs the town; he runs firearms... These are kids... and it's all of them, the continuation of the youth movement.

Youth movements other than the scouts, which might not have uniforms and chain of command, may offer similar preparation for the military in different configurations, through playful or symbolic methods that contribute to the same imaginary. In Yosef's case, this transition makes it smoother and seemingly continuous, blurring the lines between civilian and military life.

Yosef tells about his experience during the second Intifada, the Palestinian revolt, during a period where many suicide bombings were carried out

I was in the army during the second intifada, between 2001 and 2004, am... reality here was really extreme... things were blowing up all the time in Jerusalem... I grew up going to funerals, you know, all the time... during the 90's because buses were blowing up on this side, I didn't know what was going on in the occupied territories... by the time it was my turn to go to the army I was ready, you know? I was like: "I'm ready!" My friends had already been killed, my math teacher, my youth movement counselor, we've been to the cemetery so often the joke was we needed to get a membership card, 'cause we're there all the time. By the time it was my turn to go to the army, I'm like: "I'm there!" And we went through basic training, and we're just waiting for something to happen because the Intifada is going on around us in the meantime and we're really waiting to reach the front line... and that's the point, we're gonna go guard the borders of our country

It seems having witnessed so much violence and not having had access to explanations that would make Yosef understand where that violence was coming from, and having had the anti-Semitic rationale being taught to him all his life, contributed to Yosef becoming more radicalized in his nationalism. Military training within such context also leads to certain predispositions on top of the preparation it provides for the soldiers, which given the opportunity will undermine the chances for resolving unstable situations peacefully

the first assignment was to just stand in guard, right? That's what we do most of the time in the army; we stand around in guard and wait for something to happen. We really want to shoot something, because that's what we're there for, we're trained to shoot, you know? A chef is trained to cook: wants to cook! Soldiers trained to shoot: want to shoot! Waiting for some action.

At this point, Yosef has been fully socialized in Zionist culture and narrative. He holds a well-established Zionist identity, which he shares with his friends and family, and the wide majority of Jewish Israeli population and Jewish Diaspora. He upholds the core pillars of Zionism, which this work adopts as essential to all forms of Zionism nowadays: *Jewishness, security/militarism, and Zionist discourse hegemony*. Under this condition, he feels a deep connection to the land relying on his Jewish background, although he is secular; he needs to defend his country against its enemies, the Palestinians, which if given the chance intend to destroy it; and he is absolutely unquestioning and unsuspecting of Zionism.

Amos

Amos, 30, is a political tour guide in Jerusalem, as well as a Flamenco musician. He arrived at my apartment for the interview, having been released from Israeli police custody a few weeks earlier. He was arrested for having participated along with his older brother in the 'Jewish Flotilla to Gaza', an attempt to break the military siege imposed on Gaza by Israel, and bring much needed provisions and aid to the Gazan population. This attempt followed the much-reported 'Gaza Flotilla' where several activists had been killed by Israeli forces.

Amos is from a small neighborhood, built especially for pilots by the Israeli Air Force, in *Ramat Hasharon* region. His father was a pilot, and was an air-force commander for 20 years. He commanded forces during the Lebanon war in 1982, while Amos's mother, politically a leftist, was very critical of the war from the start, and of his father's participation in it. After his career as a pilot, he became an Aerial Industry man and later Military Industry man, becoming the representative for all South America. For this reason, Amos lived in Santiago, Chile, for a period of his childhood. Therefore from his father's side, Amos had a full militaristic influence, having a lot of incentive to perform highly in his military service, as well as from his siblings: One of his brothers was a pilot; the other was in the top elite unit in the IDF; one sister was an intelligence officer; the other was a combat instructor. Amos's family political stance was leftist, occasionally taking part in pro-peace demonstrations, having a will of acting in a principled way but "not knowing what is really going on" says Amos. He served in a special combat unit and was very dedicated. The entire experience was very exciting, being strong, defending the country.

Amos was in the last year of his military service when he was ordered his first mission in the OPT. This was his first real contact with Palestinians. His previous experience was at the border with Lebanon in the north, where he had had some combat experience but never face to face. He and his unit had shot from a distance at some targets, and as he describes it

I shot houses 2 kilometers away, and after 10 minutes you could see ambulances through the binoculars... so you think 'it works. Something happens when I shoot...' You see it happen, but there is a total disconnection. You don't think of people, of yourself in some house and suddenly a rocket falls on you.

In the OPT, Amos did not become politically critical. He did not witness any direct violence against Palestinians, but he took part in the oppressive treatment of Palestinians without questioning much, since at the time the rationale was they were to blame for the situation (more than usual) since Ehud Barak had offered them a generous deal, which Arafat rejected. Under these circumstances, Amos was part of the apparatus that controlled Palestinian lives and their freedom of movement. To illustrate, he describes a practice used to generate more

acquiescence from Palestinians to Israeli military orders. He would confiscate car keys from drivers who broke prohibitions, leaving them stranded in the middle of the road. To illustrate the lack of respect towards Palestinians and their rights, Amos describes how closures were imposed in a bureaucratic chaos, where orders were unclear, and soldiers enforcing the closure were sometimes doing so when there was no official closure declared.

The first mission Amos took part in occurred following September 11th. It was the first time Amos had killed people.

I felt like a hero afterwards, because they managed to shoot at us at a certain point, and a bullet passed over my back and cut my friend's water canister belt. This bullet was my battle story. I thought about how I would tell it to people and to whom. I wanted to keep my modesty in front of my friends who were all non-combatant soldiers, so I was also a little shy in telling it.

The operation continued on after the fire exchange that was pretty much unidirectional, according to Amos. He had the mission of exploding a bridge as a collective punishment to that local community. Collective punishment is not discussed in any way as something wrong or forbidden by international law. Amos was curious, though not regarding those prohibited practices. It was regarding situations where it is not clear whether to shoot or not, such as encounters with civilians. He wanted to be sure he is staying within the moral code Zionist soldiers swear to uphold called 'The Purity of Arms'. Answers were vague at best. Amos had to stop asking at a certain point, since there was no answer. As far as 'The Purity of Arms' goes, which as a principle is taught at the beginning of the military training that instructs to only use lethal force in defense of one's own life and in defense of the lives of others, at this stage "afterwards [after the basic training] it is kind of obvious... we are *so ethical* that this is no longer discussed," Amos says ironically. What *is* talked about, is that while there is presence of civilians, Israeli soldiers

have to come before the enemy. Even if the enemy is unarmed, even if it is a girl. In any case, if there is any chance of danger, which can be a three-year-old that is carrying a bomb because someone had put in him a bomb, not because the child is ill-intentioned but because his parents are, then it is you first... even if a kid runs at you from inside a house, there can be a situation where you have to shoot. Then

I ask: 'wait a minute, shoot to kill?' and answers are vague... But yes, in worst case, shoot to kill.

Amos explains this blurring separation between common sense and absurdity where shooting a toddler becomes acceptable defensive practice would turn his and his colleagues' relation to the local population into complete animosity.

If you can see that you are able not to kill a pregnant woman, then don't kill her, but only if you see it will not endanger anyone. All those discussions we had in high school about the Purity of Arms completely evaporate and in the end you do what you need to do.

During the same military operation, while Amos was taking care of exploding the bridge, which was his specialty, he recalls the body of one of the people they had killed laying on the ground next to him.

I looked at him and told myself I was supposed to feel something. I didn't feel anything. I told myself 'remember his face because now you don't feel anything' but I don't remember his face even though I tried... I was about half an hour next to him.

Amos recalls other events that happened during that particular military operation: When orders were given to shoot on farmers for suspecting them of being armed from a distance, and there was not only no way of determining that due to the distance, but there was also no danger of them reaching the IDF positions even if they were armed, for the same reason; Another incident was a commander asking a sniper to shoot at an individual who was in the middle of a crowd, again from a distance too far to guarantee any precision, being able to hit five people to either side. Amos reflected a lot about this military operation afterwards and concluded he had no critical view of any of the events at the time. Out of all events of the operation involving killings, violence and house demolitions, Amos focused all his criticism on a commander that decided to do a field briefing, defiantly, in the middle of the battleground. He called for all soldiers to stand up and gather around him risking their lives by exposing themselves during a battle that was not over yet. No one got hurt. Throughout his

service Amos participated constantly in operations in the OPT. He mentions that during all this time, he still did not question anything. He was only very angry with everybody all the time.

Tamar

Tamar, 26, was born in the United States of America. She lived in Israel for one year when she was 9, came back and forth on holiday trips, and moved there as an adult in 2006. Tamar holds Israeli citizenship since her father is Israeli, and she lived in Israel until 2010, time during which she studied at the Hebrew University in Jerusalem. Afterward, she moved to Egypt to study Arabic. Her father was born in the Ukraine and was brought to Israel when he was 12, during the 70s. Five years later he moved to the United States, but those years were very influential in his identity formation. Tamar's mother was born in Jerusalem, and in 1949 moved out of Israel. Tamar was brought up as an orthodox Jew. Growing up in the Jewish orthodox community in New York, she was forbidden from going to the Israel Day Parade, because the Israeli government was secular. In this sense, Tamar was not brought up Zionist as in the sense of elite Ashkenazi (European) Zionism, meaning labor Zionism or revisionist Zionism. She was, however, raised with a notion of Israel being a historical sacred space, not related to political or legal terms, and not as a space having a government.

Of course we knew that [that there was a Jewish government], but when I lived there, it was just a place for Jews to feel comfortable, I knew a lot of stuff about it from reading the Torah, and also from my own family because my grandmother was from there, and her family, and that was a very big part of our identity. It was also the place that took my father out from behind the iron curtain. It was this mystical and important place, and the Jews are holy, and they're one organism, and if something affects Jews in one part of the world, we're affected by it, so in that capacity, that what Israel was. It wasn't a political establishment. It was taken for granted it was a Jewish place.

Tamar lived in Jerusalem for a year in a very religious neighborhood called *Har Nof*. As time went by, Tamar's parent became more Zionist and politically conscious, and purchased a home in Israel. When Tamar moved to Jerusalem in 2006, she did not know much about the conflict: "I was probably like a leftie, but

also had my own prejudices against Palestinians.” Coming to live in Israel and studying at the Hebrew University in Jerusalem, Tamar grew apart from her Orthodox past, which is possibly connected to her becoming what she calls a ‘leftie’. By ‘leftie’, Tamar means she shared progressive Zionist worldview, which although coming from an Orthodox background, she and her family have elaborated for themselves or accepted as many orthodox Jews have, the connection of Judaism and Israel, *Jewishness*, the need for security to protect it from its aggressors, and a hegemonic Zionist view of the situation that dictates what can be thought, imagined or said.

Gil

Gil is seventh generation in Jerusalem on his father’s side. His family has been in the city for about a century and a half. His grandfather was the vice commander to Yair Stern, head of the *Lechi* (Hebrew acronym for *Lochamei Herut Israel*: Fighters for the freedom of Israel), which was one of the Jewish armed militias before the foundation of the Jewish state, and in that capacity he was involved in the infamous King David Hotel bombing. Gil’s mother was also born in Jerusalem to Holocaust survivors. His grandmother was in the last group that was rescued from Auschwitz extermination camp by Raul Wallenberg, a famous Swedish humanitarian who rescued thousands of Jews during the Holocaust. Gil’s mother was extremely Zionist, having served as an officer in the IDF. His father, who used to be head of Police in Hebron for ten years, afterwards he became vice-commander of all Police for Judea and Samaria (Israeli terms used for the OPT), and now is head of investigations of the Jerusalem Police. Gil’s brother was an officer and commander in an elite unit in the IDF.

Gil studied in an arts school, along with many leftists, many of who spoke about refusing to serve the military and doing art instead. He used to feel very angry with them, arguing, “It is because there is an army and because there is a state, on which face they are now spitting, that you they can do their art, and they can live the way they want.”

When he got to military age, he postponed his service in order to take a pre-military course, in order to become the best he could be in the army.

For a 19-year-old, this preparation course is the most amazing thing in the world. 20 boys and 20 girls, placed in a Kibbutz in the middle of nowhere. We study philosophy, Judaism, Islam, Zionism, leadership, we take field trips, navigations exercises, we have deep talks about the army, and deep philosophical talks, and it is group conversations and attempts to understand the group and its ways, and there are boys and girls and hormones... It's a must... It's an amazing year. Gil at age 25 today, looks back at 19-year-old Gil... This body called 'pre-army prep-courses' - things I didn't know back then of course - is funded by the [Israeli] Defense Ministry, its goal is to produce more high quality officers for the army [people who remain over the minimum mandatory years and climb the command ladder], completely brain-washed. There is no space there for different opinions. Nowadays my own prep-course, which continues with the same instructors, does not allow me to come give a lecture on *Breaking the Silence*. The same prep-course that calls itself pluralistic and wants to talk about everything, ...It's a place that turns people's lives narrower and extremely Zionist. I grew up in an atmosphere where the worse thing you could do was to not be Zionist. I was in a pre-military preparation course; we were in *Alon* [name of pre-military prep-course], at *Kfar Edomim*, which is beyond the green line [internationally recognized border separating Israel proper and the OPT]. In the course we had an Identity Seminar, and when they got to me, I said: "I am Jewish, I am Israeli, and I am going to be a soldier." So if you ask me whether it is a question of identity? Yes, it is a question of identity. It is not a question of political opinion.

Gil believes political opinion must derive from your identity, At the time, he could not define himself as a humanist. Nowadays he can, and it necessarily clashes with the Zionist he used to be.

He explained many of these pre-military prep-courses are set in locations that are over the green line (internationally recognized borders which separate Israel and the OPT), which according to Gil is part of the Israeli government's plan of settling the land. Some are in the OPT, others are in the Golan Heights (Syrian territories occupied by Israel since 1967) and others still on Bedouin land which Israel has been slowly expropriating for a long time.

Gil postponed his army service and took part in a Service Year Program where he participated in community or education work under a civilian association named *Alon*, working as part of a team, which in Hebrew is referred to by the term *Gar'in*, meaning core or seed, and used to identify a team of people, which later would enlist into the army together in the *Nachal* Brigade, the same brigade Yosef served in, and later on would serve as a foundation group for a new settlement. The *Gar'in* is composed of both boys and girls, but when the group enlists in the military service, male members typically go to fighting units together

and female members typically go to perform educational activities within the army, although there are exceptions in both cases. This period of the service takes 18 months, and then the group is reunited in a mission-city that is assigned to the unit, and the group goes back to education work, this time in uniform. After this phase the female soldiers are released of their service and the male soldiers return to military combat activities for another year. The hope is that the Gar'in will continue united after the military service ends, and become the foundation for new settlements such as a Kibbutzim (plural for Kibbutz, historically an agrarian settlement based on socialist principles, nowadays having modified versions), most of which started in this fashion. This is the historical role of the Gar'in structure, a vital part of settlement policy of the Israeli government throughout Israel's history. In recent decades, things have been changing and Israel has not been developing many new settlements on its land. Gil's military service had more time focused on military combat than on social and educational work, which seems to him a process of the Israeli government rolling back this kind of settlement project.

Gil's Gar'in was developed under *Alon*, an association considered to be left wing. Under the auspices of this organization he worked in education in schools for a year in *Lod*, a city known for its poverty, social inequality and violence. When time came for his Gar'in to enlist, the whole group was very motivated to become soldiers. "We were very *poisoned* [Hebrew slang describing exaggerated, single-minded motivation of becoming military combatant], we were called *Mechinazim* [word-game of *mechina*, Hebrew for prep-course, and *nazim*, Hebrew plural for Nazi] because we ere very motivated to get into battle." Gil's whole group had decided to become commanding officers and sign up for career military service for at least twenty months beyond the minimum requirement.

Gil has always been very sensitive in relation to the Holocaust. His mother used to say that in a past life he might have been a victim. "I always felt a huge attraction to Nazism, always", says Gil. He has been to Poland twice. Once with the school on an organized trip, which is part of the educational program on Holocaust Instruction, which takes tens of thousands of high-school students to visit extermination camps in Europe. The second time was with his grandmother,

in Auschwitz, where they visited the hut she lived in on the camp during the war. Both times Gil's main curiosity was not directed at the Jews. He questioned how was it possible for the Nazi army to exist? How could they do what they did, and on the weekend go out for a drink?

5.2 Discussion on Zionist Socialization Process

I would like to briefly discuss the socialization process, making some comments and comparing between the four interviewees. Although they do not present a uniform configuration, they do share many of the elements we are looking into in terms of identity.

While Yosef comes from a leftist progressive family, a stance which Tamar also adopted as she grew apart from her Orthodox past, that many times represent an added challenge in itself. People in a Zionist leftist political mindset believe they are part of the most progressive section in Israeli society, feeling they represent those among the Jewish people who are willing to sacrifice the most for peace. The difficulty is the inability to see beyond, out of the belief that *there can be nothing beyond* what they are willing to admit, relinquish, and reconsider. They are on the cutting edge of *Zionist hegemonic discourse*, but do not leave its boundaries.

Yosef has had a long experience in a youth movement. The presentation of Zionism as apolitical, and its placement adjacent to Jewish identity, combines Zionism's elements of *Jewishness* and *Zionist hegemonic discourse*. To participate in a youth movement means to be involved in ideologically motivated action, based on Zionist nationalist agenda. It took priority over school, and although it delayed his military service, Yosef chose to continue because the social and educational work, furthering Zionist ideology gave him a sense of meaning. It is noteworthy that Yossef developed skills in the youth movement of which he is proud, and feels they are of great value to him and a big part of who he is even now, despite he does not identify with the purpose of the movement anymore. Yossef rejects the Zionist parts of that experience, but he values others. It is important to notice that in the complexities of identity, it becomes a major issue to know how to choose the parts one can value and keep, while discarding others, in order to not bring the

situation to a complete rejection of one's identity, which involves great suffering and possibly self-hatred.

Although Yossef does not share with Gil the early ideological initiation in the youth movements, they do share a similar experience in the military, where they went through programs that integrate military combat, youth education and ideally foundation of new settlements in Israel. They transition from their civilian lives into the military, together with their immediate social group, is one of the ways integration of militarism with civilian life occur in Israeli society.

Both Amos and Gil come from families who have had a deep-rooted history of militarism, struggle, and institutional involvement with the state in the military and the police. In those kinds of environments, there is absolutely no question as to whether one is Zionist. Amos had the chance to see his mother disagreeing with his father, and criticizing the Lebanon war. However, differently from Gil and Yosef who as we will see in the next section, started to question things during military service, albeit a little, Amos did not.

In order to understand Amos's mindset at the time, it is important to understand the political context. Amos served during a period, which became famous for the Arafat's refusal of a 'generous' offer made to him by Ehud Barak, Israeli prime minister at the time. The offer was made in Camp-David in the year 2000, and according to Barak offered the Palestinian to meet almost all of their demands. The meetings at Camp David had no official documents drawn, and there is no record of the offer other than through testimonies of participants. Barak came back to Israel and used the slogan "There is no partner for peace" as his reelection campaign. The phrase caught on quickly, since it became apparent to the majority of Israelis that Arafat, and the Palestinians, did not want peace. It confirmed the victimhood rationale that what the Palestinians really want is to eliminate the Jews and Israel. Left wing politics suffered a terrible blow in Israel at the time, and since the right wing Likud inherited the more aggressive political stance it became the popular choice for constituents, and took power. The peace camp disappeared for a few years, and the slogan continued echoing as Israel pushed Palestinians into the second Intifada in the same year, and opened one of the most violent chapters in the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. According to then

Foreign minister, Shlomo Ben-Ami (2006) "Camp David was not the missed opportunity for the Palestinians, and if I were a Palestinian I would have rejected Camp David, as well." Demonization of Palestinians at the time of Amos's military service was quite heightened, which might have increased Amos's inability to question beyond the frontiers of *hegemonic Zionist discourse* and the militaristic apparatus.

Amos's military service was immersed in the mentality described above, and as he recounts, counted with ill-treatment of Palestinians, dehumanization to the point of considering toddlers as valid targets, all the while sustaining some vestige of an ethical discourse regarding the integrity of the soldier, and how it is difficult to preserve it under such difficult circumstance. To a degree, there has to be a disconnection between discourse and practice, theory and reality. Out of the military experience, Amos talks about the 'gain' of prestige, and how incidents of little consequence become 'battle stories' of bravery and near-death situations.

Yosef also makes remarks regarding the period mentioned of the second Intifada, since it was then that suicide bombings were used the most by Palestinians. Many people he knew died in those attacks, and he interpreted as most Israelis and Jews do, as an anti-Semitic attack by crazy extremists who wish to eliminate Israel. This ended up motivating him even more to serve in the military and defend the country, an expression of victimhood and security/militarism.

The argument over conceptually de-politicizing Zionism and placing it adjacent to Jewish identity is usually in defense of *Zionist hegemonic discourse* that alleges that Zionism is essential to Jews and one cannot be one without the other. Gil's argument is slightly different; since he extricates Zionism from politics in the sense that being in favor or against Zionism does not depend on the political left or right. He argues it is a question of identity, in the sense of whatever is the political bias, one can be subject to *Zionist hegemonic discourse*, and have his/her identity shaped by it. Gil's familial history is part of *Zionist hegemonic discourse* in history textbooks, as his grandfather was one of the Jewish freedom fighters at the foundation of the State, his grandmother survived the Holocaust, his mother served the military and was very Zionist, and his father that to this day occupies

high-command positions in the Israeli police. He sought to improve mentally, physically and emotionally before going to the army, in order to accomplish more in the military service. He now understands the preparation course was an indoctrination. His fascination with the Nazis will appear in a curious way in the next section of this work.

Tamar's past is the most different from all, since she started off in the Jewish orthodox environment in New York, and while moving away from it, decided to live and study in Israel. Her initial view was disconnected from Zionism, and as her parents became Zionist she did as well. Her expectations were based on Zionist discourse when she moved to Israel, which she considered a 'Jewish space'. In Zionist circles in the Diaspora there is an aura of 'mission' around moving to Israel, different than a regular migration. The main difference in Tamar's case from the other interviewees, is that she was not born Zionist, and had had a different experience of being Jewish, which provided her with a different perspective on Zionist worldview.

In this section we looked at how these interviewees have been socialized in Zionist environment. The next section is really the heart of this work. It describes the instances, events and moments where these individuals have perceived the gap between the hegemonic discourse and reality.

6. De-Identification

In this chapter, I intend to explore the content of the interviews to show crucial moments, which sparked and furthered a de-identification of the informants from their Zionist identity. In these moments, they seem to notice a gap between their personal values and their actions as representatives of the state or the collective Zionist identity, in other words, the *hegemonic Zionist discourse*.

6.1 Interviews

Yosef

Yosef's first experience in the OPT was during his first military assignment at age 19, which was to guard the Jewish settlements in the city of Hebron. According to Yosef "going to Hebron was one smack in the face... from my understanding of what is going on there." Hebron is the largest city in the West Bank with a population of 165.000 Palestinians. It is home to the Cave of the Patriarchs in the Jewish tradition, second holiest place in Judaism following the Temple Mount in Jerusalem, and is also known as the Ibrahimi Mosque, or Sanctuary of Abraham in the Muslim tradition, viewed as one of the four holy cities of Islam. Over centuries there have been Jewish presence on and off in the city, but Jews were forbidden from accessing the sacred site for most of the history of the place. After 1929, when a massacre of 67 Jews occurred during the Palestinian riots mostly directed against the British rulers and growing Jewish settlement of the time, the Jewish community left, only to come back in 1968. A group of settlers moved into the region that year, and a decade later into the old Jewish quarter in Hebron, next to the Cave of the Patriarchs. Settler presence in Hebron has been marked by violence towards Palestinian citizens. It reached its

peak with the 1994 Hebron Massacre, when a Jewish American physician named Baruch Goldstein, a religious Jewish settler, entered the Ibrahimi Mosque during prayer time and opened fire murdering 29 Palestinian worshippers. Nowadays there are around 600 Jewish settlers living in Hebron. The city was divided into two regions, H1, containing about 130.000 Palestinians and under control of the Palestinian Authority, and H2, containing the remaining 35.000 Palestinians and around 600 Jewish settlers under Israeli Military control. The declared mission of soldiers posted there is to protect these settlers from Palestinians.

At the time Yosef's identity as an ardent Zionist shared many commonalities with the Jewish settlers, which relate directly to the aspects of Zionism mentioned adopted in this work. He believed Israel should be Jewish, that Israel is the ultimate protection for the Jewish people, that it is under serious menace from the Palestinians and other Arab countries and needed the protection that only the Israeli Defense Forces (IDF) soldiers could provide. Although he grew up in a home where he learned the West Bank and Gaza were not part of Israel, he accepted the rationale that keeping them under occupation was a necessary evil, for security reasons. He understood that settlers were usually religious, and that they took scripture more literally than most secular Jews did, which was the reason the West Bank was so important to them, since it contains so many sites of biblical narrative cornerstones. His understanding was that they were his brethren Israeli religious Jews, and they were following their faith while trying to do no harm. They needed his protection from Palestinians who hated Jews and wanted to see them indiscriminately dead. He knew some Palestinians were 'good', but that there was no way of telling for sure and the risk was not worth lowering the guard.

...then we get our first assignment in Hebron, in a city of 160, 170 thousand Palestinians, and we're there to guard a bunch of settlers, about 6 or 7 hundred, and they're right smack in the middle of this Palestinian city, which was really weird, because there is no border there, and then it turns out that they're the craziest, most fanatic, extreme, radical, violent bunch of Jewish settlers that I had ever seen, or ever experienced. [...] I never knew that anything like that existed. I never knew that people like that existed.

Yosef tells the story of his first moment of confusion. According to him it is the first time he confronted a gap between his expectations and the reality he encountered. He imagined his role as a soldier in Hebron and how he fit into the larger political picture. The soldier is the front line for Zionism, and in its conception, for Israeliness and *Jewishness*. Yosef talks about his first assignment:

I hear this mess, a ruckus coming from the market place, which today is closed, it's a ghost town. But when I was there... the market place was still open, when you could go in and out of the market place, imagine a Middle Eastern market place... there were colors and there were shouts, and there was you know... people would be selling clothes, and cloths and meat and spices, and women and children and everyone, you know, it was packed... it was really crowded.

Yosef is describing the Hebron Shuhada market, which used to be one of the main street markets in the old city of Hebron. It was shut down as a result of settler presence. The Israeli army imposed closure on the entire Shuhada street on security grounds, causing a collapse of local economy since this used to be the commercial center for the entire southern West Bank. The army sealed shops by welding their doors, and shopkeepers could not re-enter their workplace. Inhumane hardship on the street's residents who cannot go in and out of their homes through their doors, and had to make holes in the back walls, or through their ceilings in order to go in and out.

I hear this screaming coming from the market place and yelling and shouting, and I run over to see what is going on, and it turns out that these four large women walked out of the settlement, Jewish women, one of them is holding a rolling pin, one of them is pregnant, one of them has a baby in her arms, and they're walking around the market place, and they're shoving Palestinian shop keepers and smacking them on the head and throwing things off the shelves and making a complete mess, and I'm like... what the hell is going on!?! 'Cause that's the last thing I was expecting to see, 'cause we were there to protect them, obviously, their the innocent ones, it's the Palestinians that were gonna be the terrorists, Palestinians were gonna be the violent ones... and it turned out that... I just watched the scene with these four women just walking around smacking people and shoving things off the shelves and I'm like... But anyway, our assignment was really clear, you know, were there to keep the peace, no matter what, that's... that's our job, no matter who's making what mess, and we know that whatever is going on it has to stop and things need to calm down cause god knows what's gonna happen next. But it's also very clear that we're not allowed to touch the women, our orders are really clear...

Q: why [are you not allowed to touch the women]? That's a limitation you have, right?...

Not allowed to touch the women! especially the Jewish women. Under no circumstance were we ever to touch the women, the only way we could stop them was to actually get in between and block their path to the Palestinian shop keepers, so we start running around chasing each other like a cartoon around the market place, and I find myself between one of these ladies and a Palestinian shop keeper, and she's trying to smack him and I'm right in the middle, and I'm yelling at her, and she's like: "Get the hell out of my way kid, I'm trying to..." And I'm like: "what are you doing lady?!?" And this is this weird scene... That's very very clear to everyone that's playing around... it's that the Palestinian shop keeper knows, full well, that if he's going to try and protect himself or maybe hit back, I'm not going to have any choice but to get up and turn around and either shoot him immediately, or hand cuff him, blind fold him and arrest him. Either one, he can't do anything, and he knows this, I know that, and she knows it. We all three of us know what role we're playing in this little game. Anyway, so we run around the market place a little bit, for like 10, 15 minutes, until it finally ends with a shop keeper with a broken nose on one side of the street, and the pregnant lady fainted on the other side. And me and my buddies look at each other, take a deep breath, and it's all like: "Oh! ... so this is what we've come here to do... this is the story." And it took us actually a very long time to get a grasp on what was going on, 'cause from then on, every Saturday this was the case... Especially with women and children, because when it was the men it would get really violent and sometimes we'd get into fist fights with settlers, and it was the most confusing... confusing situation for... for... for me as an Israeli soldier...

Another situation Yosef describes is of settlers illegally taking over Palestinian shops. The Jewish settlement is built on top of Palestinian homes and shops in the old city center. Settlers would knock down walls from their homes into Palestinian shops, which were empty due to the closure, and simply take over. Yosef explains that "we had no authority to arrest anyone, we're not there to arrest people... obviously we're not police officers, we're not there to... we're actually there to guard them... we're not there for anything else..." He points out the Israeli police had authority over the settlers, but they feared them and usually would require military protection in order to deal with them. Until now, Yosef explains, around sixteen hundred shops have been closed in the old city of Hebron, in the name of six hundred Jewish settlers' security.

they [Jewish settlers] managed eventually to make a hole into the wall, they'd go inside, pull the merchandise out of the shop, lock it from the inside, and put a new settler couple there. That's how the settlement would slowly expand. While we were there, especially during curfew, if there's a curfew that's a month long, there's no way... a Palestinian shopkeeper... he's won't be able to fix the hole in the

wall. And by the time the curfew's over, he goes back to his shop and it's no longer his shop, there's someone living there, and that's it. And there's no authority, there's no court he can go to, there's no police that he can say "someone just stole my shop, even though it's my private property, and [it was] my great-great-grandfather's shop.

During the military experience, Yosef slowly starts to question, but it is still not a turning point for him. He is too well trained in not asking questions and following orders. The context of the military seems to be exhausting and the young age seems to not allow for much self-confidence and autonomy.

I'm too tired, and we're too busy, and there's a very clear assignment and I'm 18 and I'm 19 and I have a commander, and a good soldier - and this is what we do during basic trainings - six months of basic trainings can be a lot about getting into shape, and can be a lot about knowing how to shoot a gun, but the bottom line in basic training is learn how to never ask questions, do what you're told, follow orders. That's what basic training is about. Training you into some sort of machine, and numbing your mind and numbing your questions. So if you're a good soldier - and I wanted to be a good soldier, I've been waiting to be a good soldier - turn the conscience off, or turn the questions off, just do what you're told, and later on deal with what whatever there is to deal with.

Yosef does not believe many people start thinking and questioning during the army, unless they suffer a violent crisis, which usually ends up in the hands of a psychologist, or even worse, a psychiatrist. It was still during the army service that he started to talk to his friends about creating the organization *Breaking the Silence*. Later it became one of the most important organizations advocating for social justice for Palestinians, by exposing grave violations of human rights and international law committed by Israeli Defense Forces (IDF). Soldiers who committed transgressions gave testimonies willingly. The idea emerged from their perception that Israeli public is not aware of what happens in Hebron, or in the rest of the OPT. They do not understand Palestinians are mistreated with grave injustice. Israeli military occupation of Palestine contributes to more hatred and further insecurity instead of promoting security, as is widely held by Israeli Jews and by Jewish Diaspora. Yosef believes there is a lack of *will to know* among Jews

as well. He and his colleagues from *Breaking the silence*¹¹ wanted to tell the public about what is happening, criticizing Israel and Jews, stressing they are speaking from within, groping for acceptance, and not as an external criticism which generally elicits defensive reactions. The most internal place they could find was to speak from the Israeli soldier point of view

Nobody really knew what was going on in the occupied territories. In Tel Aviv, Jerusalem, mainstream Israel doesn't want to know... Still [nowadays] people don't want to know... we wanted people to know what the reality was there, not from a human rights Palestinian point of view, but from a soldier's point of view. This is what was going on for me... We wanted people to understand who these settlers were in Hebron, and what [was] the process, the gradual process of slowly expanding on top of those people's lives...

The avoidance of using discursive tools used by the international community to criticize Israel, such as human rights and international law, is a strategic choice derived from the rejection such concepts have in Israel. Instead of being seen as philosophies of egalitarianism and justice, they are perceived as assault instruments on the Jewish state, and realization of Israeli fears of their situation not being comprehended. *Breaking the Silence* wanted to show the reality of checkpoints that Israelis were also not aware of, and how there is no way of *humanely* occupying another people. There are over 600 checkpoints operated by Israeli military and private contractors in the West Bank, limiting freedom of movement and breaking connections between Palestinian major cities and regions. Many Palestinians have difficulty reaching their work place, schools, family and agricultural land.

the slow moral degradation that any soldier was going to experience at a checkpoint. You know, when you're at a check point, and there's a curfew going on, and your orders are that no one's to go through... and 400 people show up at your check-point over your 8-hour shift and as sweet as you might be... you know, you might grow up in a youth movement, and your parents may be left wing, sweet people that voted for Shulamit Aloni (peace activist and politician), you're gonna stand at a check-point and the first 100 people, you know it, you might make an effort and say "I'm really, really sorry, there's a curfew today, I didn't

¹¹ *Breaking the Silence* is an NGO founded by Israeli ex-soldiers, which collects and publishes testimonials from soldiers recounting brutalities against Palestinians they were ordered to carry out.

make the orders, you're just gonna have to go home" ... But the second... you know, after a hundred people you're gonna be like...

According to Yosef, this degrading treatment Palestinians are submitted to at checkpoints cannot be dehumanizing only on one side. It is dehumanizing to the Palestinians, but it departs from a dehumanization of the soldiers themselves, who were not brought up to treat people in such manner, no matter who these people are.

Yosef describes getting to a phase where he was possessed with anger. He was angry at everyone and everything. He was furious at his mother asking: "why didn't you tell me? Why didn't I know about this growing up?" while his parents did not understand what he meant.

I think a lot of people around the world today are going through a very difficult identity crisis... Jewish Americans, Jews around the world, Israelis that are having to confront the truth here... I think that people are going through a very, very difficult identity crisis... and I think it's hard, I think it's difficult... It was NOT easy for me... it was NOT fun... I left after *Breaking the Silence*... I was very active in *Breaking the Silence*, I wanted people to know... [...] that was waking up... that was... "I need people to realize what's going on, 'cause I need somehow to deal with what's going on, with my confusion", and the only way to do that was to shout out, and it got really big, really fast. So right after the army we went right into morning talk shows and evening news and international reporters, and Japanese reporters were knocking on my mother's door, and it got really big, it went *vroom!* And it got more intense than the army was ever before, and I got *sooo* confused I couldn't remember what the hell I was doing there... what in the world led me... I couldn't remember why I went to the army in the first place, and then after the army being led to breaking the silence, it all seemed like such a world... and I couldn't remember... 'What the hell am I doing? What's going on with life now?'

During this first phase, Yosef was forced to act based on the discrepancies he found between his own values, and what he had to do in the army; Between what he thought he stood for all his life, what he thought were the *real* values of the Israeli State and Zionist spirit, and what he not only witnessed on the ground, but was a consenting actor contributing to it on behalf of the Israeli state, doing away with all these treasured values. *Breaking the silence* was a success, attracting national and international media attention and stirring heated debate.

But although Yosef felt compelled to act, it was a kneejerk reaction to his shocking experience during military service. He did not yet process what that meant on a larger scale. The implications of his initial discovery were much larger than he had initially imagined. He felt overwhelmed with the excessive attention given due to his activism, and could not see clearly the way ahead of him. He was disconnecting from his past, without yet having any connection to hold onto in his future. He decided to leave Israel, and spent the next six years abroad. Yosef's first visit to Israel was only four years into his stay away, and during this time Yosef says, "I did not wanna see anyone. At some point I stopped calling myself Yosef, my new name was Jo... I'm not Israeli, I'm not Jewish, I'm a new person, I don't want to talk about it, leave me alone!" He was rehearsing what it would be like to abandon Zionism more fully, by imagining what it would be like to abandon various central components of his identity – *Jewishness*, Israeliness – since the fault lines between them and Zionism are blurry, and it seems to most people today there cannot be one independently of the other.

It was about me... it was finally just about letting go, it wasn't about holding onto anything. And it was just about... you know... it didn't have anything to do with reality there... it was a story... it wasn't truth. Truth was what was going on around me... the whole context, the whole abstract, the parts of my identity that I'm supposed to cling to just so I can feel... confident about a certain... it slowly... it all fell away... over the years... I mean it took a long time... this is definitely not a weekend seminar... I stayed away for four years... I didn't want to see anyone; I didn't want to talk to anyone... I just wanted to... I... My body just said, you know... go finish what you're... go through this process... I didn't think I was ever... as far as I was concerned I was never gonna come back.

In this other environment, Yosef sensed reality differently. He was able to see how his reality in Israel was not as concrete as it had seemed before, unquestionable. Now it seemed constructed, a story. He saw no need to cling to any label in order to feel confident as a person. He reduced the scope of identity that he needed to define himself, where in Israel he grew having an ample scope which included himself and his collective, with very little clarity as to where are the boundaries between the self and the group. Being Zionist there was to merge into the mass. Any thought that dissented from that would mean to be a traitor.

Now, this scope had reduced to circumscribe only himself, his body, and he could identify who he is without having to rely on a collective for that.

It's not... this isn't a... this isn't a political opinion. It's not an ideology. No, no, no... This is about giving... me a chance to find out who I really am, what I really believe in... not all the stuff that was crammed into my psyche as I was growing up, you know... the three thousand years of responsibility, the Holocaust, the wars of independence, the Jewish Zionist entity and my identity within that... what's my role... and building a new society... and all this other responsibility that... that's all mine, it's all my responsibility and I'm... I'm capable, and I'm the youth movement leader that can lead the new Zionist patriotic new world and country, and all this other crazy stuff that I had never actually had a chance to decide on!!!!... I was told that I was all this stuff... And for me the realization was: "wait a minute! if I release for a second, if I give myself a minute to breathe, and just live, it turns out that I'm a completely different person...

While spending time in India, Yosef met a documentary maker who was looking for someone to help her in Israel/Palestine while shooting a film. He went back to Israel as her guide. While on this job, Yosef went back to Bethlehem in the West Bank for the first time after his military service. Last time he had been there he was wearing his uniform during the second Intifada, the Palestinian popular uprising.

I was scared silly... to go back to the... my instinct was to be scared silly... but my instinct was also to never say no. Like, after traveling around for a while and waking up in the morning and meeting new people and living in different countries and being in different situations - never say no anymore! There's no reason to ever say no. So I went happily, but I felt my instinct as I was trained very well... I was about to pee in my pants... I was really scared to walk around Bethlehem again... I was sure that every single person was out there to get me... that it's going to be a terrorist, and they hate me, and they see through my soul, and they see how afraid I am and... And everywhere we went, people opened their doors, and said sit down, calm down, have a cup of tea... eat... you're fine... and it took me a little while just to calm down...

Yosef's surprise at being well received and treated in the West Bank once he was not in the role of a soldier anymore, shattered his belief, even thus far, that Palestinians essentially hated Israelis, or even Jews. It is very hard to hide this identity in the OPT, since Palestinians have been living amongst or next to Israelis long enough in order to nearly always recognize them based on small details. It is quite safe to assume they knew he was a Jewish Israeli. This side of Palestinians

was out of reach for Yosef while he was wearing uniform. His expectations were to not be forgiven for being Jewish, for being Israeli. The risk of deep blind hatred does exist and should not be dismissed on a romantic whim, since effects of the Israeli military occupation of Palestine run deep, and has traumatized the population. Nevertheless, Palestinians seem to regard Israelis in categories such as soldiers and settlers, which are to be feared and disliked, and there are civilians who in very small numbers roam the Palestinian Occupied Territories and usually are peace-camp activists who defend social justice for Palestinians.

Step by step Yosef's image of Palestinians became more and more humanized, seemingly through small details, which to him were immeasurable shocks

At some point she (the documentary maker) took me to... we were interviewing different organizations around, and we went to the Holy Land trust, where there's a... it's a non-violent communication center... and they train trainer to go to different schools, and to teach farmers to communicate non-violently with one another, and with soldiers that would show up. And that's when I cracked. I was like: 'What?!?! There's a non-violent communication center in Palestine? How come no one ever told me?' That's when I went home and I was like: 'how come you never told me that actually Palestinians are human? How come never no one made that connection for me?' I cracked!!! I went home and I cracked.

Making a connection between concepts of a nonviolent communication center and the quality of being human, and being surprised at its existence in the OPT may suggest a 'clash of civilizations' and Islamophobic mindset, where nonviolence is associated to a Western, Modern, humane, civilized society, and violence with a Muslim, Arab, backwards society. These distorted notions are built into Zionist discourse through sustaining that Arabs/Muslims want to eliminate the Jewish people, as an extension of historical anti-Semitism, which the Jewish people have had always to survive. This discourse connects Israel to the Western world, ignoring its vast non-Western components among the Jewish population which immigrated from various Arabic and Muslim countries. Part of Israel's difficult history relates to internal social struggles of non-European Jews for equality. Israel's elites have always been mostly of European descent, and although Israel's population is balanced between Ashkenazi Jews (European) and Mizrahi Jews (non-European), all Israeli Prime ministers to date have been of

Eastern European descent. Much has been written (Shohat, 1992, & 2008; Pappé, 2006) on the oppression of Arab identity among Arab Jewish immigrants and their descendents, and the pressure to adopt Western identity instead. Arab Jews could not keep the Arab component of their identity since in the new reality of the Jewish State Arabs, which once were the hosts of large Jewish communities were now the enemy.

In a short time span, Israeli Zionism has constructed a perception of eternal animosity with labels such as Arabs, Muslims and Palestinians. Even to this day in Israel it is rare for Israeli Jews to refer to Palestinians as such, while the term Arabs is much more common. The notion that Arabs are irrational religious radical barbarians that hate Jews, simply for being Jews, has also been burned into Israeli minds. This kind of notion generates deep mistrust and can continue to exist unconsciously in the minds of quite progressive Israelis under a form of latent fear but not explicitly in their discourse.

When Yosef became aware that there is a Palestinian nonviolent communication center, all of this construction came crumbling down in his mind and he comes face to face with his own prejudice. He recognizes that this is not a value he considers his own, and that it was instilled in him by Zionist sources, which he had trusted throughout his life to guide his moral interpretation of the world.

Like, any four-year-old is supposed to know this stuff... They did that... they did that... we do that... so well, that you know... Non-violent communication classes??? What??? I was furious!!! I was throwing things all over the place!!! I was like... why??? and I cried on my mothers lap for hours that night...

The guilt for not having known this all along and the surprise of how pervasive was the ideological education he had received, and how either little power he had in deciding his own life, or how incompetent he was for not being able to question it by his own merit before being part of the Zionist enterprise. That day was a turning point for Yosef. Not only he had become aware of the *humanity* of Palestinians he had not yet acknowledged deeply enough until then, but he also came face to face of who he was before.

Still in Bethlehem, Yosef encountered a roadblock where from a military vehicle he saw some Israeli soldiers come down to raid a building and make an arrest. Yosef describes how he became aware of how distant he became from who he once was, but yet has retained understanding for that old version of himself

I'm watching this soldiers and they... they leave the army vehicles to go into a building and I'm watching their faces, and they're scared silly... these soldiers they think that every single person there is a terrorist, every single... they're about to pee in their pants... just like I was... and I'm like: 'Oh my god! I'm watching myself!... that's me!... look at them!... they're me!... they're me!...' They're kids, and they have no idea of what's going on around them, and they're scared... they're scared silly...

Later that day Yosef came back to the same building to meet a friend of his, and found out the soldiers had raided his friend's office. His friend was still shook up hours later, and told the soldiers pointed the gun to his face while shouting, and arrested a random man that was in his office. When Yosef arrived his friend was shivering.

I didn't know what to say... And I was just standing there in front of him... and all I... the only... the only thing I can say is that... you know... I'm s... I'm so sorry... And he just looked at me and said: 'you know what's going on here. Don't you ever forget what's going on here...' He gave me a big hug and we went out to... he took me to his parent house and we all had dinner that evening. That's the night I went home and cracked... I cried and cried on my mother's lap for hours - she didn't know what the hell to do with me. That was a crack... I really cracked... but I was so grateful that that happened...

But the process of de-identification is not without hardship. There is a constant struggle to let go of labels that have had so many beautiful meanings for so long and reflected the beauty of individual identity and its special character of belonging to a special group. As I asked Yosef about his disposition to do away with ideas of Jewish state and Zionist state, and embrace the notion of a pluralist democratic state he said

To be totally honest? To be TOTALLY honest... I feel things bubbling up as you're describing this I can feel like... It's funny how Zionism is one of the first words you learn here in school... and that you're a Zionist, and that's a GOOD thing!... And it's one of the last, hardest things to let go of... I think... maybe for me... I don't know how they managed to do that... I don't know how that's such a... such a... it's

like burnt into my psyche... just saying that word... just knowing that's part of my identity that I belong to something... It's like belonging to this kinda very tight mafia, that's always gonna take care of me, and you don't want to betray it because of you betray it, they'll treat you as a traitor... And what does it say about me?... where is my loyalty values? Where are my familial values? Where are my roots?...

Yosef prefers not to rush into defining a new label for a new identity. Mainly when it comes to a definition that relies on what new form the state should take. He believes the discussion on whether Israel should be Jewish or democratic is a discussion on ideological grounds, while he is more interested in an understanding on identity grounds. According to Yosef

Actually right now, Israel, the Zionist entity, is not a Jewish state. We don't run according to Jewish values. So when it comes to actually a Jewish existence, a Jewish state, a place for Jewish people to come to from all over the world - that doesn't have to change. That's... it may be not Zionism, but it doesn't mean it's not Jewish. Maybe even without Zionism it's more Jewish.

Yosef is capable of seeing clearly the separation between Zionism and Judaism. It is possible that he might have still retained the *Jewishness* aspect of Zionism as part of his identity, feeling there is a connection between the Jewish people and the territory, but he sees it is not an exclusive right. As far as *security/militarism* go, he has understood Israel has been violent against a population of human beings in order to take their land, and has created a narrative to accommodate this agenda and implanted it in the minds of all its constituents, having them, himself included, completely accept, agree, and become agents of the State, believing something noble is being done, while taking part in oppression. This also is part of *Zionist hegemonic discourse*, which Yosef has questioned and has understood the damage it causes. He can also understand he cannot ignore this hegemony while addressing other Jews, since from their point of view he will simply be branded a traitor. Being branded a traitor is not a concern to Yosef only because he will not be able to communicate his ideas and explain his reasons, but as well because he does not want to lose his belonging to this group. He wishes to make changes, but he does not seem to be willing to write off the Zionist collective, possibly because now he understands their worldview is a construction

as well, and their political stance does not derive from an essential character he disagrees with.

Amos

Amos was consistently evaluated as an outstanding soldier, which made him become more integrated in the military structure and see from the inside how “the system itself doesn’t work in effect towards the objectives it declares to”, as he puts it. In this stage, Amos’s criticism was more directed at the inefficiencies and small corruptions in the military structure, which shattered his previous understanding of complete surrender and blind dedication to the country and the army. Slowly, as Amos himself started to climb up the military career ladder he noticed that it was not just on the lower command levels that there were ulterior motivations behind the nationalist facade, such as laziness and a wish to go home, but in higher command levels he encountered career oriented decision-making, focusing on advancement rather than on the national interests. Amos’s critical views led him to refuse an order at a certain point, which would put in risk the soldiers under his command, only for the sake of training. He noticed how the demand to exceed secure parameters came from the wish of his commanders to perform in face of the expectations they were dealt by their commanders. That cost Amos his command.

Almost towards the end of his service, already taking part constantly in military operations in the OPT, Amos took a lift with someone who lived in the West Bank, probably a settler. The person started thanking him for the protection they are providing and congratulations on a job well done. Amos started shouting at the person:

‘We are killing people with no reason, and we’re destroying homes with no reason... What do you know about what is going on there? No one is guarding you!... We’re not guarding anyone! We’re guarding ourselves! And we’re going in there to destroy Palestinians’ lives...’ While I was shouting at him I was all dirty and carrying my weapon because I just came back from an operation I had taken part in, and I was still determined to go back and take part in the next operation...

During this phase Amos was shouting very much at home, getting angry at everything, with his mother. He read a book by Herman Hess called *Narcissus and Goldmund*. In the book a character kills someone who tries to rob him. The character describes the feeling as having a ring around the heart that tightens when you kill someone. Amos felt a connection to this description:

I also killed people out of self-defense, or national defense... Do I have a ring on my heart? No... It started bothering me that didn't bother me... It is relatively easy to kill someone and continue on living as nothing happened... It slowly seeped into deeper thoughts. I think it mixed with the anger of that phase, and I stopped fearing death or injury, and I felt the need to feel something by more extreme means.

For a period Amos experienced emotional extremes, which ended up bringing him to reflect on the Holocaust. His direct family did not go through the Holocaust, but his grandparents' family who stayed in Europe was all murdered.

The Holocaust was always the ultimate test of good and evil. The Holocaust is actually the reason for which I go to war, put on uniform, go fight on a jeep, and the Holocaust is also the test if I am already like them or not. It is also the thing that makes you into the good side, and also the bad. As long as you are less evil than the Nazis, then you are within the limits of what is OK... Because you had the worst enemy in the world, and you possess the world's greatest victimhood, then you are the biggest victim and your defense is pre-approved, as long as you do not reach the level of the Nazis.

Amos has also been to Poland on the government-organized trip to the concentration camps. As things progressed and Amos questioned more and more the limits of what is right and what is wrong, using all kinds of relativistic rationale in order to relieve himself of the burden or responsibility for what is happening, thinking there is no truth but for the truth that each one holds. Toward the last phase of the military service when he was questioning the most and being the most rebellious, breaking the patterns of right and wrong, he started thinking of all the Palestinian kids whose fathers Amos had taken to prison, "I thought that they couldn't understand that I am not like the Nazis, that the Nazis were worse... what do they know about the Nazis?" This kind of thought did not come lightly to Amos. He was playing with the limits of what is conceivable to someone raised

under the *hegemonic Zionist discourse*, shaped into what I called here the 'standard Zionist education', whatever line of it that may be.

Amos recounts a moment where he watched a film in which a female character kills many people in order to save herself, and he reacts in a critical way thinking what is there left to live for after you have killed so many people for money of other shallow reasons. Then it dawns on him he has killed people as well, and he reflects about what right he has to think like that.

Then I started an internal conversation... How can I narrate a story about myself in a way that I feel good about it. Midway anger rose in me and I wanted to prove to myself suddenly that I am the evil one. I wanted suddenly to prove to myself that I am in fact the Nazi; that I am the worst thing that exists. Mainly because I wanted to cry... I had wanted to cry for many years and I couldn't. [...] I pushed myself to the edge, maybe in order to atone for something, for having killed people... In a logical-political way I imagined the situation where I come to a village, children look at me, I take their father, I blow up their home, they see uniforms, they don't see a face... Maybe a family member had been killed once by an IDF soldier, maybe they have images in their minds of IDF soldiers coming into their homes with strong knocks on the door and explosions, exactly as I have from films images of the Nazis that enter in the middle of the night and throw everyone outside [the house]. There you have it, I also came and kicked many people out [of their houses]. OK, but they took them to a ghetto... Well, I took them to a detention camp, which they did not leave. But there, they almost did not give them food... Then I thought, do I know what they gave them to eat here? I don't know... And I think, does it really matter to this child if he is taken to a place with or without food? What does he know? He knows that he was taken by the worst people in the world...

And slowly, as a mental exercise, step-by-step Amos developed the story in his mind, where he was a Nazi soldier. He imagined that there were Nazi soldiers that did not kill Jews every day; there were soldiers that were simply soldiers. There were also S.S. Soldiers that did not kill Jews, and only performed transportation functions, or arrest functions in order to protect their own troops, exactly as Amos did.

Suddenly I reached the point where I could say I can be the worst evil in world. Not just the worst evil in the world but the devil himself. I finally broke and started to cry... I cried for hours... From then on I started to look at myself differently in a more active way.

He pushed himself to the edge, and across that line that separates all acceptable evil from the unacceptable, Nazi evil. He was not a Nazi himself, but as his own Zionist, Jewish Israeli self he saw he shared the same evil that Nazis also did, not because he had done things as bad as they did, but because the potential for such evil to his dismay and surprise, was in him, but not in a particular way, rather, as it is in any human being. The lines separating evil from absolute evil disintegrated away and all that was left was the awareness that these notions of good and evil depended solely on principles and choices.

Amos does not feel he went through a process where he changed his values; rather it was a process where what changed was his understanding of the circumstances. It is also a change in understanding of how his psychology works and how the environmental psychology works, and how people are capable of believing deeply in their own story, and the *need* people have of believing in *some* story, hence the importance of the narrative subject. Amos speaks mainly of his understanding he went through indoctrination, as most Jews have, and that this indoctrination was not the most evil in the world and was understandable under the circumstances. It is something Amos feels he needs to break in order to build something new. He describes his process in terms of how it defines him:

It's a process of breaking frames that are taken for granted as a sure thing, in order to deal with what I did maybe, or in order to grow, [...] sometimes I see it as a process of atonement... I have seen it as a choice between being crazy and take responsibility off me, or take it on me to think of what I've done and why I did it. To build myself my values anew, build evil and good anew. In fact, from that moment on, I couldn't believe anything anymore. I didn't believe my parents, my environment, myself. I saw I have in me many suppressed things I don't bring up or don't remember. Dark places I don't know where I have been and what I did. Everything was a lie; everything was bad. I knew I needed to build the good again. [...] It was a total breakdown of all good and evil, because If my parents had told me all those things and sent me to this place that now I think is terrible in retrospect, and they are my good and evil, then everything broke down and I need to start anew, and I didn't have anything to hold on to... No god, no nothing... The only thing I could build my new references of good and evil were things I had already inside me. I thought of rationalizing it in terms of what happens to values if you take them to their extreme... for example take 'loyalty', and you see yourself down the line being an S.S. soldier, or 'love thy other', and you see yourself in the extreme as a hippie, dancing naked and hugging people... And I tried to choose how to organize my value universe and my life.

As it appears in most of the interviews, de-identification is deeply connected to revisiting Zionist construction of the Holocaust. Amos gained insight into what kind of mindset regarding the Holocaust is developed in Zionist socialization and identity as he held various discussions with Jews on the subject during his personal process of change. He had a privileged position to do that since he became a guide at Yad Vashem, the Holocaust Museum in Jerusalem. At first Amos had very strong interest and identification with the Holocaust, as many people develop due to Zionist education.

I grew up all my life with the Holocaust in my thoughts, in films, Remembrance Day ceremonies. The trip to Poland [visit to the extermination camps] was a highlight of sorts, and later I worked at Yad Vashem [Jerusalem Holocaust Museum] as a guide. Holocaust was very emotional for me from every angle. I would madly watch films on it, and really... any fragment of memory... and it is simply an issue of identity. The Holocaust becomes a major component almost in the identity.

It is one of the strongest rationales for requiring a strong defense and security system, and for never trusting that danger is no longer there, keeping the idea of anti-Semitism alive in hearts and minds of Jews everywhere. As he stepped away from many Zionist precepts, he started to put the Holocaust under a different perspective. This new perspective does not diminish what has happened in WWII, but shows how it has been and still is manipulated politically in Zionist rationale.

Amos recounts a conversation he had regarding moral superiority:

Something I hear a lot about when I talk to people [about the conflict], is regarding moral superiority. In a conversation with a friend I asked: "are you saying that we are morally superior, and thus, it is ok that we killed 800 kids in Gaza two years ago?" [During operation Cast Lead]. He replied: "yes, because they kill us..." and so on and so forth. So we have a moral superiority that allows us to kill children as well. I asked: "What is this moral superiority based on? At what number of children you kill per day do you lose your moral superiority?", and he said: "It doesn't matter at all. We will always be morally superior because we are Jewish." And he is not a religious person at all, and considers himself a leftist... At first the conversation was very rational, but after some anger on my side and his, and heated debate, he refined his definition of moral superiority, which does not depend on how many children you kill, not in how much you think straight, not in how much you are miserable, but solely on the fact that you are Jewish. [...] I said: "So there is some kind of genetic code, a race if you will...", and he said: "not race!"

No way!...", I said: "OK, then. Not Jewish race... Jewish people, but with a genetic base, since you are not religious and have no other connection to it, that makes you moral, no matter how much you kill. Equally we can put people in gas chambers and we will remain morally superior. And because he was so angry, he said: "Yes! That too!"

Amos reached the conclusion that original thoughts among many people is very similar to the original Nazi thought, and rather than make him resent Israelis more, it made him understand that it might simply be a lamentable yet inevitable human trait.

The discussion over the Holocaust is not a political debate, regarding whether Jews nowadays are similar to the Nazis of the old days, because it is a slightly dumb debate. It is possible to reflect on what is good and what is evil in ourselves, but in fact, it is a discussion over identity. If people know that you are dabbling with it because the Holocaust is your identity, and now you are in an identity crisis, therefore you are talking about the Holocaust as a tool in order to understand who I was back then, and where I am sensing I am going now. It should be clear to people you are not saying Jews are like Nazis, rather you are using the Holocaust experience in order to understand where you are headed, where is your understanding headed, where is your new identity taking you... I use it only when I talk to someone about identity, here and there in order to pester people... I will not call a soldier 'Nazi'... it doesn't help me... But I think it is helpful when someone mentions an argument such as: "we need our living space", or "all the Arabs will always want to kill us no matter what", so then I am happy to connect it to Nazi sentences and propaganda, just for laughs...

During his work experience at Yad Vashem, Amos had a lot of experience in showing parallels between the Holocaust and real world examples, such as America and Iran, among which there were also examples from Zionist history. Amos was fired for that. Examples included cases such as the Jewish refugees that escaped Germany and tried to enter other countries looking for shelter and were refused. Governments such as the British explained their decision to their populations saying they couldn't guarantee there were no Nazis amongst the German Jewish refugees, which might present a risk of an attack from the inside. Similar case happened recently when Israel refused refuge for the Sudanese refugees that came looking for shelter from their own holocaust. Israel put them in jail or deported them to Egypt, based on a rationale they could be Muslim terrorists and there might be Al-Qaeda cells that are wondering around Sudan,

which could end up entering Israel in such a manner. Israel has many refugees that have no citizenship, no legal status, which Israel puts in Jail.

And if I as an Israeli citizen want to know why, then the answer is exactly the same as the one given to the British citizen in 1938. And this is before there was the Holocaust. It's a quite comfortable and easy comparison. They were not killing Jews, they were just persecuting them, and this is how the world behaved, and we do the same with people that come from a holocaust of their own. It is important to see how it was so difficult for the German society to stop what was going on, how it was an integral part of it, and how it is difficult for us to see things...

Around the period of operation Cast Lead in Gaza in 2008/2009, during which 1400 Palestinians were killed, half of which were civilian non-combatants and around 400 were children, Amos was guiding groups at *Yad Vashem*. He used to attempt to respect the limits of his listeners to a certain extent and at the same time challenge these same limits, in order to maintain an openness and receptiveness of his listeners while promoting change in their perception. He would ask soldiers if they would sometimes receive illegal orders, or if they remember how difficult it is to kill in the beginning, but later it becomes easier. He would try to recreate situations similar to those lived by the soldiers showing them how being surrounded by war makes it easy to dispense with moral concerns by which they would normally abide. Some of the soldiers attending the *Yad Vashem* Museum tour that Amos was guiding had just arrived from the Gaza Cast Lead operation, and were about to be sent back to the "massacre", as Amos calls it.

Amos's process of questioning started off as mere disappointment at the idealized image he had of the military institution that represents so much of the mythical dimension of the fight for survival of the millenary Jewish people. He notices common mundane behavior and problems that showed him there was nothing special or noble in the military. It was just another career. His reflections on having killed people made him question the references he had for good and evil, which are heavily influenced by the Holocaust in Zionist socialization. As he experimented in his mind with his own identity and found that evil is not 'owned' by the Nazis, as well as 'victimhood' is not 'owned' by Jews, he found that although there are great differences between Jews and Nazis, mere resemblance of

patterns of thought between them should be an alert and an instrument to counter *Zionist hegemonic discourse*.

Tamar

Tamar tells about many situations that shocked her, and made her reflect on how Palestinians saw Jews and Israelis. Holding progressive Zionist views, she believed peace should be a priority, but that it could not come at the expense of putting Israel in danger, since *Zionist hegemonic discourse* and *security/militarism* rationale do not allow to see Jews as other than victims and Palestinians as other than aggressors. It is interesting how a small event in daily life can be shocking enough, provided the individual is noticing these details, if it makes the *Zionist hegemonic discourse* and opposing reality collide. She recounts one:

I went to study Hebrew [...] and there were some Palestinians in the class. I was talking to them one day during the break and they asked me if I was Christian, and I said: 'No, no... I'm Jewish. Why?', and they didn't believe me, and I said: 'why won't you believe me? I'm studying Hebrew in Israel, of course I'm Jewish.' And they're like: 'You're just so nice...you are like... speaking to us nicely...' And it was one of those moments I just realized...

In her mind, it was not possible Jews had such an arrogant, discriminatory and aggressive image in the minds of Palestinian Israelis. It was evident from their comment they had never been treated humanely by any Jew before. Tamar had come from the USA, and possibly cultural diversity there had her much more used to talking to anyone regardless of national affiliation. *Zionist hegemonic discourse* imagery of the 'civilized good Jew' who is the eternal victim, always righteous, and never the aggressor had collided with what the Zionist regime had produced in those Palestinians she had met, which was an automatic expectation of hostility and discrimination from Jews. This is one example Tamar chose to share out of many seemingly small daily-life situations that added up and de-stabilized her acceptance of the *hegemonic Zionist discourse*.

Tamar though she would like to interact more with Palestinians on a leveled playing field, and engage in serious conversation about the political reality. She tried to find a space where Israelis and Palestinians spent time

together, or a dialogue project of some sort since Jerusalem is a divided city and Tamar thought it was bound to have one. She was surprised at how difficult it was to find such a place, considering the political reality of the region. It showed her how little this kind of interaction occurred. After a lengthy and complicated research she finally found a place in Tel Aviv.

I started to find out more and more about it. It was just a learning curve. I also went through a process, I mean, where first you're in disbelief and you have all these theories that correct it, and you think if you go and explain to the soldiers in Bil'in [leading Palestinian village in non-violent resistance to the occupation] that they're mistaken then they'll go home... [...] Then I really started to figure out what's going on [...] and I went through a period where I was just seething [...] suddenly, something shifts... like a screen that shifts and you can see... It's painful, shocking, and you're filled with anger... a sense of having been deceived and manipulated. I took it very emotionally.

Her approach was not yet taking into account how difficult it is to challenge a hegemonic discourse, where its subjects are dominated by their own acceptance and consent. As Tamar figured out more what is going on she became angrier and more radical. She joined the Israeli committee Against House Demolitions (ICAHD) and worked as a political tour guide in Jerusalem. During this period Tamar says her understanding moved from being emotionally-centered to a more reason-centered guided by cold hard facts and strategy, decision-making and legal issues. After some time, Tamar felt she was being changed by the situation more than she was able to change it, and decided to step away.

Tamar was also astounded by the way a large section of secular Jewish Israelis regard religious Jewish Israelis. Use of demeaning terms such as 'parasites' and 'cockroaches' is made in mainstream media and everyday conversation in reference to the orthodox religious Jewish Israelis, usually because a large number of them live off government allowance. Additionally, there is widely held perception that it is the religious that are the major problem on the Jewish side in the conflict with the Palestinians because of cases such as the one in Hebron and other religious settlements. Tamar regards it as hypocrisy of the secular Jewish section of society, and does not identify with secular Jews anymore, she says:

Going to Israel I felt I never identified less with secular Judaism, and until today I would never call myself a secular Jew. Ever. I am not religious, but I am not secular either in the sense that to be *hiloni* [Hebrew, for secular], it is a culture in itself, and it is a religion in itself. It's not mine.

Tamar regrets the fact she calls “the tragedy of Zionism”, referring to the many Jewish communities there used to be in many different countries, where they interacted with the society they were part of in a myriad different manners, and had rich cultures there, which Zionism has completely discredited, and forced them into this ‘Ashkenazified’ (from Ashkenazi Judaism, meaning German or European Judaism) melting-pot.

Tamar recounts many instances that made her uncomfortable in Israel as she noticed how skewed was the general perspective people had of the situation with the Palestinians. She mentions things such as the lack of concern shown by her neighbor when she commented how worried she was about an invasion in Gaza in 2006, to which he answered “you will get used to it”, or driving through various places where soldiers look into the cars looking at people’s faces suspiciously, and other things that are ‘normal’ for Israelis, but to her they kept stressing how pathologic the situation is. Even in ordinary day-to-day conversation Tamar would be shocked with things people would say regarding how they thought of Palestinians.

According to the definition of Zionism in this work, Tamar has rejected the three aspects defining it. In her rejection of ‘Jewish secularist’ culture, *Hiloniut*, she is rejecting *Jewishness*, the supposition of an essential relation of modern Jews who do not practice religion to the ancient territory where Israel is now located. This refreshing perspective can only come from someone who had had a different perspective, one of orthodoxy, as Tamar had. Her critical look at Jewish secularism breaks the bi-polar notion of religious/secular as the two options usually available to Jews. She does not see herself as part of either one. As Ghazi-Bouillon (2009, p.43) points out, David Ben-Gurion was responsible for creating a ‘civic-religion’ for the new State, which was based on religious symbols, but secular in its essence. She also rejects the Zionist character of security/militarism, not only when she perceives that aggression is mostly committed by Israel towards Palestinians, but when she notices the desensitization of people to violence due to militarism, and

an acceptance of the surrender of rights to privacy and freedom of movement for the sake of 'security'. She rejects as well *Zionist hegemonic discourse* when she touches on the aspect of the reduction of the richness of Judaic cultures, as they existed in the Diaspora, to a Zionist *Ashkenazi* culture, which she calls the 'tragedy of Zionism'. Ghazi-Bouillon (2009, p.45) also points out how David Ben-Gurion considered Jews in the new State of Israel should have the culture they had in the Diaspora (meaning European Diaspora) and that they (him and his leadership) did not want Jews to become Arabs and corrupted by the culture of the Levant.

Gil

Gil describes what was the first "crack" in his Zionist worldview. During the military service phase, training was very intense. Free time had high value for Gil and his friends. As they were instructed in the *Mechina* (Hebrew for prep-course), they tried to combine the combat training with some reflection on religion and philosophy. Gil describes how he and some friends used some of their scarce free time on the military base for reading *Thus Spoke Zarathustra*, by Nietzsche.

An officer sees us on the roadside and approached us [while we were reading the book together]. He confiscated our book and started shouting: "We don't read non-Jewish books here!" It's a brainwash. Everyone pretty much accepts it and goes to their tents. Me and a friend, who incidentally is very right wing nationalist nowadays, stay on and talk about how it feels strange: "is it possible they are trying to erase our identity?"

Basic training is very hard, and Gil and his friends do not think about these issues too much. He finishes his training with honors, his parents are proud in his graduation ceremony, and he goes out to his first mission in Hebron, same city Yosef served in. Gil spent a year in Hebron on and off, taking part in the Lebanon War in the middle, in 2006.

Gil comments about his mother's posture towards the political situation. At a certain point, his parents moved out of Jerusalem to Tzur Hadassa, which while being inside the Green Line (Israel proper), access to it often is through roads that enter the OPT and thus go through military checkpoints. When they would drive through these checkpoints, Gil's mother would get out of the car and bring coffee

to the soldiers posted there, because they are sweet, and they have a hard time and do a good job, but also after that there are other people there too, some of them blindfolded and tied up, so she would bring them coffee as well. Gil considers her posture to be “non-political, she was humanist.”

During his time in Hebron, Gil’s mother was dying of cancer, and his conversations with her during his visits home were what “kept his sane side, where he talked about what he saw in his service.” Gil says that during his time in Hebron:

I had an image in my mind of Gil, and who I am, the neo-Zionist that came to show the Palestinians that it is possible to do it differently, that he is a moral fighter, that he came to change the situation in the OPT, that he will protect security but will tell them ‘sabah el hir’ [good morning in Arabic), and ‘thank you’ and ‘sorry’. And slowly I begin to understand that the Gil that I have in my mind, and Gil that exists in reality and does what he does... there is no connection between them anymore.

Gil’s grandmother never talked much about the Holocaust itself, but about how it all started. She would tell that her father, which was very respected man, one day came home and said the bank would not give him a loan, because he was Jewish. That is how her story always started, and it developed on to a phase where one day they were not allowed to leave home. Her friends from school were playing in the street, and she came out to them to play. Two soldiers came and took her back home by force, since it was prohibited for her, a Jew, to leave home, due to a newly installed closure policy. To this day, Gil says, she does not cry when she talks about the concentration camp, but she does cry when talking about this moment. Gil continues without pause and talks about his first mission as a soldier in Hebron. He tells about a special Jewish festivity, which brought to Hebron, on top of its 800 Jewish settler population, another 10.000 religious Jews, amidst the 35.000 Palestinian residents in area H2, which is the part of Hebron under Israeli military control. In order to keep the peace, the army imposes a curfew on the Palestinian population. He starts to remember things: “It’s *a little* like my grandmother told me. It’s *totally* different, *totally* different... But *a little* like my grandmother told me.” The curfew is a prohibition of leaving home. No one

can be on the street. Once a week, there is a 'humanitarian day', Gil explains, where people can go out quickly for a few hours and get groceries.

You see people like your grandfather, even older than your grandfather... You wouldn't even let your grandfather bother himself to get a glass of water... and they are carrying a gas drum on their back. Women with sacks of food and rice and flour and oil, on their head. Little children with water jugs. It's amazing. What is happening there right now, while we are talking, is unimaginable here, in West Jerusalem, in 2010. People on the street here don't have any idea. They will say that maybe that happened decades ago...

Gil shows his perception of the human dimension of the Palestinians he was ordered to impose a curfew on in his first week of duty. It is not clear whether this is his current ability of seeing that or whether he was able to see that at the time. "Still, things hadn't quite settled down for me. I spent seven months that disassembled my identity, and assembled a Zionist identity, in which for the Jewish people to survive, this [the occupation] is what we have to do."

The boy

Gil's mission is to take shifts doing patrol around the Palestinian residential area making sure no one comes out of their homes. Gil and his crew spot a young Palestinian walking around wearing a large coat. In those circumstances there is very little chance of not thinking the worse. They run towards the youngster, and reach him. They see he is just a boy, about ten years old, and it does not look like he has explosives hidden under his coat. Gil starts shouting at him if he is aware he is violating a curfew, and the boy stutters back,

But then I remember who I am. I am of course Gil, the neo-Zionist, the humanist, and I was in a prep-course and in a Service Year Program, and I love children! Just five minutes ago I worked with a kid that age!... So I tell him "walad, ruh el beit, dir balac" [Arabic for: kid go home, be careful], and he goes. My friends say, "You shouldn't have let him go like this. We were supposed to arrest him. Those are the orders." But I tell myself "See how things are? I have already changed things!" After half an hour we are patrolling the streets, and we see him again. And we run towards him and scream at him, and again I say "no!", I was so in love with the fact that I can do things differently and I tell myself "you are the moral guy" and I tell him: "last time! *Dir balac!*", and I let him go home, and he goes home. After two hours patrolling, we see the kid again 200 meters away at a home doorstep, and there's a man in front of him, and he gives him money, his coat is open and he

takes something from the coat. And we completely lost it! This son of a bitch not only breaks the curfew, he doesn't give a shit about us, and it seems he is selling weapons or something like that. We run towards him, catch him, throw him to the ground, his head hits the curb he is bleeding, we turn him around and we are mad. My friend ties his hands behind his back tight, which stops his blood circulation, and I blindfold him. We arrest him and leave him at and leave him at the base.

It is a common punishment, to leave someone tied up and blindfolded for a while at the base, thrown on a side road, even if this someone happens to be a ten-year-old. Gil continues his shift, and goes back to rest. There are only 6 hours to sleep, shower, eat, call the family and girlfriend, and leave for another shift. When Gil comes back from the second shift the boy is still there. Gil realizes the boy had been there for 16 hours, and he looks immobile, almost dead, thrown on the side road. Gil wakes his commander to ask if he can release the boy, and the commander gets angry and punishes Gil, taking away his free weekend. Next day he wakes up for training, and he sees the boy there, already almost 24 hours in the same state. According to Gil, this happens all the time, and according to him by Israeli police rules, it is illegal. During the training, which focused on what happened, when soldiers would wake the commander up unnecessarily, Gil decides he has nothing to loose and asks about the boy. The commander asks "what boy?" and everybody laughs. "The boy that we arrested yesterday. -You arrested a boy yesterday? Then leave him there to sit a little. - But he has been sitting there for over 24 hours. - Oh, really? Ok, then go release him."

This is when Gil finds out that there is no plan in arresting the boy. There will be no investigation. This was the punishment. On his way to release the boy Gil is completely shaking, and he tries to understand how can he apologize to him, and he feels terrible.

I arrive there and I lift him. He stinks from sweat and urine. I take his blindfold off, he looks at me and he is completely terrified, and I really understand that he can't be over the age of ten. And I want to cut open his plastic handcuffs with my pocketknife. The boy is shivering and he is scared and he tries to escape from me, and I don't know how to explain to him I want to release him, but he doesn't let me he is afraid to death. So I say OK, I'll release him like this and someone will cut those handcuffs at home. I take him and say you can go [with gestures]. He looks at me and walks a few steps back, turns around and runs for his life. After a hundred meters he trips and falls on his face with his hands still tied behind his back, and he lifts himself up and continues to run, and I didn't see him again.

After two days, Gil goes back with his team to the house outside which they caught the boy. The family becomes very upset thinking they are there to arrest a family member. The soldiers calm them down and ask about the boy. Gil wanted to feel better about himself, and thought that if he finds out the kid was doing some kind of terrorist work, he would be justified. What Gil finds out is that the boy is a brilliant businessman. He knows during curfew no one has access to supplies, so he stocks some at home and runs delivery door to door during curfews.

This whole story started because of Gil's grandmother. Because of his definition of 'Zionist'

In Auschwitz I understood how Zionist I am. Grandma used to tell stories about the ghetto in Budapest. She was the slimmest girl in the ghetto, so she could pass through the fence. Everyone would give her money and she would bring back food to the ghetto. And this was her heroism story that she would walk around during curfew, when it was prohibited, and this story would cause me to feel such pride in her, and courage. And for the first time, ever, I understood that maybe, it is possible to start to compare... This kid I arrested... And I don't make a full comparison, because if my grandmother would be caught [by the Nazis], they would have killed her, and I would not kill him. But a *beginning* of a comparison *must* take place... For the first time, this 'game' they play in us here with the Holocaust... it backfired, it turned around. First time I understood that BECAUSE of the Holocaust, we ought to STOP doing what we do, and not because of the Holocaust we do what we do. And that's how my thoughts started to crack...

Gil's process of becoming aware of the gap between his imagined identity and real identity continued when a friend of his died in the Lebanon war of 2006 a few hundred meters from him in "an operation that lacked any logic, that was completely dumb, and we knew about it, and we were told this, some strategic victory after an agreement on a cease-fire had been reached." The process continued on when Gil demolished a home in south Hebron Hills and did not know why he was doing it, and his general feeling started to be that everyone is lying to him,

my commanders are of course lying to me, my instructors from the prep-course are lying to me... but it developed because I understood that my parents are lying to me, and my brother is lying to me, and my teachers at school are lying to me, everyone is lying to me... Now, maybe they are being lied to as well, but they are lying to me.

While going through this crisis, Gil's mother died of cancer. Gil believes he lived a crisis that many soldiers will not be able to live, because they will not have this element that will ultimately break them. After a week in *Shiv'a*, Jewish seven-day official mourning time, Gil was forced to go back to his service although he wanted to stay at home. From that moment on, he was a "zombie", disconnected from his actions, executing all orders without questioning, no matter how inhumane they were.

They told me to shoot, I would shoot. They told me to batter, I would batter. They told me to shut down the Shuhada street, I did it even though people were telling me they would not be able to go in and out of their homes anymore, I would threaten to beat them. I became a machine.

During this process of having become a machine, Gil was called to the next phase of his service program called mission year, where he and his colleagues from the unit were united with the girls from their *Gar'in*, to go back to work in education, this time in uniform. "This is the most Zionist act I can imagine: To be a fighter, and afterwards to go work in education in uniform. The army gives to the country, the country gives to the army." Gil and his colleagues are put into schools to teach adolescents. He found himself substituting a teacher in seventh grade, where students are typically 13 years old

At this age we would freely arrest kids in Hebron, I mean... we would do with them whatever we wanted... I get there and the kids are excited, it's their first day in junior high and they don't stop speaking. I get angry and I tell some kid "get out of my classroom. Leave!" And he looks at me like that... And I don't make the connection that I am in a place... I am with Jewish children in a Jewish city... I can't do it. Because I am still on 'automatic mode', I am the machine... The kid tells me: "why should I get out? It wasn't I who was speaking... It wasn't me! It wasn't me!... I get angry: "How dare he answer me?" So I grab him by his shirt, I drag him on the floor, all the children are screaming, I open the door and throw him out... And I say: "anyone else? Who's next? Who else wants it?"

Five minutes later the school principle came in and called Gil out for a conversation. In the conversation with the principle, she confronted him and said the student told her he was treated with violence. Gil argued "He spoke during class!!!" to which the principle replied "so what!?" Gil started crying, in front of

the principle, a social worker and the battered student. Gil was not able to cry when his mother died, and now something broke him. This goes on for a long time, and Gil is not even able to speak. At the end of the day the principle told him he could not come back. Gil never worked in that school again. Going back to the commune, where all the members of the Gar'in lived together during mission year, he tells the story to his friends. Some of his friends are in shock, but a few of them are not. They are surprised there was a problem with Gil's attitude. Together they start to understand the transition that is done with them, as if there was an easy and elegant way to do it.

The harm we suffered will not disappear like that, once we cross into the Green Line. If you ask me nowadays, this is Zionism. It's a violent machine that has innumerable justifications, historical, moral... People in it are completely blind, very violent and destructive, even within ourselves. Even if you take Palestinians out of the equation, how can we be angry at a violent society? How? I mean, the most dominant thing in our society is the army, militarism. There can be no prime minister that has not been a general.

What Gil is talking about is that violence towards others becomes violence towards oneself. The kind of psychological hardships an individual goes through may in extreme cases bring to suicide. Certain levels of suicide in the military are considered normal when they correspond to the normal rate in the wider society. Levels of suicide within military population in Israel has much higher suicide rates than the correspondent population of the same age which is not in the military. Rela Mazali (2008) points out psychological suffering leading to suicide has risen in the IDF, and in recent year has become the number one cause of death in the military. These are the official numbers, but there is no way of knowing how many suicides actually occur in the IDF since it is widely known that this information is frequently hidden even from family members, in order to not implicate the IDF. Gil tells about a case like that

I had a soldier that committed suicide in basic training, and his parents were not told. My commander, I know for a fact that in a conversation with the parents of the dead soldier told them their son was killed in a training accident, that he was very brave and tied to save friends of his that were almost injured, and he jumped ahead of them and saved them, and that's how he died. On his grave it is written, "killed in fulfillment of his duty, while defending his homeland", and they lied to

his parents. I know that afterwards during the Shiv'a someone told them. His mother asked me if that was right, and I stuttered... I was afraid to tell them the truth because I didn't know what they wanted to hear, because at the time I believed this 'machine' [the army, the Zionist enterprise] does things properly...

Gil considers the most dangerous and influential aspect of Zionist preparations for young male adolescents in school, which are the target demographic for finding future combat soldiers for the IDF, is the structure of female soldier instructors. He says the kind of inspiration they bestow upon the young impressionable kids is one of the main drives for choosing combat careers in the military. Gil remembers the images that were built for him and his friends of heroism and success, social acceptance and the male fantasy of being desired by women, and what actually is found in the military experience. The manipulative way of drawing in young students until it is too late.

All these details and cracks in what used to be Gil's understanding of reality add up and

I understand that the reality that I know - is fake. And that is scary. I think many people find themselves in this crossroads. Then you have two choices: To jump, because when you find one thing that is not true, your instinct is to look for more. So to jump, or to shake your head and continue walking. I truly believe most people find themselves in this situation. They shake their heads and continue walking. They say "I will just finish the army, travel to Brazil to the Carnival, I will smoke a lot of drugs, I will come back... I have to start university... now I have already did twice or three times *miluim* [mandatory one-month-a-yearly military reserve service], but it's only for a month, it's not... and I love the country, an on independence day I will have a barbecue, and there s no partner for peace, everybody wants to kill us"...

Gil believes he has less merit than other people who went through this transition. He believes he was forced through it due to his mother's death. He felt he had nothing to loose. His brother left the country, his relationship with his father faded away, he felt lost and disappointed in himself.

I had nothing better to do than to jump, and start looking for more. [...] Something suddenly fell apart, the whole world seemed to be fake, and everything that was sold to me as truth, has been revealed as lies. As you slowly go through phases. When I left the army I thought: 'It's not possible that I won't serve my yearly reserve service... It just can't be... I mean, I suffered, I had nervous breakdowns, I think what is being done is terrible! There can't be anymore... The occupation is

something terrible! The army is something terrible! But I can't not go back, and be with my friends...' You deconstruct more truths and more truths, and I think that one of the last truths is that Israel, nowadays as a state, has almost no right to exist... almost... but if an attempt is done to save here something in the last moment. And the last thing I still play with, to this day, is the definition of my identity. Am I Zionist?... I am not Zionist! I am the latest version of a Zionist, the way I want to design it in the most personal way?... But it's a little... you kind of full yourself with that... So I am anti-Zionist? Post-Zionist? All these definitions... I don't know whom you talked to until now, I think no one can give you an answer because there still isn't any definition... There has not yet emerged something real that defines anew this period and the people that we are.

Visiting Ramallah

About six months before the interview, Gil had yet another mind changing experience. His partner who has been many times to the OPT invited him to join her on a visit. After talking about it a few times, Gil reluctantly agreed. As mentioned by Gil, and as I have witnessed myself, when talking to Israelis about Ramallah, what immediately comes up is the subject of the 2003 lynching of two Israeli soldiers. This is the image that remained carved in Israelis' minds. For Gil, this would be the first time he would step into the OPT as a civilian.

The issue of language is a sensitive one. When working in East Jerusalem and visiting various sites around the West Bank I found myself not wanting to speak Hebrew or to let people know I spoke Hebrew. I was not sure whether it was purely out of fear, or whether I just felt I needed to respect the people and the environment, considering the context. When speaking with long-time Israeli peace workers and activists I found out that they do the same. To speak Hebrew in these regions felt like to them as using the language of the occupier, even though they themselves were not partisans to that kind of politics. The funny thing was that more than once, the Palestinians who were on the other side of the conversation changed the language to Hebrew, and I am not so sure why that was, but it felt like they did not want to be paternalized.

Gil tried faking a British English accent when talking to his partner to seem like he is not from around. She told him they choose not to speak Hebrew not so much out of fear, but out of respect, since "They [Palestinians] cannot come to West Jerusalem anytime they want and speak Hebrew, so we'll speak English." Out of fear, and in a serious attempt, Gil kept creating accents, overreaching in

order to protect himself. His partner alerted him that “everybody knows you’re Jewish Israeli. Your accent is ridiculous, and you’re wearing these sandals and this shirt...” Not only the heavy Hebrew accent was too heavy to hide, but Gil’s dress code was too culturally identifiable as Jewish Israeli. Gil did not agree with her and insisted on continuing with his charade, until suddenly, while they’re walking down the street in Ramallah, a man comes to him out of his shop and speaks in Hebrew to him: “Come, come my friend, come see the merchandise, come!” Gil gets his partner’s point. He asks himself now, whether it is just a matter of time until they kill him.

And time goes by, and the day becomes more and more fun, and I loosen up, and more people speak to me in Hebrew, and then I meet my partner’s friends and they’re amazing... And then something amazing happened. This girl we met, her mother also had cancer, and she passed away in the same hospital as my mother did. And we found out we were there in the same places, the same year, same hospital, same floor, and same ward... And it’s possible we saw each other. The difference was I came on weekends in uniform and brought my mother in a wheelchair, and she had to wait for four or five hours in the Calandia checkpoint [where Palestinians coming from Ramallah have to enter Jerusalem] every time. And then I broke through another phase... I don't know if you’ve seen it, but there is a big sign on the Israeli side of checkpoints saying “the entry to ‘A’ area is dangerous for Israelis and prohibited by law”... This separation... All the time there is system that makes sure you won’t know what is happening on the other side, and to keep people apart all the time. And they tell you that beyond the wall there are monsters. And by the way, to them [Palestinians] the same story is told. But on their side there is more justification since what they see are only soldiers.

This was Gil’s first friendly contact with Palestinians. “These encounters helped me understand who I was, and why I am not that person anymore. It doesn’t sound right to me, but today I define myself according to what I am not, and not what I am.”

Fear

Gil tells about an experience at *Tapuach* (Hebrew for apple) checkpoint, inside the West Bank, where he was stationed for a long time. He describes how they would pull to the roadside and detain Palestinians who would behave disorderly, cut in front of others in line or respond defiantly to the soldiers. Not once did he detain anyone due to suspicion regarding security. One day a man with

his family was asked by Gil's colleague to stop the car and wait on the roadside. He stopped the car and walked towards them. Gil told him he could not do approach them, that they will go to him. The man continues walking and Gil shouts 'you can't come here', now pointing the gun at him. The man steps up to him and says "Why are you delaying me now? Why are you detaining my family? What's wrong with you? I have children inside who wish to go home, why are you detaining us?" Gil at this point was really stressed, and the man now is really close to him and shouting at him. Three soldiers jump on the man and push him to the ground, handcuffing and blindfolding him. His wife and kids are next to the car watching the seen, frozen in their places, completely terrified. Gil takes him back to his car, to sit there while they wait. Gil says:

He started talking to me, and I am terrified of him. He took all my power away. He said 'Do you know what it makes me feel? That a kid like you has to see me [terrified], or has to handcuff me? Do you realize how weak you are? Do you know how small you are? Do you know how miserable you are - I think you are afraid of me. [...] If you feel you need to arrest me, it seems you are terrified of me. How weak you are and how strong I am!' [...] I noticed that he was right. All we do, we do out of an insane fear and weakness. All the power we have is a complete sham.

6.2 Discussion on De-Identification

In this section I discuss how processes of de-identification relate to the three elements that in this work define *Zionism: Jewishness, security/militarism* and the *hegemonic Zionist discourse*. Since these are not independent concepts, any shift in one of them might generate a shift in the others, therefore, in my view it is a matter of around which of these three elements the processes observed tend to center around.

Yosef seems to have gone through a few clear phases in his process of de-identification. The first was the shock of the encounter with Jewish settlers and the political reality on the ground. His initial questioning remained within the frontiers of hegemonic discourse, reinforced by military training and culture of non-questioning and obedience. Towards the end of the military service Yosef and some of his colleagues felt they needed to do something to recover morality and

dignity for the sake of the Zionist project to which they dedicated themselves so much. He and his colleagues founded *Breaking the Silence*, which aim was to show Israeli public the reality and have them press the government to change policy in the OPT or end the occupation, which would salvage Zionist ethos as they had always understood it. Up to this point, the main questioning presented by Yosef was regarding the Zionist component of security/militarism. Israel was clearly not under threat; rather its deployment of the IDF was inflicting unjust treatment towards Palestinians while favoring what Yosef considered criminal behavior on part of the Jewish settlers, thus generating more hatred and insecurity towards Israel.

Unexpectedly, *Breaking the silence* had explosive growth and became much larger than they imagined. Its implications went way beyond just a 'route correction' of Zionist military ethos – it infringed on identity and challenged its legitimacy. As a result, Yosef became confused as to his motivations and goals, both in the Zionist mindset and in his role as a critic, and decided to leave Israel. During seven years abroad, of which only on the fourth he came back to visit, he kept a distance and was able to flexibilize his self-perception, his identity. He experimented taking on different identities, just by not presenting himself as Jewish or Israeli, and a different name. He understood identity as having a non-essential nature, as a construct, as something he could decide to shed or keep, according to the context. Yosef considered not returning to Israel ever again, and felt no need to be Jewish. In this sense, he crossed a line that allowed him to exist and not necessarily have Jewish identity be his first defining identity. As he points out, he does not think Israel is a Jewish state as it is, since it does not follow Jewish precepts. These self perceptions and perceptions of the State break with the character of *Jewishness*. The idea that there is an essential Jewish characteristic in him, or that there is an essential relation between the government of Israel and an ancient relation of the Jewish people to the land has become irrelevant.

Yosef went back and was ready to look deeper into where this combination of events could lead him. He dove into deep crisis finding out more about how Palestinians were not what the hegemonic Zionist discourse has led him to believe, and were as human and as sensitive as he was, looking for similar things

out of life, and having similar sense of respect and justice. He came face to face with the fact that Israel has been the aggressor all along. Yosef reached a point where he still has a longing for the beauty of the old Zionist identity that now seems unreal and false. The emotional memory remains though, and he ponders upon whether the State would be less inhumane if it really were closer to Judaism or not, maybe in an attempt to salvage Jewish identity at least. At this point there is very little Yosef is not willing to question. He understood there was an imposition of an interpretation of the world through a Zionist template, which forced a distorted perception of reality.

Amos's process had also started with a shock that made him question the integrity of the military structure. His own experience of having killed people sparked an internal conversation regarding the morality of the act and its context. His strong interest in the Holocaust made him weigh many of perceptions of his own military activities against it, drawing parallels that clash with the hegemonic discourse and are considered taboo. He became conscious of how important the Holocaust is in Zionist identity and discourse, serving as a pre-approval for committing violence, which is acceptable as long as it doesn't reach the level of the Nazis. He used to be curious regarding how was it possible for the Nazis to have done what they did. He Imagined looking through the eyes of a Palestinian boy whose village was invaded by IDF soldiers, and concluded the boy could see him as Jewish boys saw Nazi soldiers, possibly. Reflecting on good and evil made Amos become aware there was a lot Zionism shared with Nazism in its original thought patterns. He does not believe the two were the same, but the mere existence of a few shared elements was enough to make it clear that there is a serious gap in the discourse. In his comparisons, Amos breaks with possibly the most untouchable taboo in *hegemonic Zionist discourse*, the Holocaust. Although it was not originally part of Zionist doctrine, the Holocaust became instrumentalized during the first 2 decades after its occurrence. To challenge the holocaust, and to make comparisons between Nazism and Zionism, as thin as they may be, is so unthinkable among Jews that any further challenges to *Zionist hegemony* becomes easier from there. By taking away the positions of 'absolute evil' from Nazis, and 'absolute victims' from Jews, Amos makes it possible for Jews to occupy the place

of oppressors as well. Additionally, he takes away the essential character of Judaism as being the reason for persecution, thus making anyone eligible for victim position, including Palestinians. This extricates Jews from the eternal victim position, and undermines *security/militarism* principle.

Becoming aware how Palestinians perceived her as a Jew in Israel triggered Tamar's change. They were surprised she treated them nicely. Coming from a rather pluralistic society, albeit with its own problems, she rejected the notion that being Jewish included her in a categorization that meant automatically something negative to Palestinians. It did not represent her. It pushed her to want to have interactions with Palestinians and made her look for a space of dialogue. Her initial approach was in her words 'naïve' attempts, where she thought it was possible to convince soldiers during demonstrations that they should not take part of oppressive actions. Lacking results, she moved on to more structured action through an NGO where action was based on political strategy. In this organization she worked as a political tour guide where educating the public on the conflict. As she became aware of how large is the challenge of changing the *hegemonic Zionist discourse*, she felt she was making little progress in changing anything. She felt her personal principles of justice, equality, dignity and respect having to be calmed down and silenced in order to mold them into 'strategic' forms, which in her perception took away from the value of those principles, and thus diminished her commitment to such values. Being authentic she could not change anything, and in order to change she had to push her convictions aside for the sake of strategy. This impossibility of being authentic made her feel the situation was so complicated and difficult to change that she decided to leave. *Hegemonic Zionist discourse* dictates that in Israeli society what constitutes a 'neutrality', the 'norm' or the base-line against which all other groups in society are deemed 'different', is the majority of Israeli Jewish population, who are secular Jews heavily influenced by Ashkenazi culture. The 'different' are sub-groups such as reformist, nationalist and orthodox religious groups, settler groups, traditional non-European groups such as the Ethiopians and others. Tamar became aware this 'neutrality' does not exist, rather a hegemonic domination of a 'civic-religious' group with its particular culture and set of beliefs. Tamar sees the secular Jews' blaming of settlers for

extremism and for worsening the conflict as hypocritical, since they are fully backed on all instances by a democratically elected government, and serve as a discursive tool in the hands of secular Jews for 'externalizing' responsibility to settlers. Tamar excludes herself from that category as well, as she cannot see herself affiliated with the 'civic religion' of Jewish secularist culture. Many Jews who engage actively in challenging *hegemonic Zionist discourse* get discouraged and desist. Some become depressed and give in to the sad reality they do not believe they can change. Others take a break and return to fight once they recharge their energies. It is hard to know at this point whether Tamar will return.

Gil has also started questioning during the army, where the indoctrination that had prepared him for it did not match the realities he encountered both in the executive structure of the IDF itself, and in the role it had in the OPT. He makes connections between a situation he was involved in with a Palestinian boy and stories his grandmother tells about the Holocaust. Once more, the Holocaust plays a central role in the moral structure, much so in Gil's case who had visited the concentration and extermination camps twice, once with school and the other with his grandmother. Gil compares his grandmother's heroic braving of the Nazi curfews to bring food to her family and neighbors in the ghetto, and the Palestinian boy's actions to do the same for his fellow Palestinians under Israeli curfew. Although Gil stresses he does not make a full comparison, since his grandmother would be shot dead if caught and the Palestinian boy would not, he still experiments with comparing his place with that of the Nazis. His grandmother's Holocaust most terrifying memories centered on the moment where distinctions first began to be made against Jews, much before the 'final solution' was put in place, which makes Gil compare these early stages more directly to the current situation since 'separation' has been 'normalized' in Israeli society to the point people rarely see there is anything wrong with it. Again, comparing Nazism to Zionism and Israeli policies represents possibly the most serious challenge to Zionist discourse and the victimhood argument.

When Gil was put back into Israeli Jewish society as part of his military service, to educate adolescents in schools, the fault lines dividing the reality between the OPT and Israel crumbled, and he treats Jewish Israeli adolescents

with the same violence he treats Palestinians the same age. He becomes aware Zionism is a violent machine, and that violence is committed against himself and other Israelis by the army and the national hegemonic discourse, by turning them violent and desensitized. This violence often turns against oneself, sometimes culminating in form of suicide. He had been part of a cover-up of a suicide, ordered by his commander, and he reflects on how the IDF tries to protect its image. Gil decides then to give testimonies to the NGO Breaking the Silence, as a first reaction against all this pressure. After the army he becomes a member, and over time he becomes one of the main leaders of the organization, formalizing his commitment to the goals of the NGO. He went through phases of internal negotiation regarding what could he keep of his identity and what did he need to discard, what attitudes and behaviors he needed to change and which ones he needed to continue. When he went for the first time to the OPT as a civilian, his fear was met with warm treatment. No matter how much he tried to hide his Jewish Israeli identity, he was recognized and treated well. Although it drove him into deeper confusion and heartbreak, he realized to which degree he was still retaining bits and pieces, and sometimes large pieces of the *hegemonic Zionist discourse* that demonizes Palestinians, from whom he was receiving a warm and friendly treatment.

Taking the theories on identity discussed in section 1.5, I find there are relations to be made between what we can observe in the de-identification processes described by the interviewees, and approaches presented by Fearon (1999), Taylor (1992), and Laitin and Chandra (2002). Fearon (1999, p.32) affirms that identity is a formulation of dignity, pride, status, honor and self-respect. Taylor (1992, p.27) refers to identity as being a moral compass. In all four cases examined, interviewees found their identity did not represent their moral values. Whether it was Yosef and his discoveries of what is the actual intervention of the IDF in the OPT, or Amos who through his experience of having killed entered a deep self examination of morality, good and evil and the ultimate references of the Holocaust, Nazis and their relation to the Zionist enterprise. Tamar's rejection of both Jewish Israeli discriminatory treatment of Palestinians, as well as her rejection of both her orthodox past and secularist culture or civic-religion which

she found hypocritical. And Gil's confusion as to where lines should be drawn to separate people from one another in order to treat them differently, and his wondering as to whether Israel even has a right to exist. All these rejections are based on accounts of Zionism not fulfilling the need these individuals have for certain moral values. Thinking in terms of Laitin and Chandra's (2002) theory, Zionism ceased to be an identity category by which the interviewees describe themselves. If we consider the attributes that qualify an individual for the identity category of Zionism, which in this work we consider to be subscription to the three pillars: Jewishness, security/militarism and hegemonic Zionist discourse; we see the erosion of these three elements in all interviewees.

7. Searching For a New Identity

After finding out that one's personal values and identity does not match the collective identity it was once inserted in, and some distancing takes place from Zionism, a new challenge arises which is to find a new way to define oneself, a way which does not include the old component of Zionism, or at least the elements of which that are not compatible with the core beliefs of the individual in question.

7.1 Interviews

Yosef

During his years abroad, Yosef remembers clearly a moment when he realized life could be lived without the burden that comes with being Israeli, Jewish and Zionist, and he wished his friends knew about his discovery.

Maybe I could be Kiwi [New-Zelander]. Maybe I don't have to be Israeli Maybe I don't have to be Jewish". I was the only Israeli in town, so nobody really cared. There wasn't anyone I could reflect off as an Israeli. I wasn't speaking Hebrew. I was Jo. I was a bartender at a sports bar, it was wonderful! I had nothing... I was on a completely different planet! For a long time... I don't need to talk about it... I don't need to think about it...

Yosef was rehearsing another life. He was attempting to verify if he could still being himself, shed all these layers and labels that had characterized him so far. He wanted to see if what was left was still Yosef. Nowadays he has matured a lot of his self-perception, and can go back and forth within his identity without that meaning a commitment, since these 'labels' as he calls them have been emptied from meaning

It took me a while... On many levels I've come full circle with certain things. For a while there I wasn't Israeli and I wasn't Jewish. I reclaimed my Jewish roots. I've come back to it and I said: 'actually, you know what? I *am* Jewish.' ammm... and to the extent that someone needs to meet an Israeli that's kinda sobered up, then I'm willing to say: 'you know what? I'm *also* Israeli.' So that you can see that there are Israelis that are actually sobering up and understanding that something here really needs to change. And it's a label and that all it is. Actually my name is MIKA, and it's nice to meet you kinda... but if we need the labels then I'm willing to reclaim them in order to show you that they're just labels, and that there's something else behind them.

Yosef describes how to him, taking physical distance was critical, and while being away attempting to live different routines, in different jobs, meeting different people and following events as they appeared instead of giving them shape with plans, in order to break the frames that have for so long entrapped him into an identity that did not fit who he was.

Currently Yosef perceives his immediate environment to be much more real to him than abstract concepts such as State, patriotism and Zionism. He believes he can influence this environment much more than he can ever influence the state. His current activities with the new NGO he founded called *Grassroots Jerusalem* focuses on creating a network of all Jewish and Palestinian grassroots initiatives for social justice around Jerusalem in order to create an example of coexistence.

I don't advocate for a Jewish state. That's not what I... What I'm saying is... ammm... that along with letting go, of the reality that I was born into, ammm... and was part of, and was going to be part of... I also had to let go of a bunch of other concepts. The state, as opposed to my community, and building my own community around me, the state becomes less relevant to me. 'Cause my circle is what I know, the family, the community of Jerusalem as a city, is much more important to me as Israel as a state. I think Jerusalem has much more potential and if we'd focus on our local communities I think we'd get much, much farther than if we focus on what politicians can do in an abstract kind of state. 'Cause this is... the state is more a mindset, and in my mind an actual sustainable community is in my own city, in my own urban reality [...] Israel and Palestine, that's a mindset. That's abstract. That's not real. That's not... It isn't real in the sense that if you have two soldiers running across a hill towards one another waiting to kill each other, and they're the last two people on the battle field, and if you stop them for a second and if you ask them where the war is? Then the only place it is, is in their mind. It's not real. And in that sense, neither is Palestine and Israel. But Jerusalem is real, and the community and the policy, the municipal policies, and the way Silwan (Palestinian neighborhood suffering discrimination from city hall) works today, and the way the German Colony (Jewish neighborhood favored by city hall) look

today, that's real stuff that is not abstract to me - I can go and see that. And that's something I want to be focusing on. I don't really care anymore about the... patriotism, Zionism, being... belonging to some abstract label...

Yosef is now pursuing goals of talking to 'difficult' audiences among Jewish people. The ones who are extreme nationalists and think the peace camp are traitors. He wishes to calm their fear, assuring them what he and his colleagues are proposing is not the elimination of the Jewish people, but the assurance it will survive not only physically, but morally as well. According to Yosef, one of the dangers so feared by dedicated Zionists, which serves as rationale for Israeli policies is the demise of the Jewish people. But if the moral core of Judaism is disrespected and disregarded by Zionism, even if Zionism prevails, Judaism will not.

I wanted to go to the Zionist Jewish youth movements... I wanna talk to them... they need someone right now, especially the 20, 30 year olds that are really confused, more than ever today about Israel, I want... they deserve actually... they need someone to sit them down and say it's OK to be confused. You're right!... It's confusing! First and foremost it's OK. I wanna do that, they need that... I needed that... I wish someone could have done that with me... and I want to go do that with them.

When asked how does he position himself regarding having a Jewish state, which is the core of Zionism, or whether he cares or not about it anymore, Yosef reiterates his new view of a smaller and more local understanding of Jewish collective

I do care... I think it's OK to be Jewish, and I think it's OK to want a Jewish community, and I think it's OK to want a Jewish community in Jerusalem, and Tel Aviv... I think that's fine...

If we weren't so afraid... imagine the level of Judaism we could actually evolve into... What's Jewish about what we're doing now? This isn't Jewish. What's going on here... is NOT Jewish. The occupation isn't Jewish, the ultra-orthodox rabbis that control who I get to marry, how I get to marry, what tradition I am supposed to be following... we erased Yemenite Judaism, we erased Ethiopian Judaism, we've erased so many cultures in the name of this new neo-Judaism... this isn't it... So when people are sticking with the Jewish state, I don't think they're sticking with something real...I think it's something very artificial built on fear, and it's not built on passion, or a connection with the divine order... through a Jewish lenses... It's very artificial... it's very superficial... there's no depth to it. There's no depth, feelings, spiritual thoughts.

Amos

Amos began building a new identity through building new understanding of moral values, good and evil. He describes how his starting point was his own body, his most primary individual reality. He was experiencing the world in various directions in an attempt to rebuild from scratch. He traveled a lot by himself, spent large amounts of time naked becoming a nudist for a while.

If everything is so fluid and there is no good or evil anymore and you can decide what it is, you can also define what happens in life by deciding how to look at things, and you can also define what happens by choosing what you look at... So you can choose what you see... I was blind to the crimes of Zionism, and I opened my eyes, so for sure there are many other things I am blind to, and I can open my eye to those things and shut them to others, and you can define reality, and I felt like god for a while, that I control reality completely, until I felt it was exaggerated...

“Identity is a very important issue”, says Amos.

I think this is essentially what I was looking for, a new identity, because suddenly my previous identity broke down... There is a game we play in the youth movement, of placing where am I in the triangle formed by ‘Jewish’, ‘Israeli’ and ‘Zionist’ on each corner. I could easily place myself closest to ‘Zionist’, somewhere between ‘Zionist’ and ‘Israeli’, tending a little to the ‘Jewish’. Meaning I am mainly here and strong, and Israeli and Zionist, but there are also Jewish roots, but because I am *hiloni* (Hebrew for secular) I am less connected to them, but I know the history and such... This was very clear, a kind of a tri-fold identity.

Q - To be *hiloni* meant to be less Jewish?

Less Jewish, yes, but on the other hand, I am the one who carries on his back the whole Jewish history, and it can only continue because I protect this place and I build here a state that is a part of... The *hiloni* Jewish identity is somehow more important for the Jewish people, because we are those who in fact will be able to do it with weapons and work the land etc. And if we remain orthodox, then... [we will not be able to do it] Religious Zionists were like that [able to carry guns and work], but I simply did not believe in god.

Amos believes his process was much easier because he had a lot of support. His two brothers, cousin and mother went through the process with him. All of them became activists and were discussing the issue constantly. His cousin joined *Breaking the Silence*; one of his brothers signed a famous collective letter from the Air Force pilots, called *The Pilot's Letter*, refusing to bomb civilian areas. His other

brother signed a similar letter from the top elite unit of the IDF, called *The Matkalist's Letter*. Both these letters have stirred commotion among Israeli society, for there are few symbols that represent more strongly the heroic Israeli Zionist fighter, the new image of the secular Jew, than these two sections of the IDF.

Only three months after the 2010 Gaza Flotilla Raid, where Israeli military killed a few pro-Palestinian activists, Amos took part in a subsequent initiative by a Jewish group of activists who navigated a vessel to Gaza aiming to break the Israeli naval blockade in what was called the Jewish Flotilla. On the way he describes having a feeling he could call himself 'Mediterranean'.

There is great food, great weather, ocean, and great people... I'll be Mediterranean... But really, I don't have a punctual need for identity nowadays... I might have an identity, which is a bunch of things together... I enjoy a lot the fact that I have access to the cultural origins of elitist Zionism, and that for myself, I know enough Judaism and I can do lyrical, political and communication things with that. But it remained as something from my past out of which I can draw catchphrases to shout out to soldiers at checkpoints, to write a song or understand people around me. On the other hand I don't see it as something that obligate me to anything. So I decided that I don't need to define who I am under a certain term, since I am pretty much against this idea... I need to know who I am in terms of how I want to live, what I want to do, How I think... And that also changes all the time, but I have no reason to say I am Israeli, Jewish, and Zionist. If people ask me abroad where am I from, I sometimes say I am from Palestine, I sometimes say I am from Israel, sometimes I say I am from Israel/Palestine... If people ask me if I am Jewish, then I sometimes say I am Jewish, and many times I say I am not Jewish... In conversations with orthodox people... He [the orthodox Jew] says: "you know how it is..."

- "No, I am not Jewish... I am just interested in the issue"

- "So how do you speak Hebrew so well?"

- "I grew up in this region"

- "So how you are not Jewish?"

- "I don't know. How is it that you are?"

- "Oh... that's a long story... but you... wait a moment, are your parents Jewish?"

- "I don't know. Ask them. It's been a long time since they've told me 'we are Jewish'. They don't believe in god, nor do these things..."

- "But are they children of Jews?"

- "Well, I think that if you had asked my grandparents, they would say they were Jews."

- "Well, so you are Jewish!"

... When people say I am a traitor, I feel the need to explain to the person that in his view I am a traitor because he sees things in black and white, and I see it differently, and why I am not a traitor and why he in my opinion is not more important than an Arab.

Amos used to be the Israeli coordinator for Fighters for Peace, and used to be in the OPT all the time. He has many Palestinian friends. Nowadays he works as political tour guide, which has been a growing instrument of social change in recent years.

Tamar

Tamar does not believe she changed with the process. She remembers how her family would speak about blacks in New York, and how it made her angry at this racism. She was always a person who was disturbed by racism, hatred, and this kind of violence and thinking. Tamar believes she remains the same, but that she was exposed to this kind of violence.

Especially for me being raised religious, being Jewish goes to the deepest root of who you are. So this [experience] travels down that root and shakes the very foundations of who you are. [...] What I've done as a coping mechanism is I divided [in my mind] Israeli Jews as redeemed Jews, from exile Jews. The way I saved my sense of identity was to say I am an exile Jew. That's who I am, and Israeli Jews are different. I identify very strongly with Jews who were raised in countries other than Israel, but Israeli Jews to me don't feel Jewish. To me being Jewish means by definition not part of the hegemony.

Nowadays Tamar makes this distinction between redeemed and exiled Jews, and by considering herself an exile Jew she rejects any responsibility for the conflict:

This is not my problem; it's an Israeli problem. It has nothing to do with me. [...] It's not a rejection of something that's inside of me. It's just that I don't identify with it. If I would do this with Orthodox Judaism, that is something that I was raised with. But this... Israeli culture is foreign to me. Israeli Jews are foreign to me, much more than French Jews.

Tamar has no desire to identify or be a part of what Israel is under Zionist precepts. She does not fight Zionism or the occupation from the inside. She does not want to redeem her identity. In the past she used to think the banner 'Not In Our Name' was representative of her, which was a slogan that expressed Jewish rejection of Israeli policies as representative of the Jewish people as a whole. Nevertheless, after her experience in Israel she has reached a conclusion that that

was not her name to begin with, meaning within this dichotomy between Jews that agree with Israeli policies and Jews that do not, she does not consider she falls into any of these categories, since both still are Jewish in relation to the Israeli state.

Tamar believes nowadays Jews in Israel would benefit the most if Israel became a fully democratic state, relinquishing its Jewish character and possibly even changing its name to accommodate a pluralistic future population. She sustains that position even if a two-state solution is achieved, because it is not just a matter of defending Palestinians rights, but protecting values that are lost otherwise.

Gil

Gil recounts how he met with his ex-instructor from the pre-military prep-course one day on the street, and told him about his work with *Breaking the Silence*. His ex-instructor was deeply disappointed in him, and told him: "You have to ask yourself one thing: are your activities and the people you are working with Zionist or not." Gil thought of himself for a long time as not at all post-Zionist. He considered himself as the New Zionism. Gil considers that Zionism nowadays is an indefinable concept. Its original conception is over, since its project of creating a Jewish state was accomplished in 1948. A new definition was given after that, which was the development of the existing state.

For my ex-instructor in the pre-military prep-course, to develop Zionism is to send 40 new officers every year. For me to develop Zionism is to make an economic boycott on Israel... because that is what will save us. This definition is so confusing... To say I am post-Zionist or neo-Zionist in my view has no meaning. When I am protesting [with other activists] in Hebron, I am post-Zionist. I stretch my limit. I even rupture it. But when I give a lecture, I am the neo-Zionism. That is dangerous, because the Nationalist Left, or the 'Rightists Left' as we call them, also claims to be neo-Zionist. *Im Tirtzu*¹² also declares itself neo-Zionist [...] It is the

¹²"*Im Tirtzu* is a centrist extra-parliamentary movement that strives to strengthen the values of Zionism in Israel and to renew and reinstate Zionist discourse, thinking and ideology in order to secure the future of the Jewish people and the State of Israel and strengthen Israeli society in the challenges it faces. *Im Tirtzu* is committed to leading and advancing a second Zionist revolution on all levels of the Israeli public discourse: intellectual, cultural, media and political." (Mission statement retrieved from *Im Tirtzu* Official website:

exact opposite [of what I mean by neo-Zionism]. But I feel that if I say wholeheartedly that I am post-Zionist, I gave up on everything that is happening here.

Gil's partner is a conscientious objector, which at very young age and although from a Zionist family had decided she is not Zionist and believes the concept to be racist and should end. She also believes statehood and nationalism are as pernicious and should not exist. Gil still sees value in these concepts, and believes Palestinians do not want to have one country with Jewish Israelis. He believes they want a country of their own, and that it is important for them to get to have this kind of pride. At this point he says, they need it in order to build their own identity. A one-state solution would be premature in Gil's opinion.

Gil also does not believe there is any point in studying in Israel nowadays. He believes vision is very narrow in Israel.

Gil talks about values:

I think your value system has to be built in a way that it doesn't matter where you are born or die. It can continuously be shaped and you can learn new things, but your moral and spiritual basis, you must be able to tell yourself 'it would be the same if I were born in Rio [or elsewhere],' and it is clearly not what I had. Clearly what I was given was a sham. It was mundane, based on fear, on hatred, it was racist.

"I would love to cancel my 'membership card' [referring to being member in the Jewish collective]." Gil would like to be able to not feel bound to the Jewish group, Zionist group or Israeli group, in the manner his brother did right after the military service, when he left to Germany where he lives to this date with his wife, and considers himself a German, and follows Buddhism.

I can't... after all this conversation it sound funny... I accept all this weight on myself. I accept not only that I was born into some kind of 'sludge' [complicated situation], but that I have contributed to it all my life, not only in the military, but that I continue to contribute to it and that what will happen here is my responsibility [...] I can't escape this responsibility. I feel Jewish, I feel Israeli... As much as I said before that I define myself nowadays by what I am not, I also define myself by the future, when I imagine with my partner our children and what kind of country I want them to live in. I accept this weight of being Jewish and Israeli in

Jerusalem; I am completely addicted to it. I don't know what I will do the day when I cannot any longer define myself as a human rights activist. Theoretically in a world where all these problems will no longer exist, I will be very confused... The entire definition of myself is related to the oppression that I inflicted and that I suffered. It's scary to think of this...

While his friends went after the military service to their round-the-world trip, Gil started working almost immediately in *Breaking the Silence*. Now most of his friends are almost graduating their undergrad courses, and he occupies a key position in the organization. "I am not capable of leaving it," He says. "I feel this is my definition today. I need to atone for things, but I am also searching for a definition of myself. My definition today is not of a self-hating Jew [he laughs], but of a Jew that loves himself very much."

Gil does not believe enough in the Israeli society to change itself. That is why he supports the boycott and world pressure. "I love Israeli society and the country, and I do what I do out of selfish motivation..." Both he and his partner believe that although it may seem as though their activities look like they are for Palestinians, but what they are actually doing is they are nesting out of their own selfish needs. They want to see their children growing in Jerusalem, but for that there must be justice and equality.

All of this struggle, my will to change things, all my nerves... every day I am nervous every day I hear stories... [Gil's job in *Breaking the Silence* is to collect testimonies from Israeli soldiers] Everyday I sit in front of soldiers that tell me what they did during their service... Most of them don't understand what they are telling me, they just speak up, and they don't understand the political and military context. All the nerves and the sensitivity and the tears and the happiness and this struggle... All of this is in fact is a journey in search of the definition of what kind of human being I am.

It seems that one of the things that motivates me the most, in my daily life... My mother was very important to me. She was the most important person who knew me. Through her eyes, I think I molded who I am. I saw how she looked at me with love and respect, and what kind of person she thinks I am, and I all the time aspired to that place. And she died when I was a soldier in Hebron. And my biggest regret in life, really, even larger than my regret of having served the military or done what I did, my biggest regret in life is that my mother died knowing that that was what I did, and that she cannot see me today doing what I do, because I would like her to know who I really am. And I say who I really am, I mean, I want my mother to see who is the real Gil. The Real Gil is the one who works in *Breaking the silence*, and that goes to demonstration in the OPT, and that fights for justice and equality, and isn't scared and loves... But what does it say? It's not a good enough definition 'Gil that goes to demonstrations in the OPT', this

can't be the definition of my identity... and in fact, all my struggle is a struggle after I was crushed... I grew up in a certain way, I knew a world in a certain way... It got erased... the army finished me. I lost all my identity components in the army. In fact, in this sense the army did me a great service, because it managed to disassemble my whole identity, and gave me the space to rebuild it. And now through this entire struggle I am rebuilding it.

Gil believes the question of identity is central to the matter at hand: "your questions about identity are the most important questions that Israeli activists, or Palestinian activists can be asked nowadays, because everyone in this struggle defines him/herself by the struggle." In his view everyone is fighting without knowing exactly who they are. "It is very comfortable to say who you are inside a group, more so a group that sounds appealing." Gil believes that of all the aggression radical peace movements suffer in Israel from public opinion, being called traitors only makes these movements stronger.

At the end of the day, what established identity? By the things you do? By the things you were born with? By where your grandparents came from, if they have been through a concentration camp or not? Nowadays I don't believe there is a need for a state only for Jews. But I do believe in having my son know he is Jewish, and know Jewish history.

Gil talks about the group to which his partner belongs, which became famous through the *Shministim* (Hebrew for twelfth-graders) letter, in which they denounce Israeli occupation and object to serve in the military. Typically these adolescents are put in jail for a few months for refusing to serve the military. Gil used to abhor this group since he did not believe they could be so critical of the situation without having served the military first and experiencing the reality first hand. "I couldn't stand the possibility that someone could know something before doing it, mainly because of what it said about me. Because it meant I failed somewhere. My partner understood something before me. I changed my mind before I met her." Gil felt it took away from his pain of having lived the role of the oppressor. He could not understand how these young people could understand how horrible it was without having gone through it. Much of what Gil has managed to go through, he believes he was only able to go through thanks to the support of his partner. "There are things that you can only do if someone takes

your hand, and it has to be someone really close to you [...], and says 'I will jump with you over the next stumbling block', the one you can't pass without them. Some things you can't do by yourself."

7.2 Discussion on the Search for a New Identity

Yosef seems to have gone through a difficult, yet liberating identity crisis, where he could experience the possibility of being himself yet not having to carry the identities that have forced him to come under ideologies and attitudes that he morally disagrees with. He has made his peace with his past, in the sense that he accepts his origins, without feeling he is bound to any identity that does not satisfy his moral needs. From his experience of living through the collision between his Zionist identity with its derived expectations, and the reality he encountered as a soldier and later as a civilian in the OPT, it seems he has acquired a critical perspective, which allows him to make distinctions between constructed identities with manipulative context he deems meaningless, and identities that actually are representative of the individual. Possibly in this sense, he feels liberated from his past identity *categories*, as termed by Laitin and Chandra (2002). Yet he understands their value in the eyes of most Jews. In his role as a political activist advocating for social justice in Israel/Palestine he appears to instrumentalize identity *categories* in his work, so he identifies himself according to what will help him best relate to people or get his message across. Although he now stands far away from his starting point, he remembers his Zionist worldview and identity as it used to be, which allows him to be aware of the difficulties Jews face when exposed to discourses that challenge their Zionist identity, by challenging Zionism and its notions of *Jewishness*, *security/militarism* and the *hegemonic Zionist discourse*. When questioned about his current national identity, Yosef seems to reject the notion of national identity altogether. His collective identity is now defined on smaller more local scale, where he can see concretely the repercussions of his actions. Yosef's case illustrates Fearon's (1999, p.26) definition of identity as a representation of dignity and self-respect, and his assertion that it is the defense of such values that move people to act. The choices made by Yosef also illustrate

ideas of identity crisis described by Taylor (1992, pp. 27, 28) as a re-orientation in a moral space. By remembering his mindset from his relinquished Zionist identity, Yosef understands that the Zionist Jewish public he addresses in his work also draws its dignity and self-respect from their Zionist identity. I find it remarkable how this knowledge translates into a non-aggressive action when challenging Zionist discourse, and subsequently in positive constructive results. From a general observation of social-justice activists involved in this struggle it is possible to conclude that such feat is quite rare.

It is interesting to notice a similar movement done by Yosef and Amos of an attempt of a maximal reduction of their perception of themselves, to themselves alone. In Yosef's case it was an abandonment of all labels and a feeling he 'is', he exists, even without them. In Amos's case it became more physical in his nudist phase, where he 'is' only his body, and nothing else. In both cases all weight that came attached to the categories of identity they carried was gone, as they became only themselves, Yosef and Amos, people and no more. Starting from the most basic point, his body, Amos attempted to re-construct morality. As with Yosef, Amos also did not simply 'switch' identities. His identity crisis led to a need for complete reconstruction. He became aware of the loss of his identity, which had been a good example of Ahad Ha'am's secular Judaism or *Jewishness*, and later on Ben-Gurion's civic-religion, led by Ashkenazi Jews, the dominant cultural group in Israel since its inception. He explains the pride that was involved in the identity of the *hiloni* Jew, who carries all Jewish history on his back, and on whom the future of Judaism depend, although not its essence. To carry the essence, religious Jews were necessary. Amos has gone through a rough process of breaking the otherwise 'untouchable' taboo of the Holocaust. Although it might sound shocking to some, he is not a radical, therefore he does not compare fully between Zionists' treatment of Palestinians to Nazi treatment of Jews. However, the slightest comparisons that he manages to make successfully, were enough for the whole Zionist moral structure to come crumbling down in his mind. When Amos realized he was active part of what he calls "the crimes of Zionism", he indicates he needed to regain his dignity and self-respect, which Fearon (1999) has pointed out, is fundamentally represented by identity. Zionist identity could not provide

that anymore, which drove him to an identity crisis, as Taylor (1992) theorizes it, a loss of moral orientation, which seems to explain his drive to reconstruct moral references.

Similarly to Yosef's belief that it was due to his long stay away from Israel that he was able to change, Amos also believes his conditions were optimal and somewhat special, which made it easier for him to go through his identity crisis, mainly having support of close family members and going together through this process. Amos goes a little further than Yosef in choosing an identity category to represent him by. To an extent, he does not see any reason to keep his Jewish identity, and is willing to dispense with it, but not to the same degree as his Zionist identity. While he would say he is Jewish in certain contexts, he would not say he is Zionist under any context anymore. As an internally bargained solution he defines himself as Mediterranean, at least for now. Thinking on his choices for Jewish identity through Laitin and Chandra (2002), it seems Amos cannot see any present attributes that qualify him to the identity category 'Jewish'. However, as Yosef, and possibly many people who have gone through similar identity crisis and became aware of how questions of identity are fundamentally connected to thinking the political reality, Amos also instrumentalizes identity categories in order to reach his goals, which might be social or political.

Tamar is, in this selection I have made of the several interviews I have collected, the odd one out. She has found a way to regain, or to maintain her dignity and self-respect by making a fundamental separation between the category of Israeli Jews and Exile Jews. She defines herself as an exile-Jew, since for this identity category she has the qualifying attribute - she was born and raised in the United States. It is a maneuver in identity both Yosef and Amos cannot use. She creates a new category to fit herself and keep much of her other identity categories. Recalling Hall's (1996, p.3) use of the concept of 'frontier-effects' in delimiting the inside and outside of a group, this can be seen as the strategic use of 'frontiers' in order to isolate oneself from an unwanted series of attributes that can be dismissed by separating an entire category to which they are attached. Although she does not mention it explicitly, she did at one point become Zionist when she relinquished Jewish orthodox life and went to live in Israel. However

progressive, and however short-lived, she abandoned it and makes reference to it by referring to the experience of having lived in Israel as something that shook the deepest root of who she was. In her choice of identity she completely disconnects Judaism from Israel, and does not feel the existence of Israel is required under any form of Zionist conception. To an extent, her choice of category of identity seems to relinquish any responsibility for what has happened in the Israeli-Palestinian conflict, leaving it to the Jewish group, which decided to move there and take part in the Zionist enterprise. There is a problem in her rationale however, since Israel has relied heavily on American Jewry both politically and economically for a great part of its existence. Both American Jews who move to Israel doing aliyah and those who stay there their whole lives have taken part in such support. Nevertheless, very strong social justice for Palestine movements have also sprung from American Jewry, which makes the composition of its political orientation mixed. Tamar's definition of identity might need to mature some more in order to relay her values clearly, since the separation she suggests does not account for the identity of exile-Jew include ardent Zionists, and very influential ones too.

Gil has a more confusing stance regarding how he defines his identity. He seems to be in a negotiation with himself as to whether he can or cannot reject his Zionist identity. He presents his use of identity as Yosef and Amos do, instrumentalizing it according to context, but he believes there is value to the Zionist identity which means 'not giving up on Israel'. However, he does not use the word Zionist alone, but rather combines it with the term 'new'. Throughout the interview he has used the term in two different forms: New Zionist, and neo-Zionist. Gil described at the beginning of the interview the 'new' Zionist to be a humane Zionist, one that behaves correctly towards Palestinians. But he also recognizes that ultra-nationalists, with whom he shares no political resemblance, use the term neo-Zionism. He also suggests that to really be a Zionist, by which I believe he means 'to love one's country', is to support international boycott on Israel, and to take other actions to change the regime. He believes this is a fight to 'save' Israel, in an attempt to recover whatever beautiful images he might retain from his involuntarily blind Zionist period, which seem tainted with his

discoveries, and make them true now on a truthful basis. He wants to recover the morality not only of himself, but of the nation.

Gil reveals a definition of his identity, which he may not share openly customarily, which is that of a human right activist. If we think in terms of Laitin and Chandra's (2002) structure of identity, the attributes for this identity category could be 'Jewish', and 'Israeli', and possibly feeling it is his 'mission to correct the wrongs of Zionism'. This clearly relates as well to the quest to recover dignity and self-respect, and to find a moral way of living, all of which I have mentioned before. Gil's identity is defined not only by the conflict, but also by the discovery of the constructed character of the Zionist discourse. At the same time his identity at the moment is defined by an ethical concern regarding justice for Palestinians, it is also defined by a cyclic search for identity, where he still encounters himself in crisis.

Gil's reference to his mother's untimely death, which did not allow her to see the 'real Gil', is blatant example of Kelman's (2004, p.120) assertion that through identity change one will get closer to his own core values. Gil tells a saddening story of how finding out the truth and the service in the army smashed his life, the world he knew, and his identity. Yet almost in the same breath, he asserts that it probably was a great service done to him for which he should be thankful, for accelerating his process of identity crisis and pushing him out of his ideological prison. It made me reflect upon my own philosophical wanderings and a Yoga teacher who was prone to teach the philosophy behind the physical practice that once asked me: "Is disillusionment a bad thing?" to which normally the reaction is to say yes. However, the lesson he was trying to convey was that although there is pain in disillusionment itself, no one should prefer to remain under an illusion, living a lie, not knowing the truth. At the end of the interview Gil confesses he does not believe there is a need for a Jewish state.

Gil also speaks of the support he has from his partner and how that is helpful to go through difficult moments, as Amos has mentioned was his case with his close family. But interestingly enough, Gil also has confessed that he believes he has changed because he had hit rock bottom due to his crisis in the army added to his mother's death. He thinks his change was circumstantial, and

that if it had not been for that combination of events, he would have not gone through his process of change. As I mentioned before, this was the case of Yosef and Amos as well, and reflecting on it I must say that in my own process I felt my circumstances have somehow made it possible for me to change, since I had left the Jewish community, married a non-Jewish woman, and initiated a research into this subject – all of which contributed to my going through this process of identity crisis. Possibly, this feeling of ‘owing to circumstantialities’ evoke in me a reflection as to what were the circumstances that made other people change – hence this research. All of the interviewees became engaged in political action for social justice resulting from their identity change. In various ways they have been working to change public opinion Israel, educating the population as to what is not taught by Zionist apparatuses, in the hope they will change as well. Whether the circumstances that made possible the interviewees’ changes and mine have any equivalence in effectiveness to the ones being generated for the larger public by these political activists is yet to be seen. The strongest vantage point working in their favor is their status among their target public. Being Jewish, they can speak from within. However, they must choose language strategies that allow them to still be seen as being part of the ‘in-group’, otherwise, if they become excessively critical, they lose the vantage point. One of the biggest challenges is to attempt to approach this matter believing international modernist universal values will be the common denominator, as I discuss in the next section. Again, as I said, the vantage point these political activists have is not the fact they are Jewish by itself, but their possibility of being perceived as still part of the ‘in-group’, which relies on their capacity of remembering what their identity was like before they changed, how they used to see the world, and what were their deepest fears and needs. Speaking based on this level of comprehension and empathy, it has been the experience of many of the activists I encountered, as well as my own, that receptivity and openness to change are much easier to encounter.

8. Conclusion

This work discussed processes of changes in identity occurring amongst Jewish Israelis and Diaspora Jews, by which they have distanced themselves from Zionism. It presented interviews done in Israel with actors directly involved with political action for social justice for Palestinians and policy change in Israel, in which they engaged as a direct result of changes in the way they define their identity. These individuals who had been socialized in Zionist environment experienced reality, either in the military service or in contacts with Palestinians in everyday life in Israel, and became overwhelmed with the gap extant between that reality and their expectations, product of their Zionist socialization. This gap represented profound moral contradictions for these individuals, generating in them an identity crisis. They see themselves as being part of a collective that upholds a high-standard moral discourse, built on what now they know to be immoral practices, which in some ways have become culturally accepted, and cease to identify with this collective.

I have discussed these issues writing from a theoretical framework sympathetic to post-Zionism and New Israeli History, tending to broader critical theoretical approaches. This work has presented a definition for Zionism based on three major pillars: *Jewishness*, *security/militarism* and *hegemonic Zionism*, in order to be able to analyze the data collected and assess whether the interviewees have in fact rejected these principals, which practically to a full extent, they have, as well as the subscription to the identity category of Zionism. I have also looked into the notion of identity in this work for the sake of clarification of the discussion, and established there are considerable relations between identity and moral values, in which to an extent, it is in search or defense of these values that an individual is

motivated to act, in a sense that one's identity is a representation of what one stands for.

Thus, the main conclusion of the central issue dealt with in this research, the processes of identity-change, rejection of Zionism and de-identification of Israeli and Diaspora Jews from Zionism, is that it cannot be attributed to the common explanations of self-hatred, treason, or at times even anti-Semitism. These labels are produced as part of Zionist identity, by the same apparatuses that produce *Zionist hegemony* and the consent of large numbers of people. To them, such phenomena seem unintelligible, mainly because of Zionist nature of perceiving Zionist identity and Jewish identity as inseparable 'merged' identities, inseparable. In this conception, an explanation within the hegemonic discourse is required in order to make sense of a Jewish person that rejects Zionism. Labels are assigned then, such as 'abnormal', 'defective' or 'anti-natural', commonly reaching extremes of being associated to evil - anti-Semitism, or to psychological disorder - 'self-hating Jew'. Explanations are given such as never having been committed to, or having come from marginal positions in the national collective, in a way, never really having been part of it or loyal to it from the start. In a sense, it is a notion that 'a true son of Israel will never do such thing'. In any of these cases, such an individual relegated to marginality, and dismissed as illegitimate. All of these reactions or perceptions derive from the hegemonic nature that Zionism has gained over a large majority of Jews. There is a close-to-religious devout belief in the principles of Zionism described here as *Jewishness* and *security/militarism*, both being parts of a larger *hegemonic Zionist discourse*, which, for its hegemonic nature, sustains a perception it cannot be questioned or challenged. The individual who has rejected Zionism is then dismissed in people's minds without looking into the reasons for that rejection, which in turn, are never considered to exist. This work has offered a deeper look into those reasons, and the results we see is they are based on moral values held by the interviewees even having been socialized as Zionists. None of them is self-hating or anti-Semitic, and all are driven by humanistic values. They did not come from marginal or non-loyal sections of society, rather, many of them are the ones who believing they were doing good, volunteered to combat units, willing to sacrifice their lives for the collective under

severe sense of existential threat. In terms of *Zionist hegemonic discourse*, those soldiers are the bravest most loyal sons of the nation, who used to be few of the most ardent defendants of Zionism. As a central part of this conclusion then, is the legitimacy of the experiences related here, and the great value they hold vis-à-vis the larger Zionist society.

The relevance of this work lies in the relation between identity and conflict, and the role identity plays in sustaining conflict or making conflict resolution possible. However, identity is in great part a result of a series of factors that produce it, and its stability is in a sense, rooted in the *habitus*, that is, in the forgetting of how it was produced. As I have shown, Zionist identity is built in a way its rationale disqualifies the legitimacy of Palestinian rights and sees fit to infringe on them, contributing immensely to generating and sustaining the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. Thus, the changes in identity observed and discussed here represent ways of resisting, and possibly rejecting the dominant inscription of identity, produced by Zionist discourse.

This work presented various relations this process on the individual level establishes with the political situation. I have found some suggestions of relevance of identity to the field of political science by the possibility of explaining political action through identity. Relevance to international relations field relates national identity to public interests, and to influence on foreign policy. Fundamentally, the setting in which this discussion occurs is a question of international relations, since in the modern international system of states, where identity is based on territory, if a group has no state, it has no recognition. It can be seen as both the context that shaped the emergence of Zionism and establishment of Israel, and the difficult situation Palestinians find themselves now. It is in Anderson's (2006) notion of 'imagining' of nations as the foundation of modern national movements that the distortions created by Zionism can be found, and consequently the roots of the identity crisis discussed in this work.

Thus, understanding why these identity changes happened and how, is not a matter that stays isolated in a localized relation of causality. It connects the core of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict to this identity question, as well as the phenomenon of identity change to perspectives of resolution of the conflict.

Considering for a moment the possibility of a new national self-perception becoming widespread, founded on a critical approach to Zionism – post-Zionism or other labels it might have – would allow for a few fundamental things to occur: the Jewish side would be able to take responsibility and free itself from the victimhood trap, recognize it is the strong party in the equation and reduce its perception of threat; It would allow for a strengthening of *Jewishness*, in a sense it will allow for a new kind of *Jewishness* to emerge, different from Ben-Gurion’s politically-motivated *Jewishness*, this one would be one of cultural preservation under coexistence with other cultures and nations. This is a crucial point that may need further clarification. In criticizing Zionism there is a pitfall, which is still difficult to avoid. It is the merging of the notions of *Jewishness* and Zionism into one entity. General opinion, which suffers from the influence of such merged perception of the two, might mistake post-Zionist criticism directed at Zionism, as directed at *Jewishness*, and possibly at Judaism as well. However, critical approach to Zionism is fundamentally based on the separation of the two notions, primarily of Zionism and Judaism, but of Zionism and *Jewishness* as well.

To illustrate, I would like to describe an example of one of the grass-roots organizations I worked with in Jerusalem. Emek Shaveh, Hebrew for ‘common ground’ is an NGO composed of Jewish Israeli archeologists. They take the general public on political tours, showing how archeology has been used politically to argue the connection of modern Jews to ancient Judeans and Israelites, and thus to the land. While Jewish artifacts and ruins have been scientifically warranted, preserved and promoted, other people’s past has been silenced and erased, and this serves as an argument for Jews to own the land. Emek Shaveh’s archeologists advocate for a preservation of the histories of all peoples who have passed over millennia on that land, and the justification for coexistence side by side of various cultures and nations in the present. This serves a solid example of the critical approach this work proposes, which does not call for a dismissal of Judaism nor of *Jewishness*. However ‘constructed’ or ‘imagined’ the modern Jewish identity has been, it now exists, and it encompasses far richer aspects of people’s lives than just its nationalist aspect. *Jewishness* has reached a condition of deep culture, going back to Galtung’s (2000, p.33) description, is “a

web of notions about what is true, good, right, beautiful, sacred.” A dismissal of Jewishness altogether, as requirement for change, would generate far greater new suffering in order to atone for old suffering, possibly contributing to a cycle instead of transcendence. However, I would expect Jewishness would undergo immense changes if the Zionist aspect were ever extricated from it, becoming free to center on Jewish contribution to world society, which has rendered admiration for Jews in the various social realms.

This work has also discussed the relation of identity change processes and conflict resolution. By offering a better understanding of the identity change process, placed in a larger context of social change, politics and the Israeli-Palestinian conflict, the discussion this work brings might be useful to approaches to conflict resolution, transformation and reconciliation. Official political approaches to conflict have proven to lead to dead ends in this matter, when not proving to be facade that wishes to appear as peace-seeking, while motivated by a belligerent identity actually pushing an expansionist agenda. It seems identity drives these ‘peace’ attempts, and at the risk of being redundant I refer again to Ghazi-Bouillon’s (2009, p.144) assertion that “Questions of history and identity lie symbolically at the heart of the peace process, inspiring political participation at both grass-roots and elite levels.” As I discussed progressive initiatives that suggest ‘identity change’ as an approach to conflict transformation, this work also pointed out that while it does agree that this conflict is fundamentally identity-based, primary focus should not be made on the dynamic between Palestinian and Israeli identities, but between Zionist and post-Zionist identities.

Going back to the question this work is posing regarding changes in identity, which inquires why these changes occurred, the answer could be found in the processes by which these individuals became aware of incongruence between their imagined reality, produced by their socialization process, and perceived reality, produced by their direct experience, in addition to the incongruence itself. The reason for the combination of both, process and incongruence is that the individual’s drive for change in identity will derive from the process by which the individual learns about, reflects upon and accepts the

existence of the incongruence. The process is equally or more important than the incongruence itself.

As a final reflection and suggestion for possible further research, I would like to point out once more to the expanded relevance of this study. This work argues that even in face of the strong antagonism with which criticism to Zionism is met, changes such as the ones depicted in the interviews do happen. How should we then approach attempts to reproduce, foster, accelerate, instigate or just influence and raise debate of a critical approach to Zionism? There must be a way to avoid the perception of threat that rises almost instantly due to the nature of Zionist identity, as Sonnenschein, Bekerman, And Horenczyk's (2010) have pointed out. They have shown that perception of threat seems to be diminished in uninational setting, Jewish to Jewish, rather than in bi-national dialogue dynamics, Jewish-Palestinian. However, uninational setting is still not a sufficient condition, since so many Jews who are outspoken about their opposition to Zionism have been labeled self-hating Jews and traitors. If the language or attitude used show any level of aggressiveness, perception of threat will be sparked against a Jew as well, making one lose the in-group vantage. I would ponder on researching initiatives that foster 'identity change' advocated by Israeli and Diaspora Jews in a uninational setting, and additionally using non-violent strategic approaches, technique and language. I have personally been experimenting with techniques such as Marshal Rosenberg's Non-violent Communication (NVC) and other similar tools as the base of these strategies, and have been surprised with the positive results. Surely, pending a good research proposal, this issue would warrant further investigation. I have used only four of the interviews I have collected in my field research, and I have other eight interviews that corroborate the information I presented here. This is still an unfinished work, and I intend to pursue a deeper research regarding identity change and its impact on social change in Israel and Jewish Diaspora in pursuit of a PhD degree, preferably a research that can contribute to initiatives for social change.

So many funds have been funneled into this conflict over the last six decades, and we are nowhere near any transformation, if anything, we are moving away from a possible solution. I would like to refer to a term used by Mary B.

Anderson, author of *Do No Harm* (1999), which is '*local capacities for peace*'. Although she uses it within the context of humanitarian aid and the impact of aid on conflict, I believe international support should be focusing on efforts promoted by these Israeli and Diaspora Jews, which in my view have the single most important capacity of transforming this conflict. The interviews I have conducted allowed me to meet these brave people who had the strength to embrace a change that is both painful and liberating. As they turn away from a strong and all-pervasive embrace of Zionism, they risk losing all that they have ever known, the good alongside the bad. Their efforts to save their society derive from their personal experience and deep understanding that unknowingly, it is possible for one to be part of a violent machine while believing one is righteous. These people within this conflict are in my opinion the *local capacities for peace*, and should receive all the support they need to promote change in their society.

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